
GRAVITATIONAL BENDING OF PHOTONS OR GRAVITATION LENSING OF SPACE-TIME

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Abstract:

One of the most important concept in Geometry is, *distance*, which is the Quanta in geometry, while in Material-Geometry the composition of Opposite, *the Material-Point* which is the Quanta in Chemistry and Physics. *As in Algebra Zero, 0*, is the *Master-key* number for all Positive and Negative numbers and this because their sum and multiplication becomes zero, *and the same* on any coordinate- system where \pm axes pass from zero. The Rolling of Positive \oplus , constituent on the Negative \ominus , constituent, creates the Neutral Material Point which Equilibrium. Angular-Momentum is identical with *Spin* and consists the *First-Discrete-Energy-Monad* which occupies, *Discrete Value and Direction*, in contradiction to the Point which is nothing, *Dimensionless and without any Direction*. *Quaternion* $[(+) \cup (-)] \equiv$ Box B_r which carries the Principal stress σ between A (+), B(-) which σ , as *Centripetal-acceleration* is the minimum Energy becoming from the in-storage AB acceleration and is equal to the *Gravity g*. *The Geometry-Spaces* \rightarrow Explain the How and the WHY, by filling the Gap with a Double-Ocean of the *Pointy-Spinning Material Points*, become from the Stationary-Material-Points, *either these are the Photons or the Electrons*. From the moving-Energy-Storages, as this is Duality Photon with equation $\rightarrow v^{\vec{}} [B^{\vec{}}_o + B^{\vec{}}_n] = |v / \pi^2 \cdot r^2_n| [B^{\vec{}}_n] + |c| B^{\vec{}}_n \leftarrow$ When $c = 0$, then Photon-motion is $|v / \pi^2 \cdot r^2_n| [B^{\vec{}}_n] =$ *The Spin with mass*. The Photons Electric-field is the motion and Magnetic Field is the reaction to this motion, which is thus the mass of Photons (*Newton's third law Action-Reaction*). Because of the Screw-motion of velocityvector on a radius r , allows to apply at a Point C of this circle $[C, r]$ The, (*2-Vectors 3-Poles Mechanism*), of two Perpendicular $CA \perp CP$ and equal vectors for distribution to the two Vectors \oplus Electric field Vector $\rightarrow F = q \cdot E$, and the \ominus Magnetic field Vector $\rightarrow F^{\vec{}} = q \cdot v^{\vec{}} \times B^{\vec{}}$. The Two-Perpendicular and equal Vectors, CA, CP, Slide on (O,OA) circle and through the Three Poles, A, C, P, carry the Stress $\pm \sigma = w^2 \cdot B / v$, of Square ACPC'', To the Two Equal and Opposite Squares |COAB|, |COPB'| for Halve Area - Stress-Energy

Acceleration of Gravity $g \equiv \pm \sigma$, is altered Locally by changing the Principal-stress σ with an Local-uniform-Pressure $\rightarrow \mathbf{g}_L \equiv g \mathbf{k} = g \cdot [\text{Force/Area}] = G$, i.e. The minimum Local - Energy acceleration is the known, *Universal Gravitational-constant* $G = g \mathbf{k} = \mathbf{k}_E g = \mathbf{k}_L \sigma$, for *Macrocosm and Microcosm*, It was proved that *Constant G, is the mechanism* for the **First-kick-Start** on the *Granular-Energy-monad*, g , which Acts in the lightest and less-mass Particle and which is Hydrogen. The Electron-Nutation-Energy due to g , effect is the minimum frequency $f_N \equiv f_R = 2,8398447 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and which so exists in all Atoms. This Energy in Hydrogen-Cave as **E-M, Conductor** is the Resonance frequency between all Atoms, *and because of Common Hydrogen*, Bond to Molecules and all Compounds in this Cosmos. In this **E-M, Conductor** is stored the Work = The Nutation-Energy produced, and is called, <The Hydrogen Bracket Hook > [BH]. These [BH] are the Hands and Brain of Atoms and Compounds. The Gravitational Force F_G between Photon's velocity vector \vec{c} and an **Object**, is Proportional to their masses m_c and m_o and Inversely Proportional to the square of their distance d_{co} . This Centripetal Force F_G Produces a New velocity vector \vec{c}_0 which is added to \vec{c} vector. Their Resultant velocity vector \vec{v}_R forms an angle w to the \vec{c} velocity vector, which is the **Photons' - Bending**.

Keywords: The Gravitation Bending of the Dual Photon.

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PREFASE :

- 1..The Electron-Nutation in Hydrogen cave Produces Energy due to g effect , as an minimum frequency $f_n \equiv 2,8398447 \cdot 10^{10}$ H and thus exists in all Atoms . This Energy in Hydrogen-Cave is an Electrical -Magnetic Conductor, which is The Pin of Atom-Plug and enters Into the other Atom-Sockets , which are the Orbit-Bracket-Hooks . These are the Hands of Atoms , i.e. \rightarrow **The Atoms-Plug** , by Placing their Pins into the other Atoms Drains \equiv Holes , and so is done that what we say Bonding .
- 2.. Because of the Resonance frequency between all Atoms , and because of the Common Hydrogen , so Atoms Bond by Pinning and form Molecules and all Compounds in this Cosmos . This is Possible because the Periodic-System of Atoms is NOW modulated into 4 New - Categories with Only-One Criterion , which is **The Number of (\pm) Energy - Conductors in Atoms** , related to their Stability .
- 3..The first Solid (4 Points not coinciding) is The **Tetrahedron** , and the first Material Space for the Two elements (+), (-), are (4 x 2 = 8 Positions for Electrons) **The-Cube** , i.e. the Tetrahedron is Into the Cube and Into its **Ex - Sphere** , and this because the Circles on Tetrahedron exist on same Sphere .
- 4.. When 1-8 Electrons \ominus are Placed on the Cube's Vertices , and into this **Onion -System** , then **Automatically** are formed the , 1 - 4 **Energy-Conductors** , where issues $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] = [p \leftrightarrow e] = [\text{Atom-Plug} = + \text{ Electric Vector} \leftrightarrow - \text{Magnetic Vector} \equiv \text{Drain} \equiv \text{Hole}]$, and are the **Actions** between Opposite . With this New modulation [The ,1 , 2 ,3 , 4 , Energy-Conductors \equiv Atoms-Four Fundamental frequencies] , Conductors exist on System and **ARE ACTIVE** + as \rightarrow **The-Electric-Vectors** \leftarrow and simultaneously **PASSIVE** \equiv Drains (-) as \rightarrow **The-Magnetic Vectors** \equiv Holes \leftarrow . The Zero-State Conductors are those whose 8 Cube-Positions are all filled with electrons . The Multiple - Plug-Pins Atoms can **Plug** all the less number Electrons - Atoms and can **Be-Plugged** from all the greater number Electrons-Atoms .*With these Four modulations are formed all Atoms and their Compounds* , as these are the Mechanisms of , Water , the CELLS , RNA , DNA , CANCER , and everything in this Universe .
- 5..In the same way , is that where an 110 Volt Refrigerator Can't-Plug into 220 Volt Socket and this because are different in construction , the same to Atoms-Plug which differ to the Number and the Length of their Pins . Hydrogen is the Multiple-Plug-Pins Atom which can Plug all Atoms and itself.

6..The Conservation of Energy in Catalyze and The Sun-Light :

a) ..**The Geometry-Mechanism** $\left\{ \begin{matrix} -A & \text{::} \cup \\ +Z \uparrow & \left[\oplus \frac{\text{::}}{2} + \ominus \frac{\text{::}}{2} \right] \mathbf{D} \end{matrix} \right\}$ of Conductors $\overline{ZA}, \overline{ZD}$, carries motion \vec{E} in Square $|ZA \times ZD|$ of Plane Z,A,D from Z-Position to 2-Half-Area Equilibrium-Squares on ZD Diameter $\Rightarrow \left[\oplus \frac{\text{::}}{2} + \ominus \frac{\text{::}}{2} \right] \mathbf{P}$, at Perpendicular-Position $\overline{ZA} \perp \overline{ZD}$, i.e. The Two-Perpendicular Vectors , $ZA \perp CP$ Slide on (O,OA) circle and through the Three Poles , Z ,A ,D , carry the Stress σ , of Square $ZA \times ZD'$, to Two Equal and Opposite Stress-Squares $|ZOAD|, |ZOPD|$ of Halve Area -Stress Conservation , where the **Neutral-Points** $\mathbf{D} \equiv \mathbf{P}$, + $\equiv \left[\oplus \frac{\text{::}}{2} \right]$ and , - $\equiv \left[\ominus \frac{\text{::}}{2} \right]$, are the **Still Halves** at , $\pm = 0$, Positions .Fig-2 . It is the **< Markos 2-Vectors 3-Poles Mechanism >**

b).. **IN Vibrating-Mechanism** , masses carry motion as , **Eigenvectors** , at the equilibrium Positions , which are the **Eigenvectors** , at the Still-Positions . The Orthogonal Property of Normal-Modes for **Eigenvalues** and **Eigenvectors Moulds** is the Process of Equilibrium , and Still-Positions as Fig-2-

$$\rightarrow [Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = \mathbf{D}] \equiv \left\{ \begin{matrix} A - & \text{::} \cup \\ \uparrow \mathbf{Z} + & \left[\oplus \frac{\text{::}}{2} + \ominus \frac{\text{::}}{2} \right] \mathbf{D} \end{matrix} \right\} \equiv \{ \pm [\times] \frac{-\oplus/2}{+\ominus/2} + \downarrow \leftrightarrow \uparrow \} \leftarrow$$

c).. **IN Chemistry-Mechanism** , NATURE occupies as first ,The Compound **Glucose-Oxide Activity** $H_2 O_2 \equiv O \frac{4}{4} H \frac{2}{2} = O \frac{4}{4} \times H \frac{2}{2} = O \frac{1}{3} H \frac{2}{0} = ES \frac{3 \vec{E}}{3 \vec{M}} \rightarrow , T \frac{6 = 4+2}{6 = 4+2} , X. Inn \frac{3 \rightarrow \vec{E} = 1+2 = 6/2}{3 \rightarrow \vec{M} = 1+2 = 6/2}$, which conserves the Atoms-activities , where the Remaining energy X. Out $\frac{\text{Halve } 6=3\vec{E} \rightarrow 3+0 \rightarrow +\text{Electric} - \text{Vectors}}{\text{Halve } 6=3\vec{M} \leftarrow 3+0 \rightarrow -\text{Magnetic-Vectors}}$, and

Still as Halves Energies at \rightarrow (+) Positions $O \frac{1}{3} H \frac{2}{0} = \times \left[\oplus \frac{\text{::}}{2} + \ominus \frac{\text{::}}{2} \right] , O \frac{3}{1} H \frac{0}{2}$, to (-) Positions \leftarrow

Conservation of Energy as **Two-Still-Halves** is for $C_6 H_{13} N_1 O_3 \equiv C \frac{1}{18} \times N \frac{3}{2} \times O \frac{6}{3} H \frac{13}{0} = ST \frac{23 = \frac{46}{2}}{23 = \frac{46}{2}}$ and Generally to all Compounds that Still at Halve or less from Electric-Magnetic Vectors .

Half-Energy (HE) = $T/2 \rightarrow \vec{E} \rightleftharpoons = 23.[e^+ = 0,3090169] = 7,1073887 \text{ eV} = 675, 2019 \text{ kJ/mol.}$
Incorporated Energy (IE) = $ES \rightarrow \vec{E} \rightleftharpoons = 23.[e^+ = 0,3090169] = 7,10738 \text{ eV} = 675, 2019 \text{ kJ/mol.}$
Total Energy (TE) = $T \rightarrow \vec{E} \rightleftharpoons = 46.[e^+ = 0,3090169] = 14,214777 \text{ eV} = 1 350,4038 \text{ kJ/mol.}$

A.. : ADDITIONS TO THE PRIOR :

- 1...**The Objective Reality** is composed of two elements , that of **Distance** , *The Space ds* , and that of **Motion** , *or else the called Energy* , and it is the content of all sciences [32]
- 2... **The Euclidean-Geometry** describes the Space only but Not the Energy as is *motion* .[48] .
- 3...The Solution of all the Unsolved-Ancient-Greek-Problems [50] opened the way to the **Material-Geometry** [54] which Incorporates the Motion \rightarrow In-Space as $(\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus) \equiv 0$, [61] . **The Space exists** in Energy - Caves as **Energy-Quantum-Quantities** [39] , while Motion or **Energy exist** in Caves as an **Confined - Stationary-wave** which is either Static or an moving Energy-Storage or an Energy-Box [68] . The Any-Two Opposites (+) , (-) exist in Nature and are found everywhere from \rightarrow Zero-Point (0) $\equiv [+ = -]$ or as $(+ A) + (- A) = 0$ in E-Geometry and $\rightarrow [0] = [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] \equiv f_n$, $[\oplus \leftarrow ds \rightarrow \ominus] \equiv ds$ in Material-Geometry , to the aperon , $\pm \infty$, where \rightarrow **The Space $\equiv ds$, is the nodes distance** , and **motion exist as a Vibration \leftarrow** [52] .
- 4...**The PrimaryMaterial-Point** is composed of Infinite - Material - Points in the Two-Aperon which consist a Huge Magnet with Infinite Parallel-lines , on where the \oplus constituent moves on them the Newton-Gravitational-constant G-force Periodically to the \ominus constituent [82-86] .
- 5... **Gravitational-Force G** is Acting in the **Beyond - Planck - Cave** , and on the light Velocity Vector \vec{c} , creates Electron-Charge $\bar{q}_{\text{Electron}} = \frac{G}{c\sqrt{2}}$ and the Material-Points $\bar{q}_{\text{Photon}} = \frac{G}{\sqrt{2}.f}$ while by effecting on the **Whole-Planck-Cave** $L_p \equiv e^{i \cdot (-5\pi/2) \cdot 10}$, creates the Pointy - Gravity Force as this is the **Ocean of Spins \bar{g}** , and which Oriented-Spins , **Originate Gravity g** and the **Electron \bar{e}** [72] . Light-Velocity \vec{c} acting on a-cave , $r = \frac{h}{c.Z_c} \neq L_p$ originates the **Hydrogen-cave**.
- 6...**The Rotation** of the only Two Elements , $[\oplus \cup \cup \ominus]$, Up or Down in the Material-Point-circles Originates the Spins , $\pm \frac{1}{2}$, ± 1 , $\pm \frac{1}{2}$, for All-Particles **Fermions or Bosons** which become from the above Three-States of motions , just by Adding their Spins [36] .
 Linear Motion $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$ of Breakage $[\pm \vec{c} . s^2_m]$ in cave { M-Point = $d s_m = e^{i \cdot (\frac{N\pi}{2})} b = 10^{-N} = \pm \infty \text{ m}$ } as velocity , $v = w r = 2\pi r . f = \sigma \Phi$, in the Great and Small circles of Glue-Bond rotation , **creates the Three-States of frequencies** $f_{\pm 1/2} = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{8\pi r}$, $f_{\pm 1} = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r}$, $f_{\pm 1/2} = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{8\pi r}$ and the energy $E = h f_m$, because from **Angular-Momentum $\vec{B} = \frac{2L}{w} = \frac{2L}{2\pi f} = [\frac{2L}{2\pi}] \cdot [\frac{1}{f}] = \frac{\text{Constant}}{2\pi} [\frac{1}{f_m}] = \text{SPIN}$** [70]
- 7...**When the Unit-Quantum-Energy** in Planck-length is equal to the Stress of Gravity g , and enters the minimum-cave a as is the **Critical-Unit-Energy** in orbit , then is measured an frequency f_p which gives the **Least-Unit-Energy-cave** and which is that of **Hydrogen-Cave H** , [81] , as is the Energy equations , $r = \frac{h}{c.Z_c}$, $g \cdot r^3 \cdot f_p^2 = 1$, and from where f_p is as $E = h f_p = 13,6 \text{ eV}$.
- 8...**When the Unit-Quantum-Energy** , k , in Planck-length is equal to the Stress of Gravity , g , and frequency f_e becomes from Hydrogen Least-Unit-Energy = $\pi \cdot g$, then , **Reaction = mass** , is that of the **Electron Cave** , e , as the Kepler-equation , $4 \pi^2 f_e^2 \cdot m_e = k = \pi g$ and $m_e = g / [4\pi f_e^2]$, [82]
- 9...**The Rotation** around the \oplus constituent , of the Confined-Electron \ominus constituent in the Potential Energy of Hydrogen-cave , which consists a configuration of masses m_p and of Charges q_e , **Originates** , an **Uniform-Magnetic - field \vec{B}_L** , that of **Atom** , the Spin of Atom connected with that of Electron-Spin , and **Forms** an Harmonic Oscillator with a Natural Frequency f_N with the less Damping-factor by Increasing of the **Potential Energy** in loop due to the Nutation-motion .

Since Electron is continually- oscillating with this Nutation - frequency f_N , so Produces an **oscillating Magnetic-field** \vec{B}_N , which in turn is the source of an oscillating **Electric-field** \vec{E}_N , which implies the Regeneration each other and which is a **Propagating Electromagnetic-Wave** related as $\vec{E}_N = \vec{B}_N \cdot c$. and with an Phase difference $[\sin \phi = \frac{B}{\sqrt{B_N^2 + |E_N|^2}} = \frac{1}{c^2 + 1}]$. [86]

10..This Resonance - frequency f_R is Independent of the **Electron's speed and radius**, therefore Proportion allows the **Bonding between Atom-caves** which contain a Formation as a Heap of Masses and of Charges . This is the New Manuscript [102] in which is shown the Programming of this Heap-Inertia . In a Proper-Stationary-Magnet in which the **Rotational-motion** becomes a Linear - Oscillation , the Centripetal Force with velocity vector , is succeeded with this way a clear **Magnetic-Resonance-Imaging** as are [The MRI , MEDIA] , [86] .

11...Constant force G is effecting on **Gravity**, g , and in turn g is acting on Electron \bar{e} , in the Hydrogen-cave which Originates the axis-Nutation-motion and which in this Precession is the **→ Cyclotron-Resonance-frequency ←** $f_R = \sqrt[4]{\frac{1}{4\pi^2 m_e r^3}}$ of cave , r , and the produced-Energy \equiv motion is stored in the Orbit as an New **Uniform-Magnetic-field** $\vec{B}_F = \left| \frac{2\pi M_T}{Q_T} \right| f_R$ independent of **velocity and cave**, and which becomes The **Bond** between the **Atoms** to be **Molecules**, i.e. **Bonds are the Magnetic-lines of the Uniform-field**. [80]

12...During Nutation of Electron-SPIN, and because of the Eternal-Varying-Velocity motion in Orbit Precesses, the **Produced-Work** of $[\oplus = \text{Proton}, \ominus = \text{Electron}]$ is Conserved in the **Nucleus-Orbit Magnet**, as the **Nucleus-Magnetic-Moment** and which is influenced by Any External-Magnetic-field . The continually Conserved Energy becomes the frequency $f_N = f_R$ and is **Resonated to the Electron-Spin**, OR to Any **Set External-Magnetic-Field-moment**.

13...The Work Produced by the \oplus , constituent in a Conductor $|AK_A|$, is the Work done from a Force x Displacement $\rightarrow A \equiv \oplus \rightarrow K_A \equiv \ominus \leftarrow \equiv |Q_{AK_A}| \equiv Z_{AK_A} \equiv |e| \cdot |AK_A|$.

In an Conductor, $A|\oplus$ d $\ominus|K_A$, **The Quantity** $|Q_{AK_A}|$ **is an Energy-Vector** on Line-Vector $|AK_A|$ and is Perpendicular to Spin \vec{S}_{K_A} , *the Inverse motion*, while the Two Vectors **form an**,

Line -Vector- Cruise - missile, which is Self - Spin-Propelled as an Helicopter. Propagation needs an Orthogonal -3-Vectors System [87] conjoined Electric and Magnetic-fields **Therefore**, all **The Elementary-Particles** are **missile of Short-action**, **Cruise or Ballistic**.

These occupy, **mass, charge, Spin**, and are Not excitation of Any field, in contrast to **Photon** which is a **3 -Vectors - System** with Magnetic-field and of **Two-Quantum-Energy-Storages** as $\vec{v} \cdot [\vec{f}_n + f_n] \equiv \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^3} \cdot |\vec{B}_n| + |\vec{e}| \cdot f_n$ with different Frequency [66]. **It is Proved the first term to be the Mass of Photon**, mass $m_{ph} = 8,846562 \cdot 10^{-21}$ Kg. (2A3). In case that Line-Vector $|AK_A|$ is analyzed into Two-Line Vectors as $|AK_{A-x}|$ and $|AK_{A-y}|$, then **at Point A** issues for **Energy - Vectors** $|AK_{A-x}| = |AK_{A-y}|$ and, directed as $|AK_{A-x}| \perp |AK_{A-y}|$, and form the **Resultant Vector** $|AK_A|$ with New direction.

As in Electricity, where **The Magnetic field created by the flow of current in a Conductor**, represents The Perpendicular-Lines of Forces, **Similarly** Material-Vector $|AK_{A-x}|$ carries the Centripetal **Maximum Conjugate-Force** $|AK_{A-y}|$, from **Screwdriver** Inscribed to, $|AK_{A-x}|$, $|AK_{A-y}|$ Circle $\equiv \pi \left[\frac{|AK_A|}{2} \right]^2 = \pi \frac{|AK_A|^2}{4}$, to the Circumscribed-circle $\pi \left[\frac{|AK_A| \sqrt{2}}{2} \right]^2 = \pi \frac{|AK_A|^2}{2}$, which is equal to **CMNH**

Square, The Anti-Quadrature, and the Double - Area circle, $\pi \cdot [|AK_A|]^2 = 2 \cdot \left[\pi \frac{|AK_A|^2}{2} \right]$ exists on

Point A. This Property of **Vectors at Point A** issues for any Point, K_A , which can have a **Screwdriver Material - Vector - $|AK_A|$ { Only the 3 -Vectors - System Propagates }**.

The Neutral Material Point balances and Equilibrium by Division. as mode

$$\rightarrow [Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = D] \equiv \uparrow Z + \left[\oplus \frac{\ddot{}}{2} + \ominus \frac{\ddot{}}{2} \right] D \equiv \{ \pm [\otimes] \frac{-\oplus/2}{+\ominus/2} + \downarrow \leftrightarrow \uparrow \} \leftarrow [96]$$

As in Electricity, **The flow of current** in a Conductor creates a Magnetic -field Perpendicular to the Conductor, **likewise** the Attack of \oplus to \ominus constituent, creates all above in $[\oplus \ominus] \equiv$

$$A[\oplus (d = |AK_A|) \ominus]K_A, \text{ Conductor. The Spin} = \frac{h}{2\pi} = 2 \cdot [wr]^2, \text{ where Conductor } r = |AK_A| \text{ and,}$$

$$\vec{B} = \frac{2L}{w} = \frac{2L}{2\pi f} = \left[\frac{2L}{2\pi} \right] \cdot \left[\frac{1}{f} \right] = \frac{4r \cdot (hf)}{(1 \mp \sqrt{5}) \cdot \sigma} = \left[\frac{h}{2\pi} \right] = \frac{\text{Constant}}{2\pi} \left[\frac{1}{f_m} \right] = \frac{c^4}{2\pi} \left(\frac{2\pi r}{\sigma \cdot \Phi} \right) = (c^4 \frac{2\pi r}{2\pi r \cdot c}) = c^3 = [wr]^2 = \text{The SPIN}$$

This Screw-Action is executed as Rotation and Halve -Division $\rightarrow \cup \vdots \vdash \rightarrow [\oplus \frac{\ddot{}}{2} + \ominus \frac{\ddot{}}{2}] \equiv$ Division, on [MM]-Mechanism. **The Rolling** of Positive \oplus , constituent on the Negative \ominus , constituent, in PNS Space { Planck-Cave $L_P \equiv e^{i \cdot (-5\pi/2)} \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ m} < \text{PNS-Space} < \text{Gravity Space} = 10^{-62} \text{ m}$ } creates the Neutral Material Point, $\rightarrow [Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = D] \equiv$ Photons motion.

1a.. The Forces, Stresses, velocities and The Spin Relations :

Figure -1-: The Energy-Space, Stress-Strain in wavelength $\lambda = 2r$, of a moving Photon :

- For area $A = 0$, the acting Force F which is an Energy-Space-cave, is manifested into the Transverse Principal stresses, σ , τ , and then as an **Moving-Storage** (1)-(2) is transported as Velocity-Vector \vec{v} .
 The force $F = \sigma \cdot A \rightarrow \vec{p}$ vector = $M \cdot \vec{v} = (m \lambda) \cdot \vec{v} = [m \cdot c \cdot T] \cdot \vec{v} = [m \cdot c / f] \cdot \vec{v} = [m / f] \cdot c \cdot \vec{v}$, i.e. **Force $F \rightarrow$ becomes a Velocity-Vector \vec{v}** or, a **Force as Stress σ** , which enters in Space Φ as $[\sigma \Phi]$ and becomes the frequency $\vec{f} = \frac{\sigma \cdot \Phi}{2\pi \cdot r_n}$, existing as the Force $F = \sigma \cdot A = \left[\frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi} \right] \cdot A = w \cdot r \cdot \left[\frac{A}{\Phi} \right] = \vec{v} \cdot \left[\frac{A}{\Phi} \right]$, which Force, F , becomes the moving Storage $\left[\frac{A}{\Phi} \right]$, with velocity $\vec{v} = \left[\frac{F \cdot \Phi}{A} \right] = F \cdot \left[\frac{\Phi}{A} \right]$.
- For area $A > 0$, Force F which is an Energy-Space-cave, diffuses as **Electromagnetic Radiation** in the Principal stresses $\pm \sigma_1, \pm \sigma_2, \pm \sigma_3$, which is **The Passage** through which Forces travel in moving Solids. From the theory of Elasticity the equilibrium of a surface - Configuration in an Isotropic material obey the equilibrium equation $\rightarrow \mu \cdot \nabla^2 u + (\lambda + \mu) \cdot \nabla \cdot [\nabla \cdot u] = 0 \leftarrow [26]$
- For area $A < 0$, because Force F is an Energy-Space-Cave which at first Passes from the Zero area $A = 0$ and becomes a velocity-vector \vec{v} . This velocity - vector \vec{v} is entering any trough, **Potential**, and is transformed to an Energy-Rim, as these are the Orbits of Electrons. Because Photon is one of the moving-energy-stores, when it enters a cave $L_s < L_P$, then the cave Becomes Discrete Energy - Packet which is the Rim L_v .

4.. For area $0 < A < \infty$, *The Extreme case, where Surface is interchanged as line or as an line Segment, and is the same as the infinite small, ds, in Calculus*, where stresses $\sigma_2 = 0$ and τ_{12} are very small, *it is the equation of Stresses*, $\sigma_{1,2}$, and from Cauchy,

$\sigma_1 / 2 = \pm (\frac{1}{2}) \cdot \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + 4 \cdot \sigma_2^2} = \sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2$, which is the *Golden-ratio-Pattern* Φ , of the Material - Point as a Type of a vanishing - Shear, due to layers laterally shifted. [26] This minimum quantized Energy σ , was Proved that is going out the Material Point as an acceleration and creates the Stationary-gravity g as frequency f_n acting on Spin as $\rightarrow S_{pA} \cdot r^4 \leftarrow$ The Proof for Stress is from **Centripetal Force** $\rightarrow F_c = mv^2/r = 1 \cdot (wr)^2/r = w^2 \cdot r = \pm \sigma = (2\pi \cdot f_1)^2 \cdot r = \sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 \equiv \frac{\sigma \cdot \Phi}{2}$

From Kinetic Energy $E = \frac{mv^2}{2} = \frac{1 \cdot w^2 \cdot r^2}{2}$ then $w^2 = \frac{2E}{r^2}$, and from $E = \frac{[(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma r]^2}{2}$ the $f_n = \frac{[(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma]}{4\pi r}$

From Spin $\bar{S} = \bar{B} = \pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot f$, then $\rightarrow 2 \cdot \bar{B} = \pi r^3 \cdot \Phi \cdot \sigma$, and **frequency-force** f_n , orients Spin

\bar{S} to \bar{B} as $\bar{g} = f_n \times \bar{B} = |f_n| \times |\bar{B}| \cdot \sin \theta = \frac{[(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma]}{4\pi r} \cdot \pi r^3 \cdot \Phi \cdot \sigma = \frac{[\sigma^2 r^2 (1+\sqrt{5}) \Phi]}{8} = \left[\frac{\sigma \cdot r \cdot \Phi}{2} \right]^2 \dots \dots \dots (g)$

Equation (g) which is the Gravity constant g , is the Permeable Path for inner stress σ , to *Pass the Material's-Point* a surface $4\pi r^2/3$ and to *expenditure its Energy*. The same exists also to the **Electromagnetic force** which is *associated with a fundamental Property* of matter which is the *Electric-Charge* and which is *a clue to The ubiquity of Electromagnetism*.

From equation of Gravitation $G = E = h \cdot f_n = \left[\frac{c \cdot r^3}{a} \right] \cdot [g_L k_L] = g \cdot k_E = g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv \sigma \times \Phi^3 = (2\pi f r) \frac{A}{\Phi} = \bar{v} \frac{A}{\Phi} = \bar{c} \frac{A}{\Phi}$, seems that the two constants, $g \cdot k_E = \sigma \times \Phi^3$, are related, i.e. *act each other through Local coefficients or through Field-lines*, called the Medium or Permissible Path which is as that of

Stress relation $\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi} = \frac{w r}{\Phi} = \frac{v}{\Phi} = \frac{G}{\Phi^3}$, a velocity vector c in the Unit-Space Φ related to G .

It was shown that the first Path is Gravity g , and Original Field-lines of Force, G , are distorted by these *Charges, the Local-coefficients, the Layers* following the Newton's laws.

The Original Field-lines terminate at the surface on one side of the Medium, and new field lines originate from the other side of it. It was shown that the Momentum vector, \bar{B} , is equal to spin S , because it is following the *Stationary - Wave - Nodes - Principle in the Material-Point*, creates the minimum quantized Energy which is conserved in lobes. This Property is extended also to the Number of lobes as well as to, π , number as velocity $\{v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c\}$ which is the minimum Number relating Lines and Surfaces. Analogous happens in equation (c) when $v = c$, and $\rightarrow r = c$.

From Inner-velocity equation $v = w \cdot r = (2\pi / T) \cdot r = 2\pi \cdot f_1 \cdot r$, and from fundamental frequency f_1 , of wavelength $\lambda = c \cdot T = c / f_1$, the energy cave $r = n \cdot [\lambda/2]$, and then $r = n \cdot (c / 2f_1)$ and from velocity $v = w r = 2\pi \cdot f_1 \cdot [n \cdot c / 2f_1] = n \cdot \pi \cdot c$ or $v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c \dots \dots \dots (\pi)$

Equation (π) shows that velocities in lobes are, $n \cdot \pi$ times that of light, following, π , number in circle i.e. *in Material-Points exist velocities multi-times that of light* and the minimum *Surface-constant, Unit π* , or the *Growth of the velocity-vectors* occurs in lobes by following the logarithm laws of Energy-constant c , which is acting on Space constant π . From velocity, $v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c$, is seen that *light-velocity, c, is the Quantum of Unit-velocity in Planck's length*. The Why velocity c and π , is such in [42-51-63] and in present.

Kepler's Laws \rightarrow Explain **How** the Planets move around the Sun But **NOT the WHY** they move.

Newton's Laws \rightarrow Explain the **WHY**, which is by filling this Gap by a Force $F = G \cdot m_1 \cdot m_2 / r^2$ acting instantly between the Bodies that are moving around each other But **NOT** their Nature and **NOT** the **HOW** Force is Acting on them.

Markos-Spaces \rightarrow Explain the **How** and the **WHY**, by filling the Gap with a **Double-Ocean** of the **Pointy-Spinning Material-Points**, which become from the **Stationary-Material-Points**, either are **Photons or the Electrons**, and from the **moving-Energy-Storages**, that of **Duality-Photons**. From

Photon equation $\bar{v} \cdot \left[\frac{\bar{f}_n}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} + f_n \right] \equiv \left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} \right| \cdot \left[\bar{B}_n \right] + \bar{c} \cdot f_n$, **When $c = 0$** , **Photon-motion is** $\left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} \right| \cdot \left[\bar{B}_n \right] \equiv$

The Spin with mass - The reaction to its motion. The two frequencies which Orientate and Re-orientate the Stationary -Spins and explain the **HOW** and the **WHY** all motions follow the **ubiquity** of the

Electromagnetism , starting from the Primary Material - Points , the *Photons* , which through the **Golden – Ratio -frequency-Growth** effect and conserve the Whole of this Natural-World from microcosm to macrocosm .

The Recent Annex relating the Greatest-Pressure-Level denotes the Pressure in the filling-Gap of Space-Energy reality . It has been done an effort of the Cosmic-Particles-Origination . [95]
It was shown that the **2 -Line- Vectors–Ballistic-missile** , is a Self Spin-Propelled as the Photon-charge

$$\bar{q}_{\text{Photon Charge}} = \frac{G}{\sqrt{2}.f} = \frac{G.h}{\sqrt{2}.E} = \frac{[6,6736923 \cdot 10^{-11}].[6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34}]}{\sqrt{2} \cdot E = 1} = 3,127 \cdot 10^{-44} \text{ C} .$$

The **2 - Line- Vectors-Cruise-missile** , is a Self Spin-Propelled as the Electron-charge ,

$$\bar{q}_{\text{Electron Charge}} = \frac{G}{\sqrt{2}.c} = \frac{6,6736923 \cdot 10^{-11}}{1,41429 \cdot 2,9979346 \cdot 10^8} = 1,575 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C} . \quad \text{which agrees with}$$

that of Coulomb's charge \bar{q} . From Stress relation $\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi} = \frac{w r}{\Phi} = \frac{v}{\Phi} = \frac{G}{\Phi^2}$, $\bar{v} = w_c \cdot r$
 $= \sigma_1 \cdot \Phi$, where σ_1 is given in Pascal=Pa . , 1kPa = 10^3 .Pa , 1MPa = 10^6 .Pa , 1GPa = 10^9 .Pa

Because the motion of the Photon is Helical , *Screw* , and the Electric-field E , alternates with the Magnetic field B , the Stress σ is applied to its rotation cycle . In each Phase Stress is divided to two halve circles for equilibrium as . $[\pi.r^2] = \mathfrak{S} = \left[\oplus \frac{F}{2} + \ominus \frac{F}{2} \right] CB^2$, where $A = \pi.r^2$

2a...The Origination of Stresses σ , in Vectors : [84]

The Rotation of , \oplus constituent around the \ominus constituent , creates a minimum quantized Energy as the Stress σ , and was proved that is going out the Material Point , *because of the Skin effect* , as acceleration and creates the Stationary gravity g as f_n , acting on Spin as $S_{PA}.r^4$. [70]

From the work relation $\rightarrow W = 2E = B w = J.w^2$, or $2E = 2\pi f \bar{B} = w \cdot \bar{B} \leftarrow$

$$F_{\text{photon}} = \frac{[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]}{r^2} = \frac{[\sigma.\sigma]}{r^2} = \left| \frac{\sigma}{r} \right|^2 = \left| \frac{2\pi f}{\Phi} \right|^2 = \left| \frac{v}{r.\Phi} \right|^2 = \left| \frac{c}{r.\Phi} \right|^2$$
 , in the same Box B_e , since the Angular momentum \equiv Spin $\equiv \bar{B} = \frac{\pi r^3 \sigma}{4} [1 + \sqrt{5}] = \left| \frac{\pi r^3 \Phi \sigma}{2} \right| = \left[\frac{\pi r^3 c}{2} \right] = \pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot f$, as the Orbit-Forces ($\lambda = r$) .

The Centripetal Force is equal to Stress σ , so $F_c = mv^2 / r = 1.(wr)^2/r = w^2 \cdot r = \pm \sigma = (2\pi.f_1)^2 \cdot r = \sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = [\Phi.\sigma]^2$, and since mass is $m = \frac{\sigma}{w^2.r} = \frac{\sigma}{w.v} = \frac{\bar{B}}{r.v}$ then , $\pm \sigma = \frac{w^2 \cdot \bar{B}}{v}$ which is a relation between the Stress , Momentum and the light-velocity \bar{v} , since **Photon-motion is** $\left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 r^4 n} \right| \cdot \boxed{\bar{B}_n} \equiv$ Spin Energy trapped in the Magnetic cavity contributes to the effective " Rest mass " and for Photon System. Since for gamma-rays $f_\gamma = 6.10^{29}$ Hz the Magnetic energy is the Total energy E , so Energy of Photon $E = hf = 6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34} \cdot 6.10^{29} = 3,975647 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ J} = \frac{1}{2} m.v^2$, and derived reaction to the motion

$$m_{\text{Photon}} = \frac{2.E}{v^2} = \frac{2.[3,97565 \cdot 10^{-4}]}{[2,998 \cdot 10^8]^2} = 8,846562 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ Kg} . \quad (2a1) \quad \text{i.e. In case of}$$

The Gamma-ray Photons **Energy E = 3,975647 . 10⁻⁴ J** (2a2) and the ,

$$\text{mass } m_{\text{ph}} = 8,846562 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ Kg} . \quad (2a3)$$

From relation , $f_n = \frac{\sigma.\Phi}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma.\Phi.E}{w.r.h} = \frac{\sigma.\Phi.B}{2.r.h}$, related to Spin \bar{B} , Stress σ and cave r ,

$$\text{then Spin } \bar{B} = \frac{2h.r.f_n}{\sigma\Phi = \bar{c}} . \text{ From relation } \bar{c} = \sigma.\Phi \text{ then}$$

$$\text{Stress } \sigma = \bar{c} / \Phi = 2,997 \cdot 10^8 / 1,6180339 = 1,8522479 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Kg/m}^2 . \quad (2a4)$$

$$\text{Magnetic field } \bar{B} = \frac{8.r^2.f_n}{n.\sigma} = \frac{8.[610^{-29}]^2 \cdot [610^{-29}]}{1.[1,852866 \cdot 10^8]} = 9,3260926 \cdot 10^{-93} \text{ Tesla} . \quad (2a5)$$

From [31] Elementary monads $(s + \bar{v} \nabla i)^{1/w} = |zo|^{-w} \cdot e^{[-i.(\phi+2k\pi).w]}$, where $\cos.\phi = s / |zo|$, and

for Rotated Energy case where $s = 0$ and $\cos.\varphi = 0$ exists for angle $\varphi = \pi/2$, quaternion $(s+\sqrt{v} \nabla i)^{1/w}$ as dimension Power $w = b$ as $\rightarrow e^{-i.(\pi/2+2k\pi).w} \leftarrow$ meaning the *Basis of Space-Energy Universe*. Using the Euler's formula to $e^{-i.(\pi/2+2k\pi).w}$, then the *Space-Energy Universe is of Wave-form* as $e^{-i.(\pi/2+2k\pi).w} = \cos[-(\pi/2 + 2k\pi).w] + i . \sin[-(\pi/2 + 2k\pi).w]$. i.e.

1,,,For $k = 0$ exists the **Absolute - Space** as $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$ i.e. **Energy = 0**, in $e^{-i.(\pi/2+2k\pi).w}$, and is

$$L_v = e^{-i.(\pi/2).w} = e^{-i.(\frac{\pi}{2}).b} = e^{-15,7079} = 1,78118 . 10^{-7} \text{ m, the Neutral Cave as Standing-Wave.}$$

2,,,For $k = 1$ exists the **Prior Absolute - Space** with motion = Energy as **Stationary -Wave** . and

$$L_p = e^{-i.(\pi/2+2k\pi).w} = e^{-i.(\frac{\pi}{2}+2\pi).b} = e^{-i.(\frac{5\pi}{2}).10} = e^{-78,5398} = 8,906 . 10^{-35}, \text{ the Planck's cave.}$$

For base $e = 2,71828$ and $k = 1$ then, $L_p = e^{i.(-5\pi/2).10}$ is the basic Geometrical interpretation of the *Planck scale meter* based on the two *Geometry constants* e, π where $k = 1$, and *base* $b = 10$, and this from logarithm Properties with different Bases on the same Base e and is $e^w = (b^{\log_b(e)})^w = b^{w.\log_b(e)}$ and $w\sqrt{e} = e^{1/w} = e^{-w} = x^{1/w.\log_b(e)}$ which are *monads in monads* and is therefore of **Wave - motion** with angular velocity $w = 4W_d / (\pi . C_o . \lambda^2)$. [26 -31]

3a... The Conservation of Energy IN Geometry - Mechanism : [62]

Figure - 2-The Two-Perpendicular Vectors, $CA \perp CP$, Slide on (O,OA) circle and through the Three Poles, A, C, P , carry the Stress $\pm \sigma = \frac{w^2.B}{v}$, of Square, $ACPC'$, To the Two Equal and Opposite Squares $|COAB|, |COPB'|$ for **Halve Area - Stress - Conservation**

In(1).On CA diameter circle (O,OA) exists the Inscribed -Square $OA \times OA = OA^2$, and Circumscribed Square $CP \times CP = CP^2$. Since Vector $CP = [OC=OA].\sqrt{2}$, therefore the Inscribed-Square is **Halve** the Circumscribed. The same to the Circles $\pi \left(\frac{CP}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 = 2\pi [CP]^2 = \pi [OA.\sqrt{2}]^2 = 2.\pi [OA]^2$. This Linear Expansion of Archimedes-Circles and Squares Passes from Point M , such that $\pi r^2 = CMNH$ Square .

In(2).. On Two-Perpendicular Vectors , $CA \perp CP$, Point C Slides on (O,OA = OP) circle forming the CAC'P to CMNH to CBAO Squares with Prior of (1) Properties i.e. $CA \times CP = CA^2 = CP^2$, $CP = \sqrt{2}OA$ and $CA^2 = 2.CB^2$,The same happens simultaneously to the Inscribed and Circumscribed Squares on CAC'P , CBAO , on AC diameter circle . This **Sliding -Rotating Method of motion** , { *Screwdriver Material Vector* } is **Markos {2-Vectors 3-Poles Mechanism}** .On this Mechanism

The Inscribed Square CAC'P , start to Rotate through Pole C , such that Point N to slide on C'A arc and forming the changeable Square NMCH until the Inscribed ABCO square of circle [E,EA=EO , and which is Halve of CAC'P . Simultaneously the Circumscribed circle [O,OA] Decreases to the Inscribed circle [E,EA=EB=EO] which is Halve of the Circumscribed . At a Point M of Circle [E,EA = EM] , the Square CMNH is equal to the circle [E,EA=EM] , and $\rightarrow CMNH = \pi .(EA)^2 \leftarrow$

A Screw-motion with Torque Perpendicular on a Plane-Area , of Circle and Squares [$CP \times CA$] , carries this *Motion* through the above Mechanism , in Two Halve areas as Circle and Squares , for the conservation of *Motion* = Energy .

In(3).. If the Two-Perpendicular Vectors **Are Conductors** with Prior Properties then Square CAC'P to CMNH to CBAO Square , are a **Rotating and Changing-Squares-System** , $CP^2 \uparrow = |\otimes|, \cup, \rightarrow$ to **2-Half** and Equal Area Squares $CB^2 = \otimes = \left[\oplus \frac{\otimes}{2} + \ominus \frac{\otimes}{2} \right] CB^2$, by turns in OABC \perp OPB'C Planes , which Equilibrium and Consist ,The Neutral-Space . Placing **Stress** in Squares becomes the Physical World as , *Physics Mechanics* and *Chemistry* by **Conservation of Energy** as **Stresses in Velocity c** .

a).. Gravitational force is acting on the velocity vector \vec{c} and produces the Electron-charge \vec{q} .The Velocity Vector distribution at Point C is done as , $\vec{CP} = \vec{CA}$ and $\vec{CP} \perp \vec{CA}$, where **CP** is the \oplus Electric field Vector $\rightarrow \vec{F} = \vec{q} \cdot \vec{E}$, and **CA** is the \ominus Magnetic field Vector $\rightarrow \vec{F} = \vec{q} \cdot \vec{v} \cdot \vec{B}$.

$$\text{The } \vec{q} \text{ Electron Charge} = \frac{G}{\sqrt{2} \cdot c} = \frac{6,6736923 \cdot 10^{-11}}{1,414212,9979346 \cdot 10^8} = 1,575 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C} .$$

b), **In Electricity** , *The flow of a current in an Conductor* , $CA = d$, *Represents the created around the Conductor by the Circular-Lines of Forces* , **Magnetic field** , *The flow of $\oplus \rightarrow \ominus$ -Charge in d Conductor* , is the Torsional Force $\vec{T}_F = \vec{v} \cdot r = \vec{w} \cdot r^2 = 2\pi f \cdot r^2 = \sigma \Phi r \dots\dots(1)$. Since edge-velocities $\vec{v}_C = \vec{v}_A = 0$, therefore $CA = d = \frac{1}{2} (aT^2)$ and acceleration , $a = 2d / T^2 = 2d \cdot f^2$, and then the velocities diagram is Energy-Triangle $\rightarrow v \cdot [\Delta-CAP] = v \cdot [\frac{1}{2} (2d \cdot |\vec{v}|)] = v \cdot [d w r] = v \cdot d \cdot 2\pi f \cdot r = v \cdot [\sigma \Phi d] \dots(2)$ The Current flow in Electric-Field \vec{E}_{CAP} of CAP Plane is transported into the Perpendicular to CA

axis Opposite Magnetic-Field \vec{M}_{PA} in PA-Plane due to the Force $\vec{T}_F = \vec{v} \cdot r = I = \frac{2\pi r}{\mu} \vec{M}_{PA} = \sigma \Phi r \dots(3)$

The Spin of cave , r , is Equal to the Angular-momentum-Vector $\rightarrow \text{Spin} \equiv |\vec{B}| \equiv r \sigma \Phi \leftarrow$ which contains and it is the Golden-Radius-frequency Φ as Pressure , σ , in cave r .

i.e. The **1-Conductor-Case** is an **Screw-motion** where a Torque is created in Perpendicular Plane of Con-axis . Markos { 2-Vector 3-Poles Rotating , Mechanism } , { $+C \uparrow \left[\oplus \frac{\otimes}{2} + \ominus \frac{\otimes}{2} \right] P$ } , carries

motion (+) \rightarrow (-) from **Point A** , *through an Perpendicular-Conductor CA* , to **Point B** , into an Changeable and Rotating-Squares-System , $PA \uparrow = |\otimes|, \cup, \rightarrow$ To 2-Half and equal Area Squares $CB = \otimes = \left[\oplus \frac{\otimes}{2} + \ominus \frac{\otimes}{2} \right] CB$, by turns in OABC \perp OPB'C Planes which Equilibrium (The Neutral-Space).

c)..The motion of the $\oplus \rightarrow \ominus$ -Charge of any Conductor $d = CA$ becomes **Stress - σ** in length **d** .

Motion is created in Conductors $d \equiv \left[\oplus \leftarrow 2r \rightarrow \ominus \right]$ following the $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$ Interactions . This Motion is Conserved and kept in Caves as **Electric and Magnetic fields** and as frequencies which are conserved in them when the **Space-Points** become Energy-Conductors and Energy $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} = \frac{2\pi}{d}$. The in caves **Energy Imports** are in symmetric Squares which equilibrium through $MPM \equiv$ Markos

2-Vectors 3-Poles-Mechanism where the \oplus Charge is accelerated **Opposite to initial direction** of \ominus Charge in an Electric-field \vec{E}_F . The **Resultant is Velocity-Vector** \vec{CC}'_{AP} , of Electric-Vector = $\frac{\pi\sigma\Phi}{4}[d]^2$, Magnetic -Vector = $\frac{\pi\sigma\Phi}{4}[d]^2$. **Similarly** any Material Vector \vec{CP} carries the **Maximum Conjugate - Force** $CC' = \vec{CK}_A$ from E-Square CP^2 to two Equal and Opposite squares - $CB'PO$, + $CBAO$ from $CAC'P \equiv \frac{+COAB}{-COPB}[\times]$ which Rest happens in the Circumscribed circle $\pi.OA^2 = 2\pi(\frac{OA}{\sqrt{2}})^2$, to the **Screwdriver** Inscribed to, \vec{CA} , \vec{CD} circles $\pi[\frac{CA^2}{4}]$, $\pi[\frac{CP^2}{4}]$. The Resting motion before the Halve areas circles, Pass through the equal to **CMNH Square** where exist Quadrature at **Position M**, and to Half-Area circle $\pi[\frac{OB^2}{\sqrt{2}}]^2 = \pi[\frac{OB^2}{2}]$ at **Position M**. This Property of any Two Equal and Perpendicular **Vectors at Point C**, issues for any Point N, which has a **Screwdriver -Material - Vector- CN**.

d)..The **Gravitational force** between the **velocity vector** \vec{c} and an **Object**, IS Proportional to their masses m_c and m_o and Inversely Proportional to the square of their distance d_{co} as $F_G = G \cdot \frac{m_c \cdot m_o}{d_{co}^2}$ (N)

Equation (N) Produces a **New velocity vector** \vec{co} which is added to \vec{c} vector.

The **Resultant** velocity vector \vec{v}_R forms an angle w to the \vec{c} velocity vector.

The **Screw-motion** of vector \vec{v}_R on a radius r allows to the Velocity Vector \vec{v}_R

to apply at a Point **C** of the circle $[C, r]$ the, **{2-Vectors 3-Poles Mechanism}**

distribution, to two Vectors \vec{CP} , \vec{CA} as, $\vec{CP} = \vec{CA}$ and $\vec{CP} \perp \vec{CA}$, where **CP** is the

\oplus Electric field Force $\rightarrow \vec{F} = \vec{q} \cdot \vec{E}$, and **CA** is the \ominus Magnetic field Force $\rightarrow \vec{F} = \vec{q} \cdot \vec{v} \cdot \vec{B}$.

4a)...Application to the Photon Gravitational bending : $2 \times d \rightarrow \downarrow 4 \times d \rightarrow$
 $\leftrightarrow S \leftrightarrow$

From [39] Monads, as an **Electromagnetic Standing wave move in Field [MFMF]** =

= $s^2 = \pm |(wr)^2|$ as **the smallest Quantized Space of this level**. Let,

L = The length of an undergoing constant acceleration monad in **Gravity field**,

$t = L / c \rightarrow$ is the needed **Time** to cross the length L ,

$s = at^2 / 2 = aL^2/2c^2 \rightarrow$ is the **Deflection** due to acceleration, a ,

1.. For a monad in Planck's length 10^{-35} m then time $T = 8,906 \cdot 10^{-35} / 3 \cdot 10^8 = 2,968 \cdot 10^{-43}$ s and, the Deflection $s = aT^2 / 2 = 9,81.8,809 \cdot 10^{-70} = 4,320836 \cdot 10^{-85}$ m

2.. The Photon velocity vector \vec{v}_{PH} , when passes by the Sun's surface changes direction. This Phenomenon is caused from the Gravitational force between Photon and Sun. Since velocity vector changes direction this means acceleration, therefore use Newton formula $F = m_{ph} \cdot a$. Since the Force-vector is applied Perpendicularly to the **initial velocity vector**, therefore the **Centripetal Force** causes the velocity-vector rotation which is Newton's Gravitational force F ,

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M_{sun} \cdot m_{ph}}{d_1^2} = \frac{6,673 \cdot 10^{-11} Nm^2/Kg^2 \cdot [1,989 \cdot 10^{30} Kg] \cdot [8,84655 \cdot 10^{-21} Kg]}{[691 \cdot 10^6]^2} = 2,4590861 \cdot 10^{-18} N \dots(1P)$$

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M_{sun} \cdot m_{ph}}{d_2^2} = \frac{6,673 \cdot 10^{-11} Nm^2/Kg^2 \cdot [1,989 \cdot 10^{30} Kg] \cdot [8,84655 \cdot 10^{-21} Kg]}{[4 \cdot 6,91 \cdot 10^6]^2} = 0,1532489 \cdot 10^{-18} N$$

where, the mass of the Sun $M_{sun} = 1989 \cdot 10^{30}$ Kg, of Photon $m_{ph} = 8,846562 \cdot 10^{-21}$ Kg.

d = the distance between the two centers of mass = Sun's Radius = $691 \cdot 10^6$ m. Because the component velocity v_{\perp} , is Perpendicular to \vec{c} velocity vector and force F constant, so exists acceleration according to Newton's equation $F = m_{ph} \cdot a$.

Acceleration $a = [\frac{F}{m_{ph}}] = \frac{2,459 \cdot 10^{-18} N}{8,846562 \cdot 10^{-21} Kg} = 277,96108 \text{ m/s}^2 \dots (2P)$, and $a = 1,73229 \text{ m/s}^2$.

The component velocity $v_{\perp} = a \cdot t$ where t is the time needed Photon's vector to run the Sun's diameter as $\rightarrow t = n \cdot d_s / c = n \cdot [13,82 \cdot 10^8 / 2,997 \cdot 10^8] = 4,6112779 \times n \approx 9,22$ s. for a Cone of 2 diameters, and Change of Velocity $\Delta v_{1\perp} = 277,96108 \cdot 9,22 = 2562,8011 \text{ m/s} \dots(3P)$. For $n = 4$ $t = 18,22$ s and $\Delta v_{2\perp} = 1,73229 \cdot 18,22 = 31,56232 \text{ m/s}$ and $w_{2,arc.sec} = 0,21715144 \text{ arcsec}$

Because the vector v_{\perp} is perpendicular to \vec{c} vector, therefore for angle w , $\tan w = [\frac{\Delta v_{\perp}}{c}]$ and

$$w_{1,rad} = \arctan\left\{\frac{2562,8011 \text{ m/s}}{2,998,10^8 \text{ m/s}}\right\} = 8,5512215 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians. Since } 1 \text{ rad} = \left[\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600\right] \text{ then,}$$

$$w_{1,arc,sec} = 8,5512215 \cdot 10^{-6} \times \left[\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600\right] = 1,7638159 \text{ arcsec} \dots(4P)$$

5a,,,The Photon Gravitational-Bending is NOT Lensing of Spacetime, [Milky-Way Star]

DATA :

$G = 6,673 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2/\text{Kg}^2$. \rightarrow Newton's Gravitational constant ,

$\vec{c} = 2,998 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$, The Photon's velocity vector ,

$m_{ph} = 8,846562 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ Kg}$, \rightarrow The mass (Reaction to motion) of Photon .

$M_{GAL} = 0,8 \cdot 10^{30} \text{ Kg}$, \rightarrow The mass of Galaxy ,

$r_{GAL} = 0,8 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}$, The radius of Galaxy ,

$d_{GAL} = 1,6 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}$, The diameter of the Galaxy.

$r_{G-P} = 1,6 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}$, The distance between Galaxy - Photon .

a)..From Newton's , Law of Universal Gravitation , the attraction force F is as ,

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M_{GAL} \cdot m_{ph}}{r_{G-P}^2} = \frac{6,673 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2/\text{Kg}^2 \cdot [0,8 \cdot 10^{30} \text{ Kg}] \cdot [8,84655 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ Kg}]}{[1,6 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}]^2} = 1,844782 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ N} , \dots(1G)$$

b)..Because the component velocity v_{\perp} , is Perpendicular to \vec{c} velocity vector and the force F is constant , so exists acceleration according to the 2nd Newton's law $\rightarrow F = m_{ph} \cdot a$.

$$\text{Acceleration } a = \left[\frac{F}{m_{ph}}\right] = \frac{1,844782 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ N}}{8,846562 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ Kg}} = 20,853095 \text{ m/s}^2 \dots(2G)$$

c)..The component velocity $v_{\perp} = a \cdot t$ where , t , is the time needed by the Photon's vector to run the Sun's diameter in Cone of $n = 2$ -diameter as distance as equation $\rightarrow t = n \cdot d_s / c$, and , $t = 2 \cdot [1,6 \cdot 10^9 / 2,998 \cdot 10^8] = 2 \times 5,3368912 \approx 10,673782 \text{ s}$. for a Cone of 2 diameters , and Change of Velocity $\Delta v_{2\perp} = a \times t = 20,8531 \cdot 10,674 = 222,58139 \text{ m/s} \dots(3G)$

d)..Because vector v_{\perp} is perpendicular to \vec{c} vector, therefore for angle w issues $\tan w = \left[\frac{\Delta v_{\perp}}{c}\right]$ as

$$w_{2,rad} = \arctan\left\{\frac{222,58139 \text{ m/s}}{2,998,10^8 \text{ m/s}}\right\} = 7,4243292 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ radians. Since } 1 \text{ rad} = \left[\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600\right] \text{ then,}$$

$$w_{2,arc,sec} = 7,4243292 \cdot 10^{-7} \times \left[\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600\right] = 0,15313777 \text{ arcsec} \dots\dots\dots(4G)$$

e)..For a distance $4 \times r_{GAL} = 3,2 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}$ then , $F = G \cdot \frac{M_{GAL} \cdot m_{ph}}{r_{G-P}^2} = 1,152988 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ N}$,

$$\text{Acceleration } a = \left[\frac{F}{m_{ph}}\right] = 1,3033184 \text{ m/s}^2 , \quad t = 4 \cdot d_s / c \approx 21,347564 \text{ s} \dots(5G)$$

$$\Delta v_{4\perp} = a \times t = 27,822672 \text{ m/s} , w_{4,rad} = 9,280411 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ rad} , w_{2,arc,sec} = 0,01014222 \text{ arcsec} .$$

Remarks :

- 1.. From Photon equation $\Rightarrow \vec{v} \cdot [\vec{f}_n + f_n] = \left|\frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4}\right| \cdot |\vec{B}_n| + |\vec{c}| \cdot f_n$, and when $c = 0$, motion is $\left|\frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4}\right| \cdot |\vec{B}_n|$ which is motion in a **Standing wave** . Photon is of Dual nature and is Electromagnetic field .where the **Electric-field Produces** the Work and the **Magnetic - Field Stores** the Work .
From Physics , *mass is the reaction to the motion* which means the meter of the motion . 'Newton's Gravitational force is the dominant force in nature in which subject all **meters of motions** , or masses, i.e. *for Photons , Electric - field is the motion and Magnetic Field is the reaction to this motion , which is thus the mass of Photons* .
When Newton's third law (Action-Reaction) is applied on Photon-Wave whenever **Electric-field** exerts a Force =Action on **Magnetic - Field** , then the Magnetic - Field exerts an Reaction - Force.
- 2.. We apply Newton's second law and Vector - Kinematics , for a duration of the Newton's Gravitational force , on a Path of the time vector at a distance of 2 - diameters.
- 3.. The Perpendicular Impulse is as the Centripetal acceleration which causes the motion on the arc and the continuous change of the velocity vector to the direction of the Force .

- 4.. The final velocity vector is the Sum of the Initial Horizontal velocity and the New Vertical component velocity vector , while the New Direction is that of the Resultant of the two vectors .
- 5.. The direction of the Photon's Resultant-velocity is maximum at the Point of contact of the orbiting Sphere, and decreases with the Photon's distance from the center of its Precession orbit.
- 6.. The Gravitational force between the velocity vector \vec{v} and an Object, IS Proportional to their masses m_c and m_o and Inversely Proportional to the square of their distance d_{co} as $F_G = G \cdot \frac{m_c \cdot m_o}{d_{co}^2}$ (N)
- The Centripetal Force F_G Produces a New velocity vector \vec{v}_R which is added to \vec{v} vector . **The Resultant velocity vector \vec{v}_R forms the Deflection angle w , to the \vec{v} velocity vector .**

- 7..The light-rays and consequently the Photons travel in Straight lines .
- 8..Time is the meter , to measure the changes in , Energy = motion = Force x displacement.
- 9..The Gravitational force G , causes the Bending of light rays (of Photons) , and **Not the warping** of Spacetime which Time is Not existing , **on the contrary** , **Space-energy**, is the essence of existence.. It was shown in [70-P32] that in a Cycloid , the area between the curve and the straight line is $A = 3\pi r^2$ and the arc length $l = 8r$. For the motion on cycloid , we consider a **Weight Q** , at a point A , moving with free motion . Since reaction N , is vertically acting , Q , so doesn't give any Tangential component , and the only one becomes from Q , which is equal to $AT = g \cdot \sin \varphi$ and since $\sin \varphi = \frac{s}{4r}$

then issues $AT = g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}$. Since acceleration $a = \frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = \frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(\frac{ds}{dt}) = \{-g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}\}$ then $\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = -g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}$ or $\{\ddot{s} = -w^2 \cdot s \text{ where } w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{g}{4r}\}$... (a) and is a **Harmonic Oscillatory motion** showing that Acceleration

is Proportional to displacement and is directed towards the origin with a Period $T = \frac{2\pi}{w} = 2\pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{4r}{g}} = 4\pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{r}{g}}$, or and $w^2 = (\frac{g}{4r})^2$, where $w = 2\pi f = \frac{g}{4r}$. From Total-Energy $2L = J \cdot w^2 = 4\pi^2 \cdot f^2$, the Circular

frequency is $w^2 = \frac{(\sigma\Phi)^2}{r^2} = [2\pi f]^2$, and the Cycloidal-Frequency $f_p = \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} = \frac{[1+\sqrt{5}]\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}$... (f)

Equation (f) relates , Circular frequency w , frequency f_p , Stress σ , in any cave , r , **from a Force Q** in a free motion . In the case of Photon , the Gravitational-Constant-Force G , becomes as Stress \equiv Force / Area $\equiv g$, as equation $G = g k_E = g \cdot [g_E k_E] = [\frac{T^2 p}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = [\frac{c \cdot r^2}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = 9,8076925 * [..]$

$6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} = 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$, and **Effects on gravity** $\rightarrow g \equiv 9,8076925 \text{ Stress } \frac{Kg}{cm^2}$ [73]

The Beyond-Planck-length Force $F = \sigma \cdot A =$ The Glue-Bond \equiv Stress x Area $\equiv [\frac{2\pi f \cdot r}{\Phi}] \cdot A = w \cdot r \cdot [\frac{A}{\Phi}] = \bar{v} [\frac{A}{\Phi}]$ and becomes a moving Storage $\frac{A}{\Phi}$ travelling with velocity \bar{v} , n times that of light-velocity c , as equation $\bar{v} = n \cdot c$. [77]

6a...The Greatest Energy Pressure-Level : From [89] .

The explanation of Pascal's -Triangle in M-Geometry and *Application In Jericho Walls* ,

<p>FROM THE PLANE MATERIAL-TRIANGLE BECOMING THE REGULAR-HEXAGON</p> <p>E-Plane = P-P-P</p>		<p>THE BASIC STEADY-SHAPE IS The Regular TRIANGLE with Three Points and SIX [6] Material - Elements .</p> <p>[1] = The Material Point P of TWO - UNITS</p> <p>[2] = Two Material Points = Vector P-P and The Material Vector P-P with FOUR UNITS .</p> <p>[3] = The Euclidean Plane P-P-P of Three Non - Linear - Points</p> <p>[4] = The Euclidean Solid P-P-P-P of Four Non - Linear - Points</p>
<p>FROM THE VOLUME MATERIAL-TETRAHEDRON BECOMES THE REGULAR-OCTAGON</p> <p>E-Volume = P-P-P-P</p> <p>The Regular-Heptagon [$7 = (6+8)/2$] Becomes from Plane-Triangle 1, 2, 3 The Material - Regular - Hexagon And Volume-Tetrahedron 1, 2, 3, 4 The Material - Regular - Octagon AND IS-The Removal of E-Plane To Volume and , n, Volume.</p>		

Figure – 3 : The [+] Spaces , [-] Anti-Spaces , [+ -] Sub-Spaces in a circle (R , OA)
The Material-Geometry explanation of Pascal's - Triangle

Stress $\sigma = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Area}}$, and is the Pressure executed by the Force on Surface A . Sound Pressure SP, is the Pressure measured within the wave relative to the surrounding air Pressure.

The SP , like other kinds of Pressure ,is commonly measured in units of Pascal's (Pa) $= \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}^2} = \frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{ms}^2} = \frac{\text{J}}{\text{m}^3}$,with minimum SP ,equal to Quantum $p_0 = 2.10^{-5} \text{ Pa} \equiv 0 \text{ (dB)}$ the Decibel .

The equation of Sound-Pressure-Level ,SPL, is $L_{SP} = 20.\log_{10}(\frac{P}{P_0}) \text{ dB}$,where P =Pressure $L_{SP0} = 0 \text{ dB}$ corresponds at frequency $f_s = 1 \text{ kHz} = 1000 \text{ Hz}$. The Sound-Intensity-Level , SIL0 is , $L_{SI} = 10.\log_{10}(\frac{I}{I_0}) \text{ dB}$, where Intensity $I = \frac{P^2}{Z_0}$ and Impedance $Z_0 = 400 \text{ Ns/m}^3$

The greatest SP, cannot be exceeded the average air pressure which is 101325 Pa and fixed

$$\text{SPL , is } L_{SP} = 20.\log_{10}(\frac{101325}{0,00002}) = 194 \text{ dB} \dots\dots(s1)$$

In Material Geometry Photon-frequency $f_{ph} = [\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}]$ which is related to the Stress ,

$\sigma = \text{Force/Area}$, and is the **Energy-Pressure-Level , EPL** , of the ,**Wave + Particle Photon** , for its frequency .The Greatest EPL for the two Opposite-Elements $\{\oplus , \ominus\}$ in Space is their Permutation $P_{1S}^2 = 2$ and for Anti-Space $P_{1AS}^2 = 2$ or for both $P_{1S+A}^2 = 2 \cdot 2 = 4$ min-Levels .

Because [9] , The Circumscribed-Regular-Polygons in a circle (R,OA) Denote the Spaces and Anti-Spaces $[(\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus)]$, and Inscribed-Regular-Polygons of the circle Denote the Sub-Spaces **and Because** [63] ,The Regular-Polygons Denote the Structure of Material-Geometry to be as

A Point $\rightarrow n=1 \quad m=2 , \{ S \equiv \oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus \equiv A \} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space}$

Line-sector $\rightarrow n=2 , m=4 , \begin{pmatrix} S & \leftrightarrow & S \\ S & \rightarrow & A \\ A & \leftrightarrow & A \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space}$

Plane-Triangle $\rightarrow n=3 , m=6 , \begin{pmatrix} S & A & S \\ s & s & s \\ A & S & A \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space} \quad s = \text{Sub-Space}$

A Volume $\rightarrow n=4 , m=8 , \begin{pmatrix} S & A & S \\ s & S & s \\ A & S & A \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space} \quad s = \text{Sub-Space}$

and Because Regular-Hexagon is of $3 \times 2 = 6$ Vertices on **Plane-Triangle** +

Regular--Octagon is of $4 \times 2 = 8$ Vertices on **Volume-Tetrahedron** then ,

Regular-Heptagon-Anti Heptagon is of , $7 \times 2 = 14$ Vertices [63-P70].

Regular-Heptagon Between the Two-Regions , **Plane -Volume** , Needs more **Pressure** ,and consists the Upper - Largest Energy-Level with Permutation , the number of **Permutation** with Repetition of the **Seventh** - Element as , $RP_2^n \equiv n^2 \rightarrow P_2^7 = 7^2 = 49$, and

The Greatest **EPL** is $\rightarrow P_{1S+A}^2 \times P_2^7 = 4 \times 49 = 196 = L_{EP} = 196 \text{ dB} \dots(s2)$

Remarks :

1... The Stress σ is executed on all Surfaces , either in Planes or on Surfaces of Volumes , and consists the exclusive-meter of measurements , in dB , in all nature .

2... Stress σ , occupies minimum and maximum limits, $0 \approx 196$ dB, differing 2 Units which can be changed by altering the Base of Pressure from 101325 \rightarrow 102389 Pa.

3... Minimum and Maximum limits, $0 \approx 194 \approx 196$ dB, become from $L_{EP} = \left[\frac{\pi^2}{Nc} \right]^3 = 194$ dB

4... Stress σ , occupies Minimum and Maximum because is related to frequency and velocity

$$f_{ph} = \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \frac{\sigma + \sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma[1+\Phi]}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma[\Phi]^2}{2\pi r}, \text{ or } \sigma \equiv \frac{f_{ph} \cdot 2\pi r}{\Phi^2} \equiv \frac{w \cdot r}{\Phi^2} \equiv \frac{v}{\Phi^2} \equiv \bar{c} \frac{1}{\Phi^2}$$

and is **The-Stress-Way** of Photon-Storages $\boxed{\bar{f}_n} \equiv \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}$, and Photon-Information $f_n \equiv \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}$

From force $G \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3 \equiv \Phi^2 \cdot [\{\sigma \Phi\}] \equiv \left[\frac{2B}{\pi r^3} \right] \equiv 2\pi f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \bar{v} \equiv m a = m g = \bar{c}$ then

Stress $\{\sigma \Phi\} \equiv \left[\frac{2B}{\pi r^3} \right] \equiv 2\pi \cdot f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \bar{v} \equiv m a = m g = \bar{c}$ is dependent on Total-Prior.

5..As soon as $\rightarrow A = \{\text{The Space + Anti-Space Positions in Universe}\}$, become **Inadequate**

for an **min-Energy-Storage** $A = e^{-i(\frac{\pi}{2}) \cdot b} = 0,207879576 \cdot b = 1,507 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{m}$, then **Motion** \equiv **Energy** is first filling **The minimum cave**, r , and with the Necessary **Velocity-Vectors** \rightarrow **Burst Into another cave** $a > A = 1,507 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{m}$ in L_p , **connected to G**, and which **Is an Overflow of the Energy** in the, **Space + Anti-Space Positions** [58]. From relation $E_{ph} \equiv \bar{c} \cdot \left\{ \boxed{\bar{f}_n} + f_n \right\}$ is seen the Storages and from $\bar{q}_{\text{Photon}} \equiv \frac{\bar{c} \cdot \sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} \equiv \frac{\bar{w} \cdot \sigma\Phi}{2\pi}$ the Stresses.

Exists 1KPa = 10^3 Pa, 1MPa = 10^6 Pa, 1GPa = 10^9 Pa, $q = \text{itAs} = \text{Cb}$,

1eV = $[1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{Cb}]$, 1V = 1,6022 $\cdot 10^{-19}$ Joule, $q_e = 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19}$ Culomb,

The Density of Electric current becomes from the Electron- Orbit-motion as equation

$$J = \frac{i}{A} = \sigma_{n-\max} = \frac{v_{n-\max}}{\Phi} = \frac{\text{Amper}}{\text{m}^2} = \frac{w_n}{\Phi}, \text{ Energy becomes from the maximum velocity as,}$$

$$E_{n-\max} = \frac{m_e \cdot [v_{n-\max}]^2}{2} = \frac{9,1 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{Kg} \cdot [v_{n-\max} \text{m/s}]^2}{2} = \text{Joule}.$$

6...Application of Stress σ , on the Walls of Jericho.

DATA :

From Biblical Account and Historical & Archaeological Context,

a). Wall construction from **Limestones** with Stress $\sigma_L = 2000 - 2500$ Kg/m³.

b). The Wall **Thickness** = 1,50 m, and Height = 7,50 m,

c). The Wall's **Natural = Frequency** $f_{NF} = 121,72$ Hz.

d). Trumpet **Frequency** $f_{TF} = 1400$ Hz, and Rams' Horn = 260 - 1100 Hz.

e). **Modulating** the Trumpet Frequency $f_{TF} = 1400$ Hz, and wind-gusts = 1-Hz = 700,5 Hz

From equations $f = \frac{\sigma_s \Phi}{2 \cdot \pi r}$, wavelength $\lambda = c / f = 2r$, Resonance frequency $f_R = \frac{\sigma_s \Phi}{\pi \cdot \lambda}$.

From Resonance frequency $f_R = \frac{\sigma_s \Phi}{\pi \cdot \lambda}$, and for wavelength $\lambda_W = \frac{\sigma_s \Phi}{\pi \cdot f_R} = 1,50$ m. then \rightarrow

1..For minimum -Stress $\sigma_L = 2000 \rightarrow f_R = \frac{[1,608] \cdot 2000}{\pi \cdot 1,50} = 681,18$ Hz, Potentially from (d) - f_{TF}

2..For maximum -Stress $\sigma_L = 2500 \rightarrow f_R = \frac{[1,608] \cdot 2500}{\pi \cdot 1,50} = 853,07$ Hz, Potentially from (d) - f_{TF}

3..From Hard-Limestone $\sigma_L = 2500 \rightarrow f_R = \frac{[1,608] \cdot 2300}{\pi \cdot 1,50} = 784,82$ Hz, Potentially from (d) - f_{TF}

4..From **Modulated-Frequency** $f_M = 700,5$ Hz, then $\sigma_L = \frac{\pi \cdot \lambda \cdot f_M}{\Phi} = 2052,88$ Kg/m³.

Remarks :

a.. At first the Resonance frequency of the collected shouting and Rams' Horn is the Potentially cause of weaken and collapse the Walls.

b.. The Modulated - Frequency of the Trumpet and the wind-gusts is the most possibility to collapse the Walls , and this because of the Limestone very Low stress Resistance .

7a... The Parallel Postulate and Relativity : [38]

AB is a straight line through Points A, B and M any other point . When $MA+MB > AB$ then Point M is not on AB .(differently if $MA+MB = AB$ then this answers the question of why any line contains at least two Points i.e. for any Point M on line AB where is holding $MA+MB = AB$, meaning that lines MA , MB coincide on AB / is thus proved from the other axioms and so D2 is not an axiom).

To Prove that , One and only One line MM' can be drawn Parallel to AB.

To Prove the above Axiom is necessary to show:

1...The Parallel to AB is the locus of all Points at a constant distance h from the line AB, and for Point M is MA,

2...The locus of all these Points is a straight line.

Figure – 4 - : The Three Points .

Step 1

Draw the circle (M, MA) be joined meeting line AB in C. Since $MA = MC$, Point M is on mid-Perpendicular of AC. Let A_1 be the midpoint of AC, (it is $A_1A + A_1C = AC$ because A_1 is on the straight line AC. Triangles MAA_1, MCA_1 are equal because the three sides are equal, therefore angle $\angle MA_1A = \angle MA_1C$ (CN₁) and since the sum of the two angles $\angle MA_1A + \angle MA_1C = 180^\circ$ (CN2, 6D) then angle $\angle MA_1A = \angle MA_1C = 90^\circ$, (P4) so, MA_1 is the minimum fixed distance h of Point M to AC. A

Step 2 .

Let B_1 be the midpoint of CB,(it is $B_1C + B_1B = CB$ because B_1 is on the straight line CB) and draw $B_1M = h$ equal to A_1M on the mid-perpendicular from Point B_1 to CB. Draw the circle ($M', M'B = M'C$) intersecting the circle (M, $MA = MC$) at Point D.(P3) Since $M'C = M'B$, Point M' lies on mid-Perpendicular of CB. (CN₁)

Since $M'C = M'D$, Point M' lies on mid-perpendicular of CD. (CN₁) Since $MC = MD$, Point M lies on mid-perpendicular of CD. (CB₁) Because Points M and M' lie on the same mid-perpendicular (This mid-perpendicular is drawn from point C' to CD and it is the mid Point of CD) and because only one line MM' passes through points M , M' then line MM' coincides with this mid-perpendicular (CN4)

Step 3

Draw the Perpendicular of CD at Point C'. (P3, P1)

- a. Because $MA_1 \perp AC$ and also $MC' \perp CD$ then angle $\angle A_1MC' = \angle A_1CC'$... (Cn 2,Cn3,E.1.15)
- b. Because $M'B_1 \perp CB$ and also $M'C' \perp CD$ then angle $\angle B_1M'C' = \angle B_1CC'$... (Cn2, Cn3, E.1.15)
- c. The sum of angles $\angle A_1CC' + \angle B_1CC' = 180^\circ = \angle A_1MC' + \angle B_1M'C'$, (6.D), and since Point C' lies on straight line MM' , therefore the sum of angles in shape $A_1B_1M'M$ are $\angle MA_1B_1 + \angle A_1B_1M' + \angle B_1M'M$

$M + M'MA_1] = 90^\circ + 90^\circ + 180^\circ = 360^\circ = (Cn2)$, i.e. The sum of angles in a Quadrilateral is 360° and in Rectangle all equal to 90° . (m)

- d. The right-angled triangles MA_1B_1 , $M'B_1A_1$ are equal because $A_1M = B_1M'$ and A_1B_1 common, therefore side $A_1M' = B_1M$ (Cn1). Triangles A_1MM' , $B_1M'M$ are equal because have the three sides equal each other, therefore angle $\angle A_1MM' = \angle B_1M'M$, and since their sum is 180° as before (6D), so angle $\angle A_1MM' = \angle B_1M'M = 90^\circ$ (Cn2).
- e. Since angle $\angle A_1MM' = \angle B_1CC'$ and also angle $\angle B_1M'M = \angle B_1CC'$ (P4), therefore quadrilaterals $A_1CC'M$, $B_1CC'M'$, $A_1B_1M'M$ are Rectangles (CN3). From the above three rectangles and because all points (M, M' and C') equidistant from AB, this means that C'C is also the minimum equal distance of point C' to line AB or, $h = MA_1 = M'B_1 = CD / 2 = C'C$ (Cn1) Namely, line MM' is Perpendicular to segment CD at Point C' and this line coincides with the mid-perpendicular of CD at this Point C' and points M, M', C' are on line MM'. Point C' equidistant, h, from line AB, as it is for points M, M', so the locus of the three Points is the straight line MM', so the two demands are satisfied, ($h = C'C = MA_1 = M'B_1$ and also $C'C \perp AB$, $MA_1 \perp AB$, $M'B_1 \perp AB$). (o.e.d.)
- The right-angle triangles A_1CM , MCC' are equal because side $MA_1 = C'C$ and MC common so angle $\angle A_1CM = \angle C'MC$, and the Sum of angles $\angle C'MC + \angle MCB_1 = \angle B_1CM + \angle MCB_1 = 180^\circ$

Conclusions :

- 1.. From any Point M, there is only one Parallel to any A-B, Straight line.
- 2.. From Point M, there is only one Parallel to, $A - B \rightarrow \infty$, Straight line.
- 3.. From Point M, there is only one Parallel to, $B - A \rightarrow \infty$, Straight line.
- 4.. The light-rays and consequently the Photons travel in Straight lines, i.e. follow the Euclidean Geometry and NOT any other.
- 5.. Time is the meter, to measure the changes in Energy = **motion** = Force x displacement, and NOT any other essence. The essence of Universe is \rightarrow Space $\equiv [\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus]$, Energy $\equiv [\oplus \sigma \ominus] \leftarrow$
- 6.. The Gravitational force G, causes the Bending of the light rays (of Photons), and Not the warping of Spacetime, which meaning is Not existing because this Concept has never been clarified.

B.. : THE E - GEOMETRY & THE ENERGY CAVES .

1b... The Golden Ratio Φ and its functions .

THE GOLDEN RATIO ON SEGMENTS & MATERIAL-POINT

On Segments AB, Point C is such that $AB \times CB = AC^2$

$$\frac{AB}{AC} = \frac{AC}{CB} = \Phi = \frac{[1 + \sqrt{5}]}{2}$$

A ——— C ——— B

On Material Point is the Frequency f_0

The Photon Golden - Ratio - Frequency

 $f_0 = [1 + \sqrt{5}] \sigma / 4\pi r = \Phi \cdot [\sigma / 2\pi r]$

Figure - 5 - : The Physical explanation of **The Golden-Ratio Φ** , in Universe :
 In figure, AB line-Vector is divided by Point C such that $AC = \frac{AB}{2} [\sqrt{5} + 1] \dots(1)$

Proof :

According to the definition of Mean ratio exists $AB / AC = AC / CB$, or $AC^2 = AB.CB$
 $= AB.[AB-AC] = AC^2 = - AC.(AB) + AB^2 \rightarrow AC^2 + AC (AB) - AB^2 = 0$ (2) Solving
the second degree equation (2) then $AC = \frac{AB}{2} [\sqrt{5}+1]$, i.e. Point C on AB vector, is such
that issues relation (1).

The Physical meaning becomes from Mechanics where, when a force P, acting on a surface
S, of a differential volume ds^3 , then Principal stresses σ_1, σ_2 , and Shear stresses τ_{12} are

as equation $\sigma = \sqrt{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + 4 \tau_{12}^2}$, and $\sigma_{1,2} = (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) / 2 \pm (1/2) \sqrt{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + 4 \tau_{12}^2}$,

where $\rightarrow \tan\theta = 2. \tau_{12} / (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)$.. (3) **When the surface becomes a Point [This is the Extreme
case where surface is interchanged as line or line- segment, it is the same as the infinite small
, ds, in Calculus], then $\sigma_2 = 0$ and τ_{12} is very small i.e.**

It is a type of vanishing - Shear due to layers laterally shifted. Since force P, is a vector then as is
in cross-product to a right-handed coordinate system where exists $\sigma_2 = 0$ and $\tau_{12} = \sigma_1$, then
equation (3) becomes, $\sigma_{1,2} = \sigma_1 / 2 \pm (1/2) \cdot \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + 4. \sigma_1^2} = \frac{\sigma_1}{2} \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] = \frac{\sigma}{2} \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})]$ (4)

Equation (4) denotes the way that Stresses $\sigma_{1,2}$, are shaped on any Volume according to the Principal
Stress σ , and which is the **Golden-ratio** $\Phi = \frac{\sigma}{2} [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})]$ of Stress σ . Since also Stress σ
eternally exists in Material - Point and is of the **Golden-ratio-pattern** Φ , therefore microcosm and
sequence all macrocosm follows, the Stress σ , Property Vector as $\{\sigma \Phi\} = [\frac{2B}{\pi r^2}] = 2\pi \cdot f_p r = w r = \bar{v} =$
 $m a = m g = \bar{c}$, and The Growing-Golden-ratio-Pattern Φ , as this is stated in,

- 1.. Stress with Golden ratio Property,
- 2.. Centripetal acceleration due to Stress,
- 3.. Gravity = Stress = Centrifugal acceleration,
- 4.. Gravitation constant G Stressing, g.

For $\sigma_1 = 0$, the **Pure Shear state**, Equation (4) becomes $\sigma_{EQUAL} = \tau_{12} \cdot \sqrt{3}$. and consists the
Flow-limit \equiv the **Safety-Factor-Range** of G action on Charge q

All above related vectors, of frequency f_p , occupying the **Growing - Golden-ratio** Pattern Φ , give the
analogous Strength to enter caves, and incidentally in Satiation Systems to follow the **Split -Property**
as this happened to the **Organic - Chemistry and Medicine**.

The Φ Properties :

To show that $\Phi = 1 + \frac{1}{\Phi} = 1, 6180339887$: The Proof ,

It is holding $\rightarrow 1 + \frac{1}{\Phi} = 1 + \frac{1}{\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}} = 1 + \frac{2}{1+\sqrt{5}} = \frac{2[\sqrt{5}-1]}{[\sqrt{5}+1][\sqrt{5}-1]}$ or ,

$$1 + \frac{1}{\Phi} = 1 + \frac{2[\sqrt{5}-1]}{4} = 1 + \frac{[\sqrt{5}-1]}{2} = \frac{2+\sqrt{5}-1}{2} = \frac{[\sqrt{5}+1]}{2} = \Phi, \text{ therefore, } \Phi = 1 + \frac{1}{\Phi} \dots (5)$$

Equation (5) is an very Interesting Property of the Golden - Ratio because is such that,
it can be Defined in terms of itself, i.e. of unit 1 equal to a new Φ which defines
the Space and from $\frac{1}{\Phi}$ define the Opposite which is **The Anti-Space**, and both still .

as continuous fraction is, $\Phi = 1 + \left[\frac{1}{1 + \left[\frac{1}{1 + \left[\frac{1}{1 + \dots} \right]} \right]} \right] \dots (6)$

Because number Φ , multiplied with its Reciprocal number $\frac{1}{\Phi}$, is process of Addition,
and equal to unit 1, so \rightarrow **Space * Anti-Space \equiv Monad** \leftarrow or $\Phi * \frac{1}{\Phi} \equiv 1$ because ,

$$\rightarrow \Phi * \frac{1}{\Phi} = \left[1 + \frac{1}{\Phi} \right] \frac{1}{\Phi} = 1 \text{ or } \rightarrow \frac{1}{\Phi} + \frac{1}{\Phi^2} = 1 \text{ and } \Phi + 1 = \Phi^2 \text{ or } \Phi^2 = \Phi + 1 \dots (7)$$

Equation (7) is written as, $\Phi^2 - \Phi - 1 = 0$, and the roots of the second degree equation is

$$x = + \frac{\Phi}{2} \pm \frac{[\sqrt{(\Phi^2 + 4\Phi^2)}]}{2} = \frac{[\sqrt{5}+1]}{2} \cdot \Phi = \Phi * \Phi \text{ i.e. The Golden-Ratio Property is continuously}$$

increasing by its self, **a Self-Growing Property of frequency f_n of Material-Point**. Equation (7) is also a very Special Property of the Golden ratio because, *according to Euclid*, A straight line AB is said to have been cut in Extreme and Mean ratio when as the whole line is to the greater segment AB / AC, so is the greater to the lesser AC / CB, **and according to Markos**, Since **frequency in Material-Point becomes** from Equilibrium of \rightarrow **The Two-Opposite-Rotational-Energies** $[\pm]$ \leftarrow as relation

$$\bar{B} \bar{w} = L = \frac{1}{2} J_1 w_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} J_2 w_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} J_3 w_3^2, \text{ or Angular-momentum } B \equiv \pm \text{Spin } S \text{ as,}$$

$$\bar{B} = \frac{L}{w} = \frac{\pi r^4}{4} [2\pi f] = \frac{\pi^2 r^4}{2} [f] \equiv [\text{Constant} * f] \equiv \frac{2L}{w} = \frac{2L}{2\pi f} = \left[\frac{L}{\pi} \right] \cdot \left[\frac{1}{f} \right] = \frac{4r.L}{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}, \text{ or}$$

$$\bar{B} = \frac{4r.L}{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma} = \frac{2r.[L=hf]}{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma} = \frac{hf}{2\pi f} = \left[\frac{h}{2\pi} \right] \equiv \text{SPIN}, \text{ where } L = hf = \text{Constant}$$

and Frequency related to Φ is $\rightarrow f_n = \left[\frac{2}{\pi^2 r^4} \right] \cdot \bar{B} \equiv \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right] \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \equiv \left[\frac{\Phi \sigma}{2\pi r} \right] \dots \dots (7a)$

The frequency which Occupies the Property of the Golden-Ratio-Pattern Φ , and equation (7-7a) defines that Material Point of frequency f_n , when collide with another Material Point, or with another Particle or Particles, then M-P Produces another monad as the ONE $\rightarrow I \equiv$ **New Quaternion** and the first continuous to be of the same Identity, **frequency f_n** , as before and from Euler's, *rigid body dynamics work* $W = 2L = \bar{B} \cdot \bar{w} = J \cdot w^2 \equiv h \cdot f_n \equiv \left[\frac{h \cdot \Phi \sigma}{2\pi r} \right] \leftarrow$ i.e.

The Frequency of Photon, is embodied with the \rightarrow Growing-Golden-ratio-Pattern $\Phi \leftarrow$ And Uses **The Vibrating Physical Structures, which are the Granular Material-Instruments, To Kick Start all of them and everything in this World**. The How is in [86]

Figure – 6 - : The Physical explanation of The Golden-Ratio Φ in Microcosm – Macrocosm . :

2b... The Acceleration Growth in Material Point :

- 1).. A line Vector AB on which Golden-Ratio is applied, is analogous to a **Conductor \bar{AB}** on which Stresses $\sigma \equiv \left[\frac{2\pi r}{\Phi} \right] |f_n$ on Vectors-Square is acting, and is set into vibration motion at its natural frequency f_n . Since each natural frequency of the Conductor is associated with One of the many Standing wave-Patterns by which Conductor AB could vibrate, **Then-When** another one Interconnected Object Pushes Conductor with one of these frequencies, the Conductor is forced into vibrating at one of its Harmonics. Natural frequency f_n , transports the Golden Ratio Φ in the other Object. This happens in Photosynthesis.
- 2). The Equations of motion in a Material Point related to the Inner motion was referred before where the In-between-magnitude AE, *The Part*, becomes the Outer AB as the **Whole or the Self-Growth**. This Augmentation-Property, of these two Golden-Ratios, exists in the Material-Point and on Frequency f_n , which **motion \equiv Growth**, and Spread in Two-Closed-Transverse Planes as is in the Propagating Electromagnetic Wave where $E \perp H$.

From equations $E = h \cdot f_n = \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right] \frac{h\sigma}{2\pi r} = \left[\frac{h\sigma}{2\pi r} \right] \cdot \bar{B}$, $f_R \equiv [f_1=N, f_2, f_3, f_R = w^2_N]$, Euler's $e^{-i.A\left(\frac{\pi}{2}+2k\pi\right).b} = e^{-i.A\left(\frac{\pi+4k\pi}{2}\right).b} = A \cdot \cos\left[\frac{\pi+4k\pi}{2}\right].b - i \cdot A \sin\left[\frac{\pi+4k\pi}{2}\right].b$, $L = \left[\frac{\bar{B}}{2} \right] \cdot w$, Then

$$w = \sqrt{2\pi f_R} = 2L / \bar{B}, \text{ and Wave Equation is } y = 2A \cdot \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{\lambda}\right) \cdot \cos \cdot wt \dots\dots(a)$$

Equation (a), is the equation of the Inner Electromagnetic wave denoting that the vertical motion, v_y , is related to the Position, x , and is defined on the Sinus curve while the horizontal motion, $v_x = 0$, frequency, w , is on the Cosines curve and is,

$$w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = 2\pi \cdot f_N \equiv \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right] \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}, \text{ which follows the } \mathbf{Growth-Golden-Ratio-Pattern}.$$

The same happens to the Outer Electromagnetic wave which equations are,

$$\bar{E} = v_x \cdot E_0 \cdot \cos(kz - wt + \varphi), \quad \bar{B} = v_y \cdot \left[\frac{E_0}{c}\right] \cdot \cos(kz - wt + \varphi) \dots(b)$$

Equation (b) is the equation of the Outer Electromagnetic wave, denoting that the Electric field which travels with light velocity $c \rightarrow$ directed to \vec{k} axis. Magnetic field travels with light velocity also, $c \rightarrow$ directed to \vec{k} , and is in Phase with Electric field.

For both, Outer Electromagnetic fields the frequency, w , is that of inner motion i.e.

$$w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = 2\pi \cdot f_N \equiv \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right] \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}, \text{ which continuous to follow } \mathbf{Growth-Golden-Ratio-Pattern}$$

Photon also occupies above Property of the Material Point and the Growth-Pattern.

With this way Photon's frequency $\rightarrow f_p = 1 / T_p$ Kick - Start, everything found on its-way.

From relation, constant $k = \frac{1}{f_n \cdot a^3} \rightarrow$ or $l = k \cdot f_n^2 \cdot a^3 \leftarrow$ then the cave-Semi-major-axis

$$a = \sqrt[3]{T^2 / k} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{g \cdot f^2}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{16 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot r^2}{(6+2\sqrt{5}) \cdot g \cdot \sigma^2}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{8 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot r^2}{(3+\sqrt{5}) \cdot g \cdot \sigma^2}}, \text{ and the } f_R = \frac{w}{2\pi} = \sqrt[2]{\frac{1}{g \cdot a^3}} \dots\dots(c)$$

From (c) is seen that the Resonance-frequency f_R follows the **Growth-Golden-Ratio-Pattern**.

3). The Produced Work \equiv motion, in Material-Point ZD, becomes the Initial frequency f_N , as

$$f_N [S \equiv f_{1=n}, f_2, f_3, f_R = w^2] = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} = \frac{n\sigma \cdot \bar{B}}{8 r^2} \leftarrow \text{ and so is the meter of Stationary motion.}$$

In case that Conductor [$Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = D$], Anti-Conductor [$D = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = Z$] combine to form

The Special Pattern as < Standing-Wave > then at Nodes Stress $\sigma_N = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi} = \text{Constant}$ since $r = 0$ and at Anti-Nodes Pressure or Stress goes Up and Down \uparrow twice the Amplitude of the travelling wave as $2 [\pm \sigma_N = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi}] = 2 \cdot k$, since the equation of a Standing wave is $y(x, t) = 2a \cdot (k x - w t)$.

Because in 1-Conductor-Case a Screw-motion is Torque T_{xy} and created in an Perpendicular to

ZD Plane, Torque $\rightarrow T_{ZA} = \sigma \cdot |ZA|^2 = (2\pi f r) \frac{a^2}{\Phi} = w r \frac{a^2}{\Phi} = \bar{v} \frac{a^2}{\Phi} = \sigma \Phi^3 = \bar{c} \frac{a^2}{\Phi}$, and Stress $\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$

$$= \frac{2\pi r b f}{\Phi} = \left[\frac{F \cdot r^2}{2}\right] = \left[\frac{e \cdot a^2}{2}\right] = 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \cdot \left[\frac{a^2}{2}\right], \text{ C.m}^2, \text{ and the nodes are curves as (one-dimensional)}$$

one less than the dimension of the System. In the three dimensional Systems *as this is the one electron in Hydrogen-cave*, The Nodes are two Dimensional Surfaces and their States are, The Spherical harmonics.[70]

4). Since $T_{ZA} = \sigma \cdot |ZA|^2 = (2\pi f r) \frac{a^2}{\Phi} = w r \frac{a^2}{\Phi} = \bar{v} \frac{a^2}{\Phi} = \sigma \Phi^3 = \bar{c} \frac{a^2}{\Phi}$ carries $\frac{a^2}{\Phi}$ the Golden-Ratio-Pattern

of $\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi} = \frac{\bar{v}}{\Phi} = \frac{G}{\Phi^3}$, of a Surface $A = \pi \cdot r^2 = |ZA|^2 = \Phi^2$ to the Unmeasured Photoelasticity

Fringe - Pattern { Morse-Code \equiv Informations }, which can be transferred from Atoms. This Procedure is used in **Photosynthesis** by Photons for more electricity Production.

The-Stress-Way of Photon-Storages is $\bar{f}_N = \sigma / 2\pi r$, and *Photon-Information* $f_n = \sigma \Phi / 2\pi r$. Thus Informations as Waves are The **Colored Fringes**, The **Stresses**, or frequencies are Deposited in **Atoms** as Magnetic fields and **Stationary Strains**, while **Motion** = Energy = Waves = **Golden Ratio** Φ , which Enters The **Geometry-Vectors**, and forms The **Elementary-Particles**. [52]

From Wave-Energy Constant $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} = \frac{2\pi f}{c} = \frac{w}{c} = \left|\frac{\bar{v}}{c}\right| \cdot |r_{A-KA}|$, issues $c = \frac{w}{k} = \lambda f$, or $\left|\frac{\bar{c}}{2 \cdot |AK_A|}\right| \equiv f$

i.e. 1..The frequency f_{AK_A} of Pipe $|AK_A|$, is the Stationary-Photon's Energy-Storage $\boxed{\bar{f}_n} \equiv \left|\frac{\bar{c}}{2 \cdot |AK_A|}\right|$

and $f_{Reson} = \sigma \Phi^3 = G$, or $\sigma = \frac{G}{\Phi^3} = \frac{G \cdot \sigma^3}{c^3}$ and $\sigma^2 G = c^3$, where σ_{Res} is between all frequencies.

2..Since Stresses follow equation $\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi}$, conclusively since all Forces and Areas are every-where and are related to their-cave r , through their frequency, f , therefore it is the mean of motion for every-Information.

3..Since Photon equation is $\Rightarrow \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n + f_n] \equiv |\frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^2}| \cdot [\bar{B}_n] + |\bar{c}| \cdot f_n$, when $c = 0$, motion is $|\frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^2}| \cdot [\bar{B}_n]$ which is motion in a Standing wave. Photon is of Dual nature and is Electromagnetic field where the Electric-field Produces the Work and the Magnetic - Field Stores the Work.

The Self-Growth Property of the Golden Ratio Stress σ :

Figure – 7 . The Golden ratio Φ on Segment AB , and Growth on Perpendicular-Planes .

From relation $\rightarrow f_n = [\frac{2}{\pi^2 r^2}] \cdot \bar{B} \equiv [\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}] \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \equiv [\frac{\Phi \sigma}{2\pi r}]$, then $\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{2\pi r f_n}{\Phi} = \frac{\bar{v}}{\Phi} = \frac{\lambda \cdot f}{\Phi}$, or $[2r] \cdot f_n \cdot \pi = \sigma \cdot \Phi = [\lambda] \cdot \pi$, $f_n = \pi \cdot [\lambda \cdot f_n] =$ Energy E_n from a Wave of frequency f_n and Wavelength λ .

Total Energy $2 \cdot E_n = \sigma \cdot \Phi = \sigma \cdot \left\{ \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} \right\} = \sigma \cdot \{ 1,6180339, -0,6180339 \} = \sigma \cdot \{ e^+, e^- \}$, where for $\sigma = 1$ then, $2 \cdot e^+ = 1,6180339$, $e^- = -0,6180339 \rightleftharpoons$ eV, which are the Unit -Active and Passive Actions between Material-Points $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$. This Property of Energy relation on Φ , either is Active or Passive and is translated as $\sigma \cdot \{ e^+, e^- \}$, Markos Program uses above relations.

3b... The Duality Of Isochronous – Photons : [77]

Photon is the first Propagating Material-Point in existing Universe in where ,

- 1.. The Space and the Anti-Space are linearly effecting and equilibrium , .
- 2.. The Space and the Anti-Space are Perpendicularly effecting and equilibrium .
- 3.. The Space and the Anti-Space are Torsionally effecting and equilibrium .

Figure – 8- : The Material-Geometry Mechanism of motion in Photons-Cave :

FROM MECHANICS **The Eternal-Rotation** of the Two Elements , $[\oplus \cup \ominus]$, Up or Down in Material Point circles ,Originates the Spins , $\pm \frac{1}{2}$, ± 1 , $\mp \frac{1}{2}$, of All Particles Fermions or and Bosons which combine from above Three-States just by Adding their Spins [36] . From Cauchy-Stress-Tensor under Plane-Stress conditions the **Equation of Principal-Stresses** $\sigma_{1,2}$, is $\sigma_{1/2} = \pm$

$\pm (\frac{1}{2}) . \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + 4 . \sigma_2^2} = \sigma_1 . [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \sigma . \Phi$, which is the **Golden-ratio-Pattern** of the Material Point as Type of a vanishing Shear due to layers laterally shifted . Equilibrium of , ABCD , ABFE , CDEF Quadrilaterals is through Ptolemy's and Ceba's Equilibrium - relations , Fig-14 .

The above Material Point is the Energy-Structure of Photon which is Quantized and Equilibrium. **Stability of Photon's** construction of , ABCD , Rectangle issues through **Ptolemy's -Theorem** for **Inner - Connectors** [AC.BD = AB.CD + AD.CB] , and the **Ceba's Theorem** for the three **Outer Connectors** of , ABCD , CDEF , Rectangles as \rightarrow [CD.AE.FB = CB.FE.AD] , BDEF , Rectangle as \rightarrow [BD.AE.GF = BF.GE.AD] , AEFC , Rectangle as \rightarrow [AE.GF.BC = AC.BF.GE] . With this Way is succeeded the Stability of the whole structure of Photon .

This minimum quantized Energy σ , was Proved that is going out the Material Point , *because of Skin effect* , as acceleration and creates the Stationary gravity g as f_n , acting on Spin as $S_{PA} . r^4$. The Centripetal Force and equal to Stress σ , is $F_c = mv^2 / r =$

$$\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = -g . \frac{s}{4r} \text{ or } \{ \ddot{s} = -w^2 s \} . (wr)^2 / r = w^2 . r = \pm \sigma = (2\pi . f_1)^2 . r =$$

$\sigma_1 . [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \Phi . \sigma$, and since mass is $m = \frac{\sigma}{w^2 . r} = \frac{\sigma}{w . c} = \frac{\bar{B}}{r . c}$ then , $\pm \sigma = \frac{c . \bar{B}}{r^2}$ which is a relation between Stress Momentum and light-velocity c . It was shown in [70-P32] that in a Cycloid , the area between the curve and the straight line is $A = 3\pi r^2$ and the arc length $l = 8r$. For the motion on cycloid , we consider a Weight Q , at a point A , moving with free motion.

Since reaction N is vertically acting , doesn't give any Tangential component therefore the only one becomes from Q , which is equal to $AT = g . \sin \varphi$ and since $\sin \varphi = \frac{s}{4r}$ and then $AT = g . \frac{s}{4r}$. Since acceleration $a = \frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = \frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(\frac{ds}{dt}) = -g . \frac{s}{4r}$ then where $w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{g}{4r}$ } ... (a) which (a) is a Harmonic Oscillatory motion showing that Acceleration is proportional to displacement

and is directed towards the origin with a Period $T = \frac{2\pi}{w} = 2\pi . \sqrt{\frac{4r}{g}} = 4\pi . \sqrt{\frac{r}{g}}$, or and $w^2 = [\frac{g}{4r}]^2$, where

$w = 2\pi f$. **Origination of Frequency , or Period** , happens from above Property where

$w = [\frac{g}{4r}] = 2\pi f$. In Material-Point the Cycloidal-acceleration g_{cyc} is transformed as Centrifugal acceleration $g_{cyc} = \frac{(v)^2}{R} = \frac{g}{4r}$, where r = the Radius of the Cycloidal-circle and R = the radius of curvature . In Cycloid velocity-vector $\bar{v} \equiv \bar{\sigma}$, and it is the Glue-Bond-Stress between the Opposites \oplus , \ominus so velocity $\bar{v} = \bar{w} . r = 2\pi . \bar{f} . r = \bar{\sigma} = \sigma \Phi$, the Frequency $\bar{f} = \frac{\bar{\sigma} = [\sigma \Phi]}{2\pi r}$ and the Total-Energy

$2L = J . w^2 = 4\pi^2 . f^2$. The Circular frequency is $w^2 = \frac{(\sigma \Phi)^2}{r^2} = [2\pi f]^2$, and the **Frequency of Photon**

$$\text{is } \rightarrow f_p = \left| \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r} \right| = \frac{[1 + \sqrt{5}] \sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma . \Phi}{2\pi r} \dots\dots (a) \text{ i.e.}$$

Equation (a) denotes that the Harmonic - Oscillation due to Any-Force or Weight , which Follows the free motion on Cycloid , is Independent of the Amplitude of oscillation and , is Isochronous . This Property belongs to Photon also , since it is a Material - Point . [70]

Since Total-Energy $L = B w - \frac{1}{2} w - \frac{1}{2} w^2$ then $2L = J . w^2$, and $\bar{B} = r . mv - r \frac{\pi . r^4}{2} 2\pi f r = \pi^2 . r^4 . f$.

From momentum relation $\bar{B} = m r v = m r^2 w = m r^2 (2\pi f) = \frac{1}{2} w = [\frac{\pi r^4}{2}] . [2\pi f]$ then **Spin S** \equiv

$$\equiv \text{Angular-momentum } \bar{B} \equiv \bar{S} = \frac{1}{2} w = \frac{\pi r^4}{2} [2\pi f] = \pi^2 . r^4 . [f] \equiv \frac{[1 + \sqrt{5}] \sigma . \pi . r^3}{4} = \frac{\pi r^3 \Phi . \sigma}{2} \dots\dots (b)$$

Frequency of Photon is $f_n = \frac{[(1 + \sqrt{5}) \sigma]}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r}$, where $\Phi = \frac{(1 + \sqrt{5})}{2} = 1,6180339887$ and , $2r$

is The Diameter of Energy-Cave $AB = 2r$ of circle $(O,OA) = \text{Monad} \rightarrow \oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus \equiv 1 + \Phi$ and

$BC = |\sigma| = \text{The Glue-Bond-Vector}$, $\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus$, from the main-Stresses magnitude,

$ABCD = |\sigma| \cdot |\Phi + 1| = \text{The Energy-Space Rectangular Parallelogram in Plane ABC}$.

$ABFE = -|\sigma| \cdot |\Phi + 1| = \text{The Energy-Anti-Space Rectangular Parallelogram in Plane ABC}$

$BF = |\Phi \cdot \sigma| = \text{The Anti-Space-Vector}$, and $FG = |\Phi| = \text{The Space-Vector}$ magnitude.

In circle of AB diameter is created the Stress $\sigma = BC$ and both the Resultant-monad $BD = AC$.

From Kepler 2nd Orbit laws the Unit-Quantized-Area, or Unit Quantized Energy is that per /sec $\rightarrow r \cdot d\phi$, following equation $1 = k \cdot f_u^2 \cdot r^3$, and expresses the area of triangles in Fig-8.

In Figure \rightarrow Triangle 2(ABC) = BC.BA = $\sigma \cdot [\Phi + 1] \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi + \sigma = [\text{Stress-In-Storage-}\Phi] +$

[Moving-Stress] Or **Storage S** = $[\oplus \leftarrow r \equiv \Phi \rightarrow \ominus]$ + **Motion M** = $[\bar{v} - \text{Vector}]$

and from Figure -3- where Stress σ is the motion and $\sigma \Phi$ the Storage, issues Geometry,

Triangle 2(BFG) = FB.FG = $\sigma \cdot \Phi[\Phi] = \sigma \cdot \Phi^2 = \sigma \cdot [\Phi + 1] \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi + \sigma \equiv S_{\text{storage}} + M_{\text{motion}}$

Triangle 2(DEG) = EG.ED = $\sigma + \sigma \Phi = \sigma \cdot [1 + \Phi] \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi + \sigma \equiv S_{\text{storage}} + M_{\text{motion}}$, and

since Energy = motion / T $\equiv \left(\frac{v}{2\pi r}\right) \cdot [\sigma + \sigma \Phi] = \bar{v} \cdot \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r}\right] \equiv \bar{v} \cdot \left[\bar{f}_n + f_n\right] \equiv$

Moving - Storage $\rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n]$ \leftarrow + Moving-Frequency $\rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \leftarrow \equiv \text{Material-Point i.e.}$

The Energy produced in Photon-Cave is consisted of **Two-moving-Storages**, that travel

as Wave $[\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} = \bar{c} = \lambda \frac{f}{\Phi}] \rightarrow [S \equiv EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2]$ and,

as Particle $\rightarrow [f_1 = (E^2 + H^2) = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} = \frac{n\bar{B}}{\pi^2 r^4}] \rightarrow \{W \equiv EM-R \equiv [\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2] = 2 \cdot \lambda \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi\}$ and,

The Duality of an Energy-Storage $S \equiv \{[\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus] + \text{Motion M} \equiv [\bar{v} - \text{Vector}]\}$,

Therefore \rightarrow Photon is travelling Both as Particle and as Wave, as

1.. **Energy-Storage S** = $[\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus] \equiv \text{Particle } [\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} = \bar{c} = \lambda \frac{f}{\Phi}] \rightarrow \text{i.e.}$

a **Stationary Standing - Wave** $\rightarrow [S \equiv [EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2]]$.

2.. **Energy-Motion M** = $[\bar{v} - \text{Vector}] \equiv \text{The Wave } [\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \equiv [f_1 = (E^2 + H^2) = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} =$

$\frac{\bar{B}}{\pi^2 r^4}] \rightarrow \text{i.e. a Propagating Wave as } \rightarrow \{W \equiv EM-R \equiv [\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2] = 2 \cdot \lambda \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi [\phi = \frac{\bar{B}}{\Phi}]\} \leftarrow$

4b.. The moving Storages of Photons and The Stability of Dual-frequency f_{photon} :

Photon is a Material-Point in cave r , where its **Inner** is *the Stationary-Standing-wave from*

Electromagnetic-Wave $[E^2 + H^2] = 2(2r) \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi$ with n Lobes representing the

Normal mode vibration with frequencies $f_n = n \cdot f_1 = \frac{E}{h} = \frac{n \cdot v}{4r} = \frac{n\sigma}{8r} [1 + \sqrt{5}]$, and its

Outward is *as the Propagating Electromagnetic-Wave* $\rightarrow \{[\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2] = 2 \cdot \lambda \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi\} \leftarrow$

where Particle $2r = n \lambda$, **Cave** r , is the *Electromagnetic-Energy-Storage*, and *Electromagnetic-Radiation E,B is the Wave conveyer*. Following above constituents of Photon then, Since **Energy is motion** and the **Total - Energy of Elementary - Particle** is equal to the \rightarrow **Intrinsic Rotational + Kinetic Energy from velocity**, then according to the conservation law of Energy, **This Energy is stored into Neutral caves as Stationary Loops consisting the Lobes**, and thus producing the **Space and the Anti - Space Particles with velocity vector the remaining of the Energy Term**.

It is proved that Hydrogen cave is the lightest and less-mass element.

The Breakage - Principle, is the way of **Energy conservation**, where **Energy never annihilates and which is always reverted into** \rightarrow the two **Opposites** $\{(\pm w)$ or the **Conveyers** \equiv **Carriers** $\}$ and an **Neutral Part** $2 \cdot \nabla i$ which is the **Energy-store** \equiv a **Tank** \equiv The **Magnetic fields**.

Energy \equiv or as **Matter** $(+ w)$, as **Antimatter** $(- w)$ and as **Energy Part**, $2L = \bar{B} \cdot \bar{w}$

i.e. Energy \equiv Motion \equiv Space + Anti space + Kinetic Energy,

Vibrations of Systems issues for Orbits as $\rightarrow W = 4\pi^2 \cdot \frac{r^3}{T^2} \cdot \bar{n} = 4\pi^2 \cdot r^3 \cdot f_p^2 \cdot \bar{n} \leftarrow$ and agree, to

Kepler celestial law such as for *macrocosm and for microcosm* .

Using the Material-Geometry-Vectors for the **Anti-Space Action** then ,

From Force $G_{ON-AntiSpace} = \overline{AB} \times \overline{BF} \equiv [\Phi+1] \times \{ |\overline{\sigma}| \cdot \Phi \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi \} = \Phi^2 \cdot \sigma \Phi = \sigma \cdot \Phi^3$, or ,

$G_{AN} \equiv \overline{AB} \times \overline{BC} \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3 \equiv \boxed{\overline{\sigma} - \text{Stress}} \boxed{[\oplus \leftarrow \Phi \rightarrow \ominus]} \boxed{[\oplus \leftarrow \Phi \rightarrow \ominus]} \boxed{[\oplus \leftarrow \Phi \rightarrow \ominus]}$

and $\rightarrow \rightarrow \rightarrow$ **Primary-Energy** $\equiv G \cdot f_p \equiv h$ and OR $G^{-1} \times \sigma \times \Phi^3 \equiv 1 \leftarrow \leftarrow \leftarrow$ where

$G \equiv$ The Newton's-Universal Force = $6,680561 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3/\text{Ns}^2$

$\sigma \equiv$ The Glue-Bond-Stress in Material-Points $\sigma = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi} = 1,85 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Kg/m}^2$ and , f ,

in Planck's length $r = L_p = e^{-i(5\pi/2) \cdot 10}$ is the Frequency $f_{\text{Plank}} = \frac{c}{2\pi r} = 2,952362 \cdot 10^{42} \text{ H}$,

in Planck's Length $L_p = e^{-i(5\pi/2) \cdot 10} = \{ \sqrt{3} \cdot \pi \cdot 1,616199 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m} \}$

$\Phi \equiv$ The Golden-Ratio Pattern $\Phi = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})}{2} = 1,6180339887$

From above relations is seen that , in Universe exists the only one Force $G \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3$, which is

Acting on all **Quantized-Quantities** as $\rightarrow G \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3 \equiv \Phi^2 \cdot \{ \sigma \cdot \Phi \} \equiv 2\pi f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \vec{v} \equiv m a = \vec{c} \leftarrow$

and From $\sigma \times \Phi^3 \equiv G \rightarrow [1,846462 \cdot 10^{-11}] \cdot [3,618033989] = 6,680561 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ o.e.}\delta.(\mathbf{q.e.d})$

i.e. Universe is a Monad , Becoming from a **HUGE-MAGNET** of Opposites \oplus , \ominus which Forms $>$

\rightarrow The 3-Dimensional **SPACES** Φ , **ANTI-SPACES** $|\Phi \cdot \sigma|$, and $> \rightarrow$ Energy , where

ENERGY \equiv **MOTION** through the **G** - Force , and the Stress - σ - becoming from Photon .

Or . **The Ubiquity of Material-Geometry in Electromagnetism** is Everywhere .

Remarks on the **Duality-Photon** $\rightarrow \{ \vec{c} \cdot \boxed{\vec{f}_n} + \vec{c} \cdot \mathbf{f}_n \} \leftarrow \equiv \rightarrow$ Particle + Wave \leftarrow

a.. From equations $f = \frac{\sigma_1 \Phi}{2\pi r}$ and $\sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \sigma \cdot \Phi$, then **Frequency** f_p , of Photon , is

Independent of the Amplitude $[\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2]$ of the Vibration , it is **Not-Damped and Not-Driven** , and so can be related to **Any-Force that can Produce Work** \equiv **Energy as Wave** and thus can be **Quantized to any Monad** . The Electromagnetic-Spectrum \equiv **Photon** in all its frequencies , which as **Frequency** f , or as **Period** T , is the Regulator of the Light - Signals .

b.. **Photon** striking on an Object of Microcosm or Macrocosm then , **It is a Source** that **Gives** \rightarrow **Energy** as Energy-Storage , $\boxed{\vec{f}_n}$, and **Information** as the G-Ratio Propagating - Energy \mathbf{f}_n .

c.. **Photon** in the Microcosm of Hydrogen-Cave can-Give such **Potential-Energy or Resonance Energy** as **Frequency** f_R and Energy in [**Bracket-Orbit-Hook**] which Joins the **Atoms to Produce the Molecules and Crystals** , MRI Photos and all Spectrum frequencies .

d.. **Photon** striking on **Hydrogen-Cave** can Produce the **Resonance-Energy-Frequency** f_R , such that can Produce **Photos** and **Image-Fringes** of Inter-Atom or any other Structures in Atoms .

e.. **Photon** striking on **Cells** can Produce a **Resonance-Energy-Frequency** f_R , such that can **Enter Cell** and **Break-It-Up** . Duality-Photon Places the Storages $\boxed{\vec{f}_n}$ everywhere then it stops and diffuses. The **Kinetic-Energy** E_K of a moving Material - Point , *as this is the Photon* , is stored as motion in its Storage , $r = [n \lambda/2]$ with the , n frequencies $f_n = n \cdot f_1$, with n lobes and with the fundamental frequency f_1 .

From above is seen the **Passage and The -How EM-Radiation can travel in Crystals** and which are the **Cauchy-Stress-Tensor** where $E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3$, in-where Energy Propagates along 3 Directions **without Birefringence** which are the tracks of the Stresses , and carries the motion \equiv Energy Storage r which radiation is **The Conveyer** , the Storages $\boxed{\vec{f}_n}$, **the Magnetic fields** .

Above procedure can be used in Cells where cells are cases of a **Birefringence material** and their **Resonance Passage** happens as the Force of *EM-Radiation in Two directions*, can travel in Cell through *Cauchy Stress Tensor* where the Two Conveyers $E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3$, can carry the Energy-Storage, r , in Cell. Interfacial Properties are detected from Surfactant, and can change the *Inner-Structure of Cell to another desirable Property*. A wide Analysis in [84-86-90].
 Moreover, in open Conductors the Conductor's Resultant-energy-Vector is as an **Cruise-missile** where for Primary-Forces Energies $|k_x, k_y| = |\leftrightarrow, \updownarrow| \equiv \varkappa$ become very strong **Cruise-Ballistic-missile**.

5b... The Quantum Interference of the Duality-Photon :

Quantum Interference is the Phenomenon when, a Photon Interferes with itself. [92E]
 This Proposition is Right when Photon is considered having a twin-existence, which is [101]3c.P-21
 The Problem is to determine the expression of the Power developed by Gravitational
 From Dual-Photon-equation, $\vec{v} \cdot [\vec{f}_n + f_n] \equiv | \frac{\vec{v}}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4 n} \cdot [\vec{B}_n] + | \vec{c} | f_n$, when $\vec{c} = 0$ or $\vec{c} = \vec{c}$, then **Photon motion** becomes $\rightarrow | \frac{\vec{v}}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4 n} \cdot [\vec{B}_n] \leftarrow \equiv$ **Spin**. i.e. **The Stationary Photons exist as their Spin only.**
 This **Rest-Space** is the Part $| \frac{\vec{v}}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4 n} \cdot [\vec{B}_n]$, and its Communication Code to be the term $| \frac{\vec{v}}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4 n} | = | \frac{w r}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4} | = | \frac{2 v}{2\pi^3 r^4} |$, The Rest Space is a Stationary Wave with fundamental frequency $f_1 = \frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{c}$, with an Electric Wave, that is acting on vector $\vec{c} = (i \cdot c_x + j \cdot c_y)$. It was proved [78] that the Newton's Gravitational constant G does NOT effect on Plane Surfaces, but on Volume Surfaces only.

This Property of G, means that the only one Force which effects on the Rest-Space in *Torsional motion*, and on the light velocity vector \vec{c} , is the gravity g only.

**Figure - 9- : The Stability of $\rightarrow \{ \oplus - \text{Space [Electric Wave] } , \{ \ominus - \text{Anti-Space [Magnetic Wave] } \}$ of the Sub-Space $\{ [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] \equiv ds \equiv [\oplus \leftarrow ds \rightarrow \ominus] - \text{or} - \text{The Neutral-Space } [A_E, B_E, C_E] \}$:
 Since \vec{c} is constant, it is analyzed to, (c_x, c_y) in any two directions x, y where $x \perp y$ and y to be the gravity direction on where gravity is acting .**

The produced Work is in y - Range , $S_y = c_y t - \frac{1}{2} g t^2 = c \sin at - \frac{1}{2} g t^2$, where maximum Range is $S_{\max-y} = c_y^2 / 2g = \frac{(c \sin at)^2}{2g} = [\frac{c^2}{2g}] \sin^2 a$, happening at angle $a = 90^\circ$ and where $\sin^2 a = 1$.

Since at Point (1) the velocity $v_y = 0$, the motion in 0-1 , maybe considered as falling in linear motion and so issues $v_y = g t$ or time $t = \frac{v_y}{g} = \frac{(c \sin at)}{g}$, as halve Period with total Period $\rightarrow T = \frac{2(c \sin at)}{g}$.

In figure are seen the 4-Point Positions , at where change the Phase and the Work done in each Phase of Photon's inner motion . The 4-Phases correspond to the Wavelength λ , as $\lambda / 4$. distance with $90^\circ = \frac{\pi}{2}$ to be the change of Phase . **This means that the Produced Work in Prior Phase-Area as Golden - Ratio Pattern is Stored in the Next and Perpendicular Phase-Area .**

The Total distance for doing Work is the Wavelength λ , in total Period T as $\lambda = c_x T = c \cdot \cos a \cdot T$

or
$$\lambda = c \cdot \cos a \cdot \frac{2(c \sin at)}{g} = [\frac{2c^2}{g}] \sin a \cdot \cos a = [\frac{c^2}{g}] \sin 2a , \dots\dots\dots(1)$$
 since from trigonometry exists , $\sin 2a = 2 \sin a \cdot \cos a$.

The maximum wavelength λ happens when $\sin 2a = 1$ or $2a = 90^\circ$ and $a = 45^\circ$, i.e. $\rightarrow \rightarrow$

The Total motion in the Wavelength λ , corresponds to the angle $a = 45^\circ$, meaning that the motion of Space , The Electric-field , and Anti-space , The Magnetic-field , equilibrium as an Bellow . The two Wings in 90° Type simultaneously oscillate to its 45° Bisector -axis , and the Produced Work from The Electric-field-area , is Stored into the Magnetic - field - area . The common axis of the two Perpendicular fields , carry the G-Ratio Surfaces , Runs with the same velocity \bar{c} to the direction of the inner motion \rightarrow

or ,

From $90^\circ \rightarrow 45^\circ$, the created Work $W = c_y g$, and is Symmetrically Stored from $0^\circ \rightarrow 45^\circ$

The created Work in [0-1] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [1`-2] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [0`-1`-1`] = \perp Surface [1`-2`-2`] .

The created Work in [1-2] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [2-3`] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [1`-2`-1`] = \perp Surface [2`-3`-2`] .

The created Work in [2-3] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [3`-4] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [2`-3`-3`] = \perp Surface [3`-4`-4`] .

The created Work in [3-4] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [3`-4] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [3`-4`-2] = \perp Surface [4`-5`-4`] .

Since from Trigonometry issues $\sin 2\pi = \sin(180 - 2a) = \sin 2(90 - a)$ then (1) becomes .

$$\lambda = c \cos a \frac{2(c \sin at)}{g} = [\frac{2c^2}{g}] \sin a \cdot \cos a = [\frac{c^2}{g}] \sin 2a = [\frac{c^2}{g}] \cdot \sin(\pi - 2a) = [\frac{c^2}{g}] \cdot \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - a) \dots(2)$$

since $\sin 2a = \sin(180 - 2a) = \sin(\pi - 2a)$, and also $\sin 2a = \sin(180 - 2a) = \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - a)$

From Dual-Photon-equation , $\bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n] + f_n] \equiv | \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} | \cdot [\bar{B}_n] + | \bar{c} | f_n$, when $c = 0$ or $\bar{c} = \bar{c}$, then Photon motion becomes $\rightarrow | \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} | \cdot [\bar{B}_n] \leftarrow \equiv \text{Spin}$. i.e. **The Stationary Photons exist as their Spin only .**

The Rest-Space is the Part $| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} | \cdot [\bar{B}_n]$ where $v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c$, and Communication Code to be the term $| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} | = | \frac{n \cdot \pi \cdot c}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} | = | \frac{n \cdot c}{\pi \cdot r_n^3} | = | \frac{w \cdot r}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4} | = | \frac{2 \pi \cdot f}{\pi^2 \cdot r^3} | = | \frac{2 \cdot f}{(\pi \cdot r^3)} |$ with **Electromagnetic-Radiation** the in monads frequency- f , which is satisfied by the relation $|\frac{2(rw)}{2v}| = \pi / 2 , \pi , 3\pi / 2 , \dots , n \cdot [\pi / 2]$, and $w = n \cdot [\frac{\bar{v}}{2r}] \times [\frac{\pi}{2}]$,

where $n = 1 \rightarrow \infty$. **When two Photons** strike each other , $\bar{c} = \bar{c}$, or reflect on a wall , then

$c = 0$, and from Spin $\bar{S} = \bar{B} = \pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot f_1$ its angular velocity $w = n \cdot [\frac{\bar{v}}{2r}] \times [\frac{\pi}{2}] = 2\pi \cdot f_1$, where then

its fundamental frequency $f_1 = n \cdot [\frac{\bar{v}}{2r}] \times [\frac{1}{4}] = n \cdot [\frac{\bar{v}}{8r}]$ which for $n = [\frac{16 \cdot r^2}{v \cdot c}]$ increases to $\frac{\lambda}{c} \cdot r^3$, and Photon-motion becomes $\rightarrow |\frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot n}| \cdot [\bar{B}_n] \leftarrow \equiv \text{Spin}$, i.e. **The Stationary Photons are Spin only and consist an Stationary- Harmonic-Vibration with the same Period T of the two Waves** [92-E].

The effective-Range of the Wavelength λ , for the Dual-Photon is related to the consistence v_x, v_y , velocities to any two Perpendicular directions of Electromagnetic fields E_x, E_y . The maximum displacement in y, direction is the centrifugal $\lambda_x = \frac{v^2 y}{2 E_y}$ and since $v_y = c$, $\sin(\varphi) \lambda_y = \frac{c^2 \cdot \sin^2(\varphi)}{2 E_y}$ where φ = the Phase difference between the two vibrations. Since time t, is the same between the two vibrations where then $t = \frac{v_y}{E_y} = \frac{c \cdot \sin(\varphi)}{E_x}$ and since the Period = 2.t then $T = \frac{2c \cdot \sin(\varphi)}{E_x}$ (2)

From the in x \rightarrow direction velocity $v_x = c \cdot \cos(\varphi)$, and displacements, λ_x, λ_y , become, $\lambda_x = v_x T = c \cdot \cos(\varphi) \cdot \{\frac{2c \cdot \sin(\varphi)}{E_x}\} = \lambda_x = \{\frac{2 \cdot c^2}{E_x}\} \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\varphi) = \{\frac{c^2}{E_x}\} \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \varphi)$ (3)

Since in trigonometry issues, $\sin(2\varphi) = \sin(\pi - 2\varphi) = \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi)$ and in Physics $E_x = g$, then

$$\rightarrow \lambda_x = \{\frac{c^2}{g}\} \cdot \sin(\pi - 2\varphi), \lambda_y = \{\frac{c^2}{g}\} \cdot \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi) \leftarrow \dots\dots(4)$$

- i.e. **Photons occupy**
- 1.. **The Dual-Property of Particles and Waves**,
 - 2.. **The Dual-Property of Stationary and Spin**,
 - 3.. **The Dual-Property of Simultaneous existence**,
 - 4.. **As Electric and Magnetic Fields in, λ_x, λ_y ,**
 - 5.. **The Bellow motion in transverse E-M- Waves the way to fly,**
 - 6.. **The Transverse E-M- Waves are \perp to Propagation-Direction,**
 - 7.. **The Electric Effective Range is thrust through G only. [Fig-9]**.
 - 8.. **With the same initial velocity is succeeded the same Length-Range with Two complementary angles.**

Remarks :

- 1.. The Produced-Work happens at $\lambda / 4$. wavelength in 4-Phases and it is Quantised .
- 2.. The Quantised-Work in $\lambda / 4$. wavelength is the $\frac{1}{2}$ of the first lobe of the Sinusoidal Wave .
- 3.. Photons follow the Aeroplanes Bellow motion to fly as (thrust - drag , weight - lift) .
- 4.. It was shown that when **Two Photons** strike each other, $\vec{c} = \vec{c}$, or reflect on a wall, **then** $c = 0$ and the produced energy enters the cave r. **The fundamental frequency of the Stationary-cave is** $f_1 = n \cdot \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} = n \cdot [\frac{\bar{v}}{2r}] \times [\frac{1}{4\pi}] = n \cdot [\frac{\bar{v}}{8\pi \cdot r}]$ which for $n = [\frac{8\pi r c}{v \cdot \lambda}]$ increases to $\frac{\lambda}{c}$, therefore for $n = N \cdot [\frac{8\pi r c}{v \cdot \lambda}] = N \cdot |\frac{8\pi r}{\lambda}|$, and for $N \rightarrow \infty$ then $f_1 = E / h = \infty$ (b)

In Dual Photon $\bar{v} [\frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}] \equiv \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n + f_n]$, **Colours are Still-Sub-Units of Storage** $[\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n]$, and exist as **Frequencies**, Violet, Blue, Green, which Stabilize with their Complementary colors Yellow, Orange, Red, of wavelength $d = \lambda \rightarrow \lambda_{min} \approx \lambda_{max} = 3.10^{-7} m \approx 3 \cdot \sqrt{3} \cdot 10^{-7} m$

- 4-1.. **The Quanta of Energy**, Passing through a Unit-Surface or Volume is **Inversely Proportional** to the **fourth Power** of the wavelength λ as $I = 0,5865 \cdot \{\frac{1}{\lambda^4}\}$. **When** $f_{BE} = E / h = \infty$ then the Energy-Intension Increases and the **wavelength λ Decreases** and for $f_{BE} = \infty$ then $\lambda = 0$.

This is what happens to Photons in **Black-Holes** where $d = \lambda = 0$, and in where $E = f_{BE} = \infty$.

- 4-2.. **The Proton Total- Harmonic- Charge** $\rightarrow Q_T \equiv 2 \cdot q_u + q_d$, and from $d = \lambda$ then $f_p = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m \lambda}}$

Applying the above to **White light**, which is composed of all colours of visible light with different

wavelengths ,when it passes through our atmosphere the tiny molecules cause it to scatter . Scattering or the redirectioning , increases as the wavelength of the light decreases .Violet , Blue , Green , have **Shortest** wavelength and **more Scattering** , while Yellow , Red , Dark-Red have **Longest** wavelength and **Shortest Scattering** , as is the Raylight-scattering . Atoms have a common way for Recognizing the **In-Between Electromagnetic Pattern** , and which is through the , **Resonance of tone** \equiv

The **Resonance frequency** , $f_R = \sqrt{\frac{k}{M}}$, where k = Their Stiffness and M = The **Harmonic-mass** of their Compound .

In Mechanics , the Kinetic Energy is equal to Potential $E_K = E_P$, and Total Energy $E_T = 2.E_K = 2.E_P$ or $\rightarrow \frac{1}{2} m v_i^2 = \frac{1}{2} k d = \frac{1}{2} m (w r_i)^2$, and for stability issues , $k d = m w^2 . d^2$, or $w^2 = \frac{k}{m} [\frac{1}{d}]$, or $\bar{w} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m} [\frac{1}{d}]} = 2\pi f$, and $f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{md}}$. From Energy equation $E = h f = \frac{h}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} = \frac{6,6260696.10^{-34}}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$

$= 1,054572.10^{-34} \sqrt{\frac{k}{md}}$. $J = 1,0545717.10^{-34} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} / (1,6022.10^{-19} eV) = 6,582022.10^{-16} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$. eV = $E_K + E_P$, i.e. In Mechanics , The equality of the Two **Opposite-quantities** $E_K = E_P$, is conserved

in a **common loop** as $\rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{k}{md}} eV \leftarrow$ meaning that when two Photons strike each other then the Produced Work is kept in the cave , r , as fundamental frequency $f_1 = n \frac{\sigma\phi}{2\pi r}$, and which is equal to **The Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors of the Photons-Heap** .

Above Procedure and because of their **common Inertia of Atoms-masses** allows us to accept the **angular- velocities of each Atom separately** , This Property also exists in Atoms Bonding .

Figure - 10 - : The Stability of Photon as Electromagnetic Wave with the Two frequencies .

The Dual Property of The **Simultaneous existence** as Electric and as Magnetic Fields in wavelengths , λ_x , λ_y , as **Effective Range** .which is thrusted through the Newton's Gravitational Force G , only becomes from the Trigonometry relations ,

$$\sin(2\phi) = \sin(\pi - 2\phi) = \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - \phi) \text{ and from Physics } E_x = g .$$

5-1..Maxwel Electric Displacement current $\partial D / \partial t$ is created from (c_x , c_y) Vectors motion , which happens from the gravity continuous action which produces the Work $W = c_y g$, Since $E-W$, $M-W$, are both the Resultance of circular -frequencies W_R , it reveals the

coupling of motion $\{ E-W \} \rightarrow \partial \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} / \partial t$, $\{ M-W \} \rightarrow \partial \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} / \partial t$, $\{ E-W \}$.

This means that the Source-charge of Electromagnetic waves are the Vectors = Resultants E-W , M-W , where $W_{RX}, W_{RY} = \vartheta \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} / \vartheta t$, and $W_{RZ} = \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} = \bar{c}$, and are E-W = The Kinetic Energy and M-W = The Potential Energy Propagating from one Position to another without any matter being transferred . Both are Propagated by the action of the Gravity , g, c_y which exists without mass , through Gravity-Field-medium continuously only. The Dual-Property of Particles and Waves allow Electromagnetic waves to Propagate in an definite direction and simultaneously to Propagate themselves along , and independently of the medium , and this because are created by the vibration of an electric charge [\oplus, \ominus] .

5-2.. The Total Energy in Loops : [79]

It was shown in [58] that the maximum velocity in a closed System occurs in Common circle , when the two velocities , \bar{c}, \bar{v} are Perpendicular between them , and are not Producing Work from where then dispersion follows Pythagoras theorem and the Resultant Quantized linear Space length , r , becomes , as the Resultant of Energy Vectors as follows ,

$$r = |(\bar{c}.T)| = \sqrt{v^2 + c^2} \text{ and by using Space Vector } \bar{r} = |(\bar{c}.T)| = \sqrt{v^2 + c^2} \text{ then The total Rotating Energy is } \rightarrow \pm \bar{\Lambda} = \bar{p}.r = (M.c).r = (M.c). \sqrt{v^2 + c^2} \text{ and by squaring both sites } [\pm \bar{\Lambda}]^2 = p^2.r^2 = M^2.c^2.(v^2+c^2) = (M^2.v^2).c^2 + M^2.c^4 = (p^2.c^2) + M^2.c^4 = [p.c]^2 + [m_o.c^2]^2 \text{ or is } E_T = E_R + E_K \rightarrow \text{i.e.}$$

Total - Energy of Elementary-Particle = Intrinsic Rotational + Kinetic Energy ,

The velocity of Elementary Particles is the light velocity $c = v = 2\pi r . f_e$ and the

frequency $\rightarrow f_e = \frac{c}{2\pi.r}$ (a) Rotational Energy $E_R = \bar{B} . \bar{w} = 2L = J.w^2$ and

$$\rightarrow E_R = \left[\frac{\pi r^4}{8} \right] . \left[\frac{c^2}{r} \right] = \frac{\pi c^2}{8} r^3 = 3,53535.10^{16} . r^3 \dots\dots\dots(b)$$

Energy and frequency of Elementary Particles can be found from cave r , only since , c ,

$$\text{constant , and Total-Energy } \rightarrow E_T = E_R + E_K = \frac{\pi c^2}{8} r^3 + \frac{1}{2} m.v^2 = 3,535.10^{16} . r^3 + \frac{1}{2} m.v^2 \dots(c)$$

The mass of Elementary Particles is $m = \frac{E}{2r^2.w^2} = \frac{J.w^2}{2} . \frac{1}{2r^2.w^2} = \frac{J}{4.r^2} = \frac{\pi.r^2}{16}$, i.e. it is dependent

on Radius of Cave , and for cave $r = 10^{-62}$ mass $\rightarrow m = \frac{\pi.10^{-124}}{16} = 1,935. 10^{-125}$ kg.

When The SPACE acquires ENERGY as Velocity then becomes an Energy-monad . [26]

Applying Quaternion equation $[-\nabla\Lambda, \nabla_x\Lambda] = 0$ for Point ,O, and for constant velocity , \bar{c} , then issues $[-\nabla c, \nabla_x c] = 0$ where $[-\nabla c] \perp [\nabla_x c]$ which means that it is a Mechanism that instantly transports Breakage-masses in two directions Dynamically and Perpendicularly to all Inertial frames Layers . From their Velocity-Energy vector are Produced the Three Breakages as ,

$$[\pm s^2 = \pm (wr)^2] , \text{ and } [\nabla_i = 2(wr)^2] \text{ and from them subatomic Particles } \rightarrow \text{Fermion and Bosons .}$$

Rotating energy is $\rightarrow \pm \bar{\Lambda} = \bar{p}.r = (M.c).r = (M.c). \sqrt{v^2 + c^2}$ and squaring both sites

$$[\pm \bar{\Lambda}]^2 = p^2.r^2 = M^2.c^2.(v^2+c^2) = (M^2.v^2).c^2 + M^2.c^4 = (p^2.c^2) + M^2.c^4 = [p.c]^2 + [m_o.c^2]^2 \text{ or is } E_T = E_R + E_K \rightarrow \text{i.e.}$$

Total - Energy of Elementary-Particle = Intrinsic Rotational + Kinetic Energy ,

a).. Dot Product and Cross Product :

The Dot-Product happens for interactions between Similar dimensions ,while the Cross-product between Different-dimensions. Cross-product of any two vectors \bar{a}, \bar{b}

is $\bar{a} \times \bar{b} = |\bar{a}|.|\bar{b}| \sin \theta . \bar{n}$ and for $\bar{a} = \bar{b}$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ then $\bar{a} \times \bar{a} = \bar{a}^2$, and for

Quaternion , s , which performs the Work of rotating the one vector around the other

→ Work = $\bar{a} \times \bar{a} = \bar{a}^2 \cdot \bar{r}$, and for $\bar{a} = \bar{v}$ then, Work = $\bar{v}^2 \cdot \bar{r} = |\bar{v}| \cdot |\bar{v}| \cdot \bar{r} = v^2 \cdot r \cdot \bar{n}$
 = $(w r)^2 r \cdot \bar{n} = (2\pi r/T)^2 r \cdot \bar{n} = (4\pi^2 r^2 / T^2) \cdot r \cdot \bar{n} = \frac{4\pi^2 r^3}{T^2} \cdot \bar{n} = (4\pi^2 r^2 \cdot f^2) \cdot r \cdot \bar{n}$, or(w)

Work = $4\pi^2 \frac{r^3}{T^2} \cdot \bar{n} = 4\pi^2 \cdot r^3 \cdot f^2 \cdot \bar{n}$, which is the Kepler celestial law for *microcosm*.

Since in Mechanics issues $z^2 = s^2 - s^2 + 2.s.s = 1$, and from Unit-quaternion $s^2 + [iv]^2 = 1$ then is → $s^2 - v^2 = 1$... (d) Equation (d) is a **Cone relation** on where Total-energy, Kinetic and Potential is conserved and for Photon, Electromagnetic radiation is the Kinetic-energy and the Velocity-vector-Energy - tank is the Potential. Photon is an Energy-store, r , in a Stationary-wave of wavelength $n\lambda = 2r$ consisted of n stationary lobes filled in λ with inner motion the Electromagnetic - Displacement-current and Outward the Propagating, Energy-store $\lambda = 2r/n$, with the light speed, c , the two transverse fields, {the + Electric-field and the - Magnetic-field}. Equation (w) declares the relation between the *Total-Energy* W in caves, and the *Geometry* of Energy=cave Space $r \equiv [EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n]$ with a binding constant, *proved to be the g*.

6b.. The Origination of Light velocity c :

$g \equiv \frac{T^2}{a^3} \equiv \frac{1}{f^2 n a^3} \equiv 9,8076941 \rightarrow$ *The minimum Granular Quantized Energy,*

The Forces Beyond-Planck-Length are → $F = \Phi^3 \cdot [\oplus \sigma \ominus] = \sigma \times \Phi^3 \leftarrow \dots (1)$

Force G acts → on Spinning M-Points on \bar{S} through $\bar{g} \rightarrow$ on Planck's - $\bar{B} \rightarrow$ on g_G , through the **Resonance frequency** f_R . It was proved that $G = \sigma \Phi^3$, and $\sigma = \frac{G}{\Phi^3} = \frac{G \cdot \sigma^3}{c^3}$, or → $\sigma^2 G = c^3 \dots (2)$, where σ is a Stress between the frequencies. From Force-relation $F = \sigma A = (2\pi f r) \frac{A}{\Phi} = w r \frac{A}{\Phi} = \bar{v} \frac{A}{\Phi}$, is seen that force G becomes a velocity \bar{v} . In the case of Planck's length this velocity is $\bar{c} = w r = \frac{\sigma \cdot \Phi}{r} r_p = \sigma \times \Phi = \left| \frac{G L_p}{r \Phi^3} \right| \Phi = \left[\frac{G L_p}{r \Phi^2} \right]$ and from Gravity relation $G \equiv \sigma \times \Phi^3$, then issues → $\left[\bar{c} = \frac{G L_p}{r \Phi^2} \right] = \left[\bar{c} = \frac{2 G L_p}{\lambda \Phi^2} \right]$ which is the **Light-velocity vector**.

Since r , becomes from the Beyond-Planck's-Region then → $\bar{v} = \frac{F \cdot \Phi}{A} = \left[\frac{G \Phi}{A} \right] \dots (f)$

Equation (f) may be written as Force $G = \bar{v} \frac{A}{\Phi}$, which is a **Viscus-Damping-Force** where $\frac{A}{\Phi}$ is a constant of Proportionality and the equation of motion is $F_G = \left[\frac{A}{\Phi} \right] \cdot \dot{x}$ Force G is applied in all **Quantized-Universe A** as Velocity \bar{c} and as Stress σ on Spaces Anti-spaces as Spaces-relation $L_p = e^{i \cdot (\frac{\pi}{2} + 2k\pi) \cdot b}$, where from **Material-Geometry [24-58]**, Space $\equiv 1$ and Anti-Space $\equiv \sqrt{-1} = +1, -1$, and $\sqrt{-1} = i =$ The Imaginary Part into the → **Anti-Space + Space \equiv motion $\equiv i \equiv \sqrt{-1} \equiv \sqrt{-1} \equiv e^{-i \cdot (\frac{\pi}{4}) \cdot b} = 0,707106781 \cdot b$** . The Base b , which for Natural logarithms issues << The Natural logarithm $\ln(x)$ of a Magnitude x , is the Power to which, e , would have to be raised to equal x >> and is Defining that → $\ln(x)$ is the Period-needed to Grow x , as this is in Integration $\int x$, so e^x is the **Amount of Growth** after **Period x** and the Possible-Repetitive-Permutations for moulds and elements in which issues **Mould^{Elements} = The -Growth-Periods** i.e. when Mould = Elements then is succeeded maximum and for e is e^e , and any $\log_x x$. For $\log_x x$ and Base $x = 10$ then $\log_{10} 10 = 10^{10}$ and for the two elements $[\oplus, \ominus]$ is $10^{[10]^2} = 10^{20}$ **Positions \equiv Distances $\equiv r$** and since $10^{-x} = \frac{1}{10^x}$ then $b = 10^{-20}$, and

The Anti-Space + Space-Positions are , $0,707106781 \cdot 10^{-20} = 1,0707106781 \cdot 10^{-19}$.

In this Way The Non-Dimensional-number [$0,707106781 \cdot 10^{-1} = 0,0707106781$], Is Quantized in cave , r , as distance and Becomes The-Dimensional-Space in the Decimal - System $b=10$ as cave r , and which cave is $r = 1,0707106781$ or , $r = 1,0707106781$ m , having Unit-Area $\pi \cdot r^2 = 3.601588$ m² , and the QUA-Universe is $A = 3.601588 \cdot 10^{-19}$ m²/s , which are The Space + Anti-Space Positions in Universe ... (i)

From (h) , light-velocity $\bar{v} = \left[\frac{G \Phi}{A} \right] = \frac{6,673692 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot 1,6180339887}{3,601588 \cdot 10^{-19}} = 2.99819938 \cdot 10^8$ m/s

i.e. Gravity Force $G \equiv$ motion , exists without mass and is Quantized \rightarrow Spread in {Space and Anti-Space} or \equiv QUA \equiv { is The Quantized-Units In-Area of Space and Anti-Space } , and as a Mould Φ Golden-Ratio , exists in the Impedance b . Impedance in Mechanics is the Friction Coefficient , where for Force G to be Proportional to the Light-velocity $c = \bar{v}$, then the Harmonic - Oscillation is an Damped-Oscillator , and Can-Oscillate due to the excitation as ,

a.. with a frequency lower than in the Undamped case and an Amplitude Decreasing with time , the Under-Damped-Oscillator which Originates the Quantum of motion which is a limiting case between the oscillatory and Non-Oscillatory motion the Critical Damping , and which Originates the Light-velocity \bar{c} , [49]

b.. with Undamped case frequency and Decay to the Equilibrium-Position without oscillation and The Over-Damped-Oscillator Originating the n-times velocity c . What is Quantization of motion and Impedance is analytically referred in [83]

A Parallel solution becomes also from the attendant logic ,

The Three Elements \equiv Digits of Material-Geometry are $\rightarrow \{ \oplus , [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] , \ominus \} \equiv [+ , 0 , -] \leftarrow$
 The Permutation , arrangement , of the Two-Elements $P_1^2 = 2$, i.e. are $\rightarrow [\oplus , \ominus] - [\ominus , \oplus] \leftarrow$
 The Three-Elements in Space need $P_1^3 = 3 \cdot (3-1) \cdot (3-2) = 6$ Positions and the same for
 Three-Elements in Anti-Space need $P_1^3 = 3 \cdot (3-1) \cdot (3-2) = 6$ Positions , and Total Places \rightarrow
 $P_1^3 \cdot P_1^3 = 6 \times 6 = 36$ Positions for Spaces and Anti-Spaces as Impedance , and as the before for $\log_x x$ and Base $x = 10$ then $\log_{10} 10 = 10^{10}$ and for the two elements $[\oplus , \ominus]$ the Growth is $10^{[10]^2} = 10^{20}$ Positions \equiv Distances $\equiv r$, and since issues $10^{-x} = \frac{1}{10^x}$ then

$b = 36 \cdot 10^{-20}$, and $\rightarrow \bar{v} = \frac{F \Phi}{A} = \left[\frac{G \Phi}{A} \right] = \left[\frac{6,673692 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot 1,6180339887}{36 \cdot 10^{-20}} \right] = 2.9795163 \cdot 10^8$ m/s

i.e. The Ubiquity of Material-Geometry in Electromagnetism is Everywhere .

6b1..The Origination of Gravity-Stress g :

a.. The Gravitation Force G , and the Kick-Start : [89]

The G - Kick-Start , on frequency $\rightarrow f_p = 1 / T_p = \frac{w}{2\pi} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{g \cdot a^3}}$, in this world is , the How this frequency can Enter , Format and cohesive , the first or any other Energy-Cave in Planck's length , From Unit-relation [79] , $1 = g \cdot f_n^2 \cdot a^3 = \left[\frac{4\pi^2}{GM} \right] \cdot f_n^2 \cdot a^3$ was shown that , An Energy-Rim = Cave is a Plane - Surface , an orbit , representing a Constant Energy becoming from the squared Frequency f_n^2 , Representing the Imaginary Part , and r_n^3 , Representing the Real-Space-Part of monad as this is $1 = k \cdot f_n^2 \cdot r^3$. The Stationary-Energy is spread in one Plane as this happens for Stationary-waves in Caves , while in Propagating-Energy in two , as the Electromagnetic Transverse waves .

All these Energy-Rims consist the Quantized-Plane-curves .The two different motions of \oplus Space ,

⊖ Anti-space , in any cave r , and in a Finite Space , *The Revolving and Periodic Excitation* create an Eternal frequency which influence all other Spaces , *caves* The minimum quantized-energy is stored in the Gravity-Layer , g , becoming from the Unit energy of the sinus orbit .

From equation $g = T^2 / a^3$ and min- a then Period is $T = \sqrt{g \cdot a^3} = \sqrt{9,8076925 \cdot (2,1145016 \cdot 10^{-11})^3} = 3,04513 \cdot 10^{-16}$ s , **Since** the Unit-Work = sine Integral $= \int_0^t \frac{\sin t}{t} dt = 1$ and the semi-major axis , a , is $a = 2,1145016 \cdot 10^{-16}$ m , where frequency $T^{-1} = f_p = 3,28393 \cdot 10^{15}$ /s , which f_p corresponds to a Sphere-loop in Planck's scale as $(4/3) \cdot \pi \cdot r^3 = 3,96 \cdot 10^{-32}$ m³ , and then the Energy in this Planck's loop is the minimum quantized . From **Energy** $E = h \cdot f_p = [6,6262 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J.s }] \cdot [3,28393 \cdot 10^{15} / \text{ s }] = 2,176 \cdot 10^{-18}$ J , and in eV then $\rightarrow [2,176 \cdot 10^{-18}] / [1,6 \cdot 10^{-19}] = 13,6 \text{ eV} = h f = h / T = h / \sqrt{g \cdot a^3}$.

The above quantity of Energy consist the **Hydrogen minimum Energy-Rim** , which becomes

from equation $a = \sqrt[3]{T^2/g} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{[3,04513 \cdot 10^{-16}]^2}{9,80769251}} = 2,1145016 \cdot 10^{-16}$ m , is the Energy-cave

for Unit Energy quantity . From Newtonian Constant of Gravitation relation issues ,

$$G = E = h \cdot f_n = \left[\frac{c \cdot r^3}{a^3} \right] \cdot [g_L k_L] = g \cdot k_E = g \cdot [g_L k_L]$$

and since for the **First Chemical-Neutral-material-cave** , r , constants g_L, k_L are equal to unity *i.e.* $g_L = k_L = 1$, then above Energy of $E = 13,6$ eV , in Hydrogen-Plane-orbit corresponds to the **minimum-Energy-Cave** , or \rightarrow **The Phys-Quantized-Energy-Structure** . Since G Pushes $\rightarrow g$, on the Earth-Unit-coefficient , k_E , and because is the **Starting for the first time beginning** , of this **Mechanism** then from $G = g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv g \cdot [1 \cdot 1] \equiv \rightarrow g \leftarrow$ or $G = g$, meaning that In Earth System of Gravity , the Newton's Gravitational constant G , and Gravity g are equal , while in all other relative Systems are equal to the proportionality of their Local-constant k_L .

Now is Proved that , the **Gravitational Constant G is the mechanism or the mould** , for the **First-kick-Start** upon this **Unit-Granular-Energy-Stress-Layer** , g , to formulate in that orbit a , into Planck's cave the lightest and the less-energy mass Particle of this Universe , which is the **Hydrogen** with the minimum **Quantized-energy** of **13,6 eV** .

The Centripetal acceleration in Photon cave due to Pressure σ , where issues Rotational Energy $E_R = \bar{B} \cdot \bar{\omega} = 2L = J \cdot \omega^2$, and $2E = B f$, or $\rightarrow 2 \cdot (0,5 \cdot m \cdot c^2) = m \cdot c^2 = 0,5 \cdot \pi \cdot r^4 \cdot c^2 / 4$, and $4 \cdot \bar{B} \cdot f = c^2 \cdot r^4$ where the Golden ratio frequencies $\rightarrow f_n = \left[\frac{n \cdot \sigma \cdot \Phi}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot r} \right] \cdot \equiv \frac{n \cdot (1 + \sqrt{5}) \cdot \sigma}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot r} = c^2 \cdot r^4 / 4 \cdot \bar{B} = \frac{E}{h} \leftarrow$ *i.e.*

The box B_p , carried with Light velocity c and Pressed into the Planck's cave , as $n c^2 = n \cdot c \cdot c$ becomes the **Gravity g** , which is a stress by which Gravitational-force G is communicating as ,

$$g_G = s \cdot \left[\frac{\pi r v^4}{2} \right] \cdot e^3 = 9,808238 \text{ m/s} .$$

Gravity is the minimum Unit-Stress-monad in Planck's scale becoming from a M-Point and which is Under -Planck's - length region . Since also acceleration in a Material-Point (*Centrifugal-Centripetal*) becomes from the **Principal Stresses $\pm \sigma$** , therefore constant

$$g_G \cong \pm \sigma = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{g \cdot \text{Mass}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{G}{k} , \text{ and for Unit-G constant } k \text{ is ,}$$

$$k = \frac{\text{System Area}}{\text{System Mass}} \quad G \text{ where } \rightarrow \frac{1}{g} = \frac{k}{G} = \frac{\text{System Area}}{\text{System Mass}} \text{ and } G = k \cdot g_G , \text{ and for the Earth}$$

$$G \equiv g \cdot k_E \equiv g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv \left[\frac{T_p^2}{a^3} \right] \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv 9,808238 * 6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} \equiv 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{Ns}^2}$$

So G , is The Pulling and Cohesive Force on all the **Quantized-Energy-Structures** which communicates with everything due to **Periodic excitation** on all Spaces .

From equation $g = G / [g_L k_L]$, is seen that g becomes from G under Local-laws ,

And also , Gravity g , is the **Unit-Energy-Path** , *Quanta of Gravitation* , due to M-Point frequency $f_g \cong \pm \sigma$ from the Revolving motion , and also the **Unit-Energy-Stress** per Surface and for the Force - G , *is the Permitted Path* , or the communication Conductor on all Energy **Wave Structures** , In and Out Planck's length .

Remarks : Gravitational Force ,G, is the Pressure which every Object in the Universe

Exerts on every other , *whether small or big* and is equal to $F_{grav} = \frac{G.M.m}{d^2} = \frac{g.R^2_E M.m}{Md^2} =$

$\frac{g.R^2_E.m}{d^2} = \frac{mg.R^2_E}{d^2}$, and $G = \frac{g.R^2_E M.m.d^2}{Md^2} = \frac{g.[R^2_E]}{M} = g \cdot k_E$, where $k_E = \frac{[R^2_E]}{M}$, and

$g =$ The minimum Quantized work as acceleration $\equiv 9, 8076941 \text{ m/s}^2$

$k_E =$ The Earth Local-coefficient between the two constants g, G .

For Earth (E) $\rightarrow k_E = r^2_E / m_E$, For Bodies (B) $\rightarrow k_B = r^2_B / m_B$,

For any Body \rightarrow Local Gravity $g_L = k_E / k_L$

The Four *Energy-Space* constants in Nature are ,

$$L_P \equiv e^{-i.(\frac{\pi}{2}+2k\pi).b} \equiv e^{i.(-5\pi/2).10} \equiv e^{i.(-5\pi/2).10} \equiv \{ \sqrt{3}. \pi. 1,616199.10^{-35} \text{ m} \} \rightarrow$$

and is The Planck's length cave ,

$$g \equiv \frac{T^2}{a^3} \equiv \frac{1}{f^2_{n,a^3}} \equiv 9, 8076941 \rightarrow \text{The minimum Granular Quantized Energy ,}$$

from the gravity frequency f_g , representing the *Bedding-Quantum-Raw-material* of force G , on all Energy structures .

$$G \equiv g \cdot k_E \equiv g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv \left[\frac{T^2_P}{a^3} \right] \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv 9,8076941 * 6,8116.10^{-12} \equiv$$

6,68056.10⁻¹¹ m³/ N.s² *The Pulling and Cohesive Bond* , of all the Quantized-Energy-Structures in all Spaces .

$$f_n \equiv \{ [S \equiv B_P \equiv EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n] \equiv n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{n\sigma.B}{8r^2} \text{ and from cave}$$

$$\lambda_N = \frac{4\pi.r.c}{n\sigma.(1+\sqrt{5})} = \left[\frac{\pi^2.r^4.c}{n.B} \right] \} , \text{The Amount of Energy , the unit meter of motion ,}$$

in the Torsional and Resonance-Augmented-Golden-Ratio-Pattern Φ .

$$\bar{v} = \bar{c} = \sigma \cdot \Phi = \frac{F\Phi}{A} = \left[\frac{G\Phi}{A} \right] = \left[\frac{6,673692.10^{-11}.1,6180339887}{36.10^{-20}} \right] = 2.9985163. 10^8 \text{ m .}$$

6b-2.. THE ORIGATION OF GRAVITAIONAL Force – G . [81-82]

1.. Gravitational Force ,G, is the Pressure which every Object in the Universe exerts

on every other , *whether Small or Big* and from Newton equal to $\rightarrow F_{grav} = \frac{G.M.m}{d^2} =$

$$\frac{g.R^2_E M.m}{Md^2} = \frac{g.R^2_E.m}{d^2} = \frac{mg.R^2_E}{d^2} , \text{ and } G = \frac{g.R^2_E M.m.d^2}{Md^2} = \frac{g.[R^2_E]}{M} = g \cdot k_E \text{ where } k_E = \frac{g.[R^2_E]}{M} = \frac{g.M}{G}$$

$g =$ The minimum Quantized Work as change of velocity \rightarrow acceleration $\equiv 9, 8076941 \text{ m/s}^2$

$k_E =$ The Earth Local-coefficient between the two Constants , g, G , and $k_E.G = g.M$

For Earth (E) $\rightarrow k_E = r^2_E / m_E$, For Bodies (B) $\rightarrow k_B = r^2_B / m_B$,

For any Body \rightarrow Local Gravity $g_L = k_E / k_L$

2.. Coulomb Electrical Force , $F_{electron} = k_C \frac{Q_1.Q_2}{d^2} = \frac{[\oplus \rightarrow \ominus]}{d^2} = \frac{8}{\pi r(1+\sqrt{5})} \left[\frac{B}{r^2} \right]$, where

Coulomb constant $k_C = 9.10^9 \text{ Nm}^2/\text{C}^2$

3.. The Work done by the Electric field to Rotate the Dipole is $W = F_{electron} \cdot E_{Field} \cdot$

4.. The Work done in Material Point needs a Path to exit from the Box $f_R = [B_{PH}] \equiv [f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_R = w^2_N] = [E^2 + H^2]$, and from where is Propagated .

Resonance-Path happens as the Force , *EM-Radiation in Two directions* , which can travel in any closed *System* , and for solids through Cauchy-Stress-Tensor where the two Conveyers $E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3$, can carry the *Energy Storage* r in *System* [+ - 0] and Change the Inner-Structure of this System to another or Destroy it.

In [70] , the Work Produced In Material-Point \overline{AB} is equal to $\rightarrow W = 2L = \overline{B} \cdot \overline{w} = J \cdot w^2 \leftarrow$ consisting the First-Energy-Store which is a Stationary Wave with , n lobes as , $W_{n(n+1)} = \left[\frac{4\pi r^2 f_1}{3} \right] \cdot n \cdot (n+1)$ and wavelength $\lambda_N = \frac{\sigma \cdot (1+\sqrt{5})}{4\pi r} = \frac{n \cdot \overline{B}}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{2n \cdot \overline{c}}{w}$ of $r = \frac{m \cdot \overline{c}}{q \cdot B}$ related to M-Field B

In [75-B] ,The Permeable-Resonance-Path for M-Point is \rightarrow The Resonance-frequencies $f_R [S \equiv f_{1=n}, f_2, f_R = w^2]$ with $f_n = \left[n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{n\sigma \cdot \overline{B}}{8r^2} \right]$ related to Spin \overline{B} , Stress σ and cave r .

Since frequency in Material-Point is \rightarrow

$$f_n = \left(\frac{n\sigma}{8r^2} \right) \cdot \overline{B} \equiv \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right] \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \equiv \left[\frac{n\sigma}{8r^2} \right] \cdot \overline{B} \equiv \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right] \frac{\text{Stress}}{\text{Perimeter}} \equiv \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right] \frac{\text{Force [N]}}{\text{Area} \cdot L [\text{m}^3]} \equiv \frac{E}{h} , \text{ then it}$$

occupies the Property of the Golden-ratio Pattern Φ , and equation defines that the Material Point of frequency f_n , when collide with another Material Point , or with any other Particle or Particles then Produces another monad as $\rightarrow 1 \equiv$ A New **Quaternion** and the first continuous to be of the same Identity , **frequency** f_n , as before and from Euler's , *Rigid Body Dynamics work* $\rightarrow W = 2L = \overline{B} \cdot \overline{w} = J \cdot w^2 \equiv h \cdot f_n \leftarrow$ i.e.

The Frequency of Photon , is embodied with the \rightarrow **Growing-Golden-ratio-Pattern** Φ and It Uses the **Vibrating Physical Structures** , or the same the **Granular Material-Instruments** , to **Kick - Start all of them and everything in this world** . The How In [75-B] Page 34 .

Because of the Periodic excitation between , Space (+) and Anti-Space (-) , $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$

exists only Collision of Opposite , where the inner acceleration is equal to zero Gravity g

and this because of Material extreme-case of the Periodic acceleration $\{ \leftarrow \leftrightarrow \leftarrow \} = 0$, which

is zero and the Net force vanishes , and where issues The **Coulomb Dipole-law** where acceleration

g becomes from the Stationary constant Dipole moment $\overline{p} \equiv \overline{B} \equiv$ momentum and which is the

analogous in the Revolving motion in where then issues \rightarrow

$$G = g \cdot k = k_E g = g \cdot k_R \cdot g_R = \overline{p} \cdot g_c = \sigma = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{\text{Mass}}{\text{Area}}$$

In Page-33 , the Earth-constant $k_E = \frac{R_E^2}{M_E} = \frac{[6,378 \cdot 10^6]^2}{5,98 \cdot 10^{24}} = 6,811551810^{-12}$ and the Gravitational Force $G = g \cdot k_E = [9,8076941] \cdot 6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} = 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3/\text{N} \cdot \text{s}^2$ becoming from g , k_E only , i.e. G is a force which Pushes \rightarrow g as energy in $\rightarrow k_E$ Earth-constant .

From Gravity relation $G = g \cdot k_E = 9,8076941 \cdot 6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} = 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3/\text{N} \cdot \text{s}^2$ and

from Energy-loop relation $1 = c \cdot r^3 \cdot f_p^2 \rightarrow f_p = \sqrt{1/cr^3}$, and from $f = E/h$ then $f = \frac{E}{h} = \sqrt{1/cr^3}$

$$\text{or } \rightarrow E = h \cdot \sqrt{1/c \cdot r^3} , \text{ and } \frac{E^2}{h^2} = \frac{1}{cr^3} \rightarrow E^2 = \frac{h^2}{cr^3} , \text{ an Energy relation between } c , r .$$

This relation is used for **Black- Holes Energy** where r , result to zero , [71]

The Permissible - Permeable - Resonance - Paths is as for ,

- 1) **Solids** \rightarrow The Normal-mode-Vibration - System $\{ -w^2 [M] + [K] (X) \} = 0$]
- 2) **Liquids** \rightarrow The Cauchy Stress-Tensor as Momentum equation $\{ \nabla \cdot \sigma = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \tau \}$
- 3) **Gazes** \rightarrow The combined Avogadro's Pressure-law $\{ PV = n RT = n \cdot m v^2 / 3 \}$
- 4) **Crystals** \rightarrow The Cauchy Ellipsoid-Stress-tensor where $\{ E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3 \}$
- 5) **Molecules** \rightarrow The Lattice-Crystal-Arrangement with their Chemical Bonds relation
- 6) **Atoms** \rightarrow The Energy-Rims with Chemical Bonds , *Ionic* , *Covalent* , relation
- 7) **Particles** \rightarrow The Resultance of the One-Dimensional-Collision $\overline{v}_{ij} = \overline{v}_j - \overline{v}_i = \overline{w}_{ij} \cdot \overline{r}_{ij}$
- 8) **M-Points** \rightarrow The Resonance-frequencies $f_R [S \equiv f_{1=n}, f_2, f_3, f_R = w^2] = f_n = [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$

$$= n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{n\sigma B}{8r^2} \rightarrow \text{i.e. the Golden-ratio-Pattern, which is related to Spin.}$$

9) Cave-Orbit → The Relation $c.L_s = L_v$, Light-velocity $3.10^8 \text{ m/s} \cdot 1.10^{-42} \text{ m}$
 cave $= 3.10^{-34} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ are the Cave-Energy-Plane-Rims in Atom's, Planet orbits

In Vibrations of Systems, for Orbits issues $\rightarrow W = 4\pi^2 \cdot \frac{r^3}{T^2} \cdot \bar{n} = 4\pi^2 \cdot r^3 \cdot f^2_p \cdot \bar{n} \leftarrow$

which is the Energy in the Conic-Sections of Kepler's Unit - Orbits .

The Energy-Storages $r = n \cdot \left[\frac{\lambda}{2}\right] \equiv W_{n(n+1)} = \left[\frac{4\pi r^2 f_1}{3}\right] \cdot n \cdot (n+1)$, are travelling through Bodies and follow, **Lame Stress Ellipsoid** $n_1^2 + n_2^2 + n_3^2 = \frac{T_1^2}{\sigma_1^2} + \frac{T_2^2}{\sigma_2^2} + \frac{T_3^2}{\sigma_3^2} = 1$ on Principal Stresses $\pm\sigma_1, \pm\sigma_2, \pm\sigma_3$, which is the Passage through which Forces (The EM-Radiation) travel in any Solid either it is in Motion or is at Rest. **Laplace's Orbital Angular-momentum** $e^{i.2\pi n} = 1$ and for $n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots, \pm n$, consist the eigenvalues operator L_z which agree with prior Resonance-frequencies f_R [$S \equiv f_1 = N, f_2, f_3, f_R = w^2$] as wavelengths $\lambda \equiv [f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n = w^2] \equiv$ the n lobes, or $\rightarrow f_N = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{n\sigma B}{8r^2}$, as the Principal-Stresses σ , and Resonance-frequencies f_R relation, which is Energy stored in the MP-lobes.
 [70] **Type - Particles at sites - Type of Bounding-Force - Properties - EM-Radiation**

Ionic : \oplus, \ominus Ions - Electrostatic $\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus$ - non-conductors - Infrared

Molecular : Atoms or Molecules - Dipole Attraction - Repulsion - non-conductors - Chemical-Bonds .

Covalent : Atoms - Network- Bonds between Atoms -non-conductors - EM-Spectrum

Metallic : Atoms - Ions and Electrons Attraction - Conductors - E-conduction .

The **Kinetic-Energy** E_K of a moving Material-Point, as this is the Photon, is stored as motion in its Storage, $r = [n \cdot \lambda/2]$, with the n frequencies $f_n = n \cdot f_1$, with the n lobes, and with an fundamental frequency f_1 . From above is seen the **Passage and The-How EM-Radiation can travel in Crystals** and which are the Cauchy-stress-tensor where exists $E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3$, in-where Energy Propagates along Directions *without Birefringence*, and carries the Energy-Storage r , which radiation is **The Conveyer**.

Above procedure can be used in Cells, where cells are cases of an Birefringence material and the Resonance-Passage happens as the Force, *an EM-Radiation in Two directions, can travel in Cell* through Cauchy-stress-tensor where the two Conveyers $E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3$, and can carry the Energy-Storage, r , in Cell, and alter the Inner-Structure of Cell to another desirable Property.

From Inner-velocity equation $v = w r = (2\pi/T) \cdot r = 2\pi \cdot f_1 r$, wavelength $\lambda = cT = c/f_1$, cave $r = n \cdot [\lambda/2]$,

then $r = n \cdot (c/2f_1)$ and $v = 2\pi \cdot f_1 [n \cdot c/2f_1] = n \cdot \pi \cdot c$ or $v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c \dots (4)$ showing that velocities in lobes

are, $n \cdot \pi$, times that of light and for $n = 1$ then $v = \pi \cdot c$, more than three times faster of light velocity.

Because of the above velocity v , an **E field** is produced, which produces the $\partial D/\partial t$ field, which in turn produces the **H field** which produces the $\partial B/\partial t$ field and which again produces the **E field**,

i.e. the total **EM-field** regenerates itself as it rotates, and is a *Phenomenon happening in a Propagating Plane-wave*. Its Permeable - Resonance - Path is impossible in an three-times stronger EM-field .

The United-Coulomb-Newton Law for Interactions :

For a Stationary interaction the **Coulomb-Law-Force** is $F_C = \frac{k[q_1 q_2]}{r^2}$, and for Charges q_1, q_2 where Constant $k = 9,0 \cdot 10^9 \text{ N.m}^2/\text{C}^2$, and r , is the distance between the Charges .

For a Stationary interaction **Newton Law for masses** m_1, m_2 is $F_N = \frac{G[m_1 m_2]}{r^2}$, and for $\bar{v} = \bar{r}$

Conjugating Interaction , **Energy E** = $\frac{v^2}{2}[m_1 + m_2] = \frac{r^2}{2} [\frac{F_1}{g} + \frac{F_2}{g}] = \frac{F.r^2}{2} [\frac{1}{g} + \frac{1}{g}] = \frac{F.r^2}{2} [\frac{g+g}{g.g}]$
 $= \frac{F.r^2}{2} [\frac{2.g}{g^2}] = \frac{F_N.r^2}{g}$, where F_N is Newton Force , and **E** is the Energy of the Field-System.

Equating the **two forces** then $\frac{k[q_1q_2]}{r^2} = \frac{gE}{r^2}$, or $\rightarrow k [q_1, q_2] = g.E \dots\dots(1)$

Equation (1) relates any two Charges q_1, q_2 , with Field-Energy **E** , under vector $\vec{v} = \vec{r} = \vec{c}$

The Gravitational force G and Stresses σ : [77]

From A-7 In Planck`s cave , the **Least-Unit-Energy-cave** is that of **Hydrogen-Cave H** , and Issues $g . r^3 . f_p^2 = 1$, or $g = [\frac{1}{r^3.f_p^2}] = [\frac{T_p^2}{r^3}]$. The Earth constant $k_E = 6,8116.10^{-12}$, and

The Gravitational-Constant-Force G , becomes as **Stress** \equiv Force/Area $\equiv g$, as equation

$$G = g k_E = g . [g_E k_E] = [\frac{T_p^2}{a^3}] . [g_L k_L] = [\frac{c.r^3}{a^3}] . [g_L k_L] = 9,8076925 * 6,8116.10^{-12} \equiv 6,68056.10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$$
 , and **Effects on gravity** $\rightarrow g \equiv 9,8076925$ as **Stress** $\frac{Kg}{cm^2}$ [73]

The Beyond-Planck-length Force **F** = $\sigma . A$ = The Glue-Bond \equiv Stress x Area \equiv

$[\frac{2\pi f.r}{\Phi}] . A = w r . [\frac{A}{\Phi}] = \vec{v} [\frac{A}{\Phi}]$, and becomes a moving Storage $\frac{A}{\Phi}$ travelling with velocity **n** times that of light-velocity **c** , as equation $\vec{v} = n c$.

1.. For The Beyond-Planck-Length Force issues $\rightarrow F = \Phi^3 . [\oplus \sigma \ominus] = \sigma \times \Phi^3$ where ,

$\sigma \equiv [\oplus \sigma \ominus] \equiv$ **The Stress of Cave** as the **Quantized distance** $r \rightarrow [\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus]$

and $\Phi = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})}{2}$ is the mould of Quantization , *a kind of Impedance in Electricity* , and

in Material-Points frequency $f = \frac{c}{2\pi r} = 2,93949410^{42}$ H , and $\sigma = \frac{c}{\Phi}$.

2.. For the In Planck-Length- G-Force as Stress $\sigma = \frac{2\pi r f}{(n)\Phi} = \frac{2\pi r f}{1.\Phi} = \frac{2\pi . 1,616199.10^{-35} . 2,93949410^{42}}{1,6180339}$

$= 1,84456315.10^8$ t/m2 $= 1,84456315.10^{11}$ Kg/m2 , and the Angular velocity , w, from Total

Planck Cave is $|w| = \frac{\sigma}{2r} [1+\sqrt{5}] = (\frac{1,852816510^{11}}{2.1,616199.10^{-35}}) . 1,6180339 = 9.274599.10^{46}$, rad/sec and

3.. For the Outer-Planck-Length- G-Force as Stress $\sigma = \sigma_{pl} = 1,84456315 . 10^{-11}$ Kg/m2 ,

and , **G** = $\sigma \times \Phi^3 \equiv [1,84456315.10^{-11}] . [3,6180339887] = 6,673692.10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$, *Nevertheless*

For Earth-System mass $M_E = 5,9723.10^{24}$ Kg , and for the Area \rightarrow Radius 6378,137 Km

$= 6 , 378.10^6$ m , then Earth-constant $k_E = \frac{[6,378.10^6]^2}{5,9723.10^{24}} = 6,8115518.10^{-12}$ and Gravitational

Force **G** = $g.k_E \equiv g . [g_L k_L] = [\frac{T_p^2}{a^3}] . [g_L k_L] = 9,80769.6,8115518.10^{-12} \equiv 6,68056.10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$

Remarks :

a.. The Stresses become from a Force and a Surface as equation $\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$, and in the case of

Gravitational constant G and a cave , r , then $\rightarrow \sigma = \frac{G}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{G}{\pi(2r)^2} = \frac{G}{\pi s^2}$, or a vector $|\vec{s}|$.

Above relation means that Force **G** needs a Vector-Surface $\pi.s^2$ to be spread as Stress σ which is the case of Constant-light-velocity **c** as \Rightarrow , or $\uparrow\uparrow c_{E \perp M}$. [96]

b.. The case of a vector **s** , is the **Linear-Stress** while of an Plane is the **Surface-Stress** and consequently of a Volume is a **Space-Stress** , as this was referred before for **G** Force ,

i.e. $G \equiv \sigma . \Phi^3 \equiv \Phi^2 . [\{\sigma \Phi\}] \equiv 2\pi f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \vec{v} \equiv m a = \vec{c} = [\frac{2.B}{\pi r^3}]$ are all Energy-Vectors .

c.. Since Stresses follow equation $\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi}$, conclusively since all **Forces and Areas** are every-where and are related to their-cave **r** , through their frequency , **f** , therefore it is the mean of motion for **every-Information** .

SUMMARY OF PRIOR : [87]

1.. Gravitational-Constant-Force G , becomes as **Stress** \equiv Force/Area $\equiv g$, as equation

$$G = g k_E = g \cdot [g_L k_L] = \left[\frac{T^2 P}{a^3}\right] \cdot [g_L k_L] = \left[\frac{c r^3}{a^3}\right] \cdot [g_L k_L] = 9,808238 * 6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} \equiv$$

$$6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}, \text{ and Effects on gravity, } g \equiv 9,808238 \text{ Stress } \frac{Kg}{cm^2}$$

$$2.. \text{ Spin of Photon } 4S \equiv 4|\bar{B}| \equiv \pi \cdot r^3 \sigma \Phi \equiv B_P \equiv [EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2 \equiv n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} \equiv$$

$$\left[\frac{(\pi r^2)^2 f}{2}\right] = \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \Phi \equiv L = -a \cdot \sqrt{2E}. \text{ When enters in minimum-Energy cave } a = 2,1145016 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}$$

creates the **Hydrogen cave** = - 13,6 eV, and from the Unit-Orbit equation, $\ddot{x} + w^2 x = 0$, the Quantum relation $k = g [f^2 \cdot \pi^3] = 1$ and the Energy Orbits f_n .

$$\text{From Photon-charge -relation, } \bar{q}_{\text{Photon}} = \frac{G}{\sqrt{2} \cdot f} = \frac{G \cdot h}{\sqrt{2} \cdot E} = 2,763 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ Coulomb}.$$

$$3.. \text{ Gravity } g \cong \sigma = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{\text{Mass}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{G}{k}, \text{ while Gravity force } [\nabla i] \equiv F_G \equiv m_G g = g \cdot \nabla \left[\frac{\sigma}{c^2}\right]^2 \cdot r$$

$$= m_G \frac{v^2}{r} = J w^2 \cdot g_G = \left[\frac{\pi r^4}{2}\right] w^2 \cdot \frac{v^2}{r} = \frac{v^2}{r} \left[\frac{\pi r^4}{2}\right] \frac{v^2}{r^2} = \left[\frac{\pi r v^4}{2}\right] \text{ and from Spin-Momentum relation}$$

$$S = \bar{B} = \frac{E}{w} = \frac{E}{2\pi f} = \frac{Er}{\sigma \Phi} = \frac{rG}{\sigma \Phi}, \text{ then } \bar{B}^2 = \frac{J^2 \sigma^2}{r^2} \Phi^2, \text{ and } \rightarrow [\bar{B}]^2 = \left[\frac{\Phi \sigma}{r}\right]^2 \leftarrow \text{ while as}$$

$$\text{centripetal} \rightarrow \text{Gravity-force } F_G \equiv m_G g = g \cdot \nabla [\sigma c]. r = m_G \frac{c^2}{r} = J w^2 \cdot g_G = \frac{v^2}{r} \left[\frac{\pi r^4}{2}\right] \frac{v^2}{r^2} = \frac{\pi r v^4}{2} \text{ and}$$

$$\text{from } f^5 = \frac{\pi g}{[2\pi r]^3} \rightarrow f^2 = \frac{\pi g}{[2\pi r]^3} = \frac{\pi g}{[v = w r]^3} = \frac{\pi g}{[v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c]^3} = \frac{\pi g}{[n \cdot \pi \cdot c]^3} \text{ and defines the,}$$

Black-Hole-Gravity-equation related to the Inner Quantum-velocity v , and to its n lobes.

$$\text{Gravity-Acceleration is } g_G = s \left[\frac{\pi r v^4}{2}\right] = \left[\frac{3,1415926 \cdot ([\sqrt{5}+1] \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot 10^{-35}) \cdot (299793458)^4}{2}\right] \cdot e^3 =$$

$$6,044981 \cdot 10^{-35} \cdot 80,776078 \cdot 10^{32} \cdot 20,085536 = g_G = 9,8076925.$$

From the Primary equation of Electron $\rightarrow w^2_e \cdot m_e = \pi g = \text{constant} \equiv \text{Energy} \equiv$

[meter of area * meter of force] \equiv Electrons on Orbits, on Traces and also the Unit

Space \equiv Massive-United-Unit-Space $\equiv \rightarrow [+v \cdot s^2] \leftarrow$ The Nucleus jointed through the

Neutral Material-Points [(+) [\leftrightarrow] (-)] with the Strong-force $\rightarrow S_F = h \cdot f_n \equiv h \cdot \{[S \equiv B_P$

$$\equiv EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2] \equiv h \cdot n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} \equiv h \frac{n\sigma \bar{B}}{8 r^2} \dots \dots \dots (mg)$$

Equations (mg) are the Energy-Space-constituents in the Hydrogen-System.

$$\text{From relation } f_n = \frac{[(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma]}{4\pi r} \text{ and } \bar{B} = \frac{\pi r^2 \sigma}{8} [1+\sqrt{5}] \text{ then Force } f_n \text{ Orient Spin } \bar{S} \text{ to } \bar{B} \text{ as,}$$

$$\bar{g} = f_n \times \bar{B} = \sigma |f_n| \times |\bar{B}| \cdot \sin \theta = \frac{[(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma]}{4\pi r} \frac{\pi r^2 \sigma}{8} [1+\sqrt{5}] \cdot 1 = \frac{[\sigma^2 r^2 (1+\sqrt{5})^2]}{32} \equiv \frac{\sigma^2 r^2 \Phi^2}{8} \dots (g)$$

4.. The Unit-Hydrogen-frequency f_e , in Stress g , Originates Electron-mass m_e from

equation $4\pi f^2_e \cdot m_e = g$, and from G, Electron-Charge $\bar{q}_E = \frac{G}{c\sqrt{2}} = 1,58 \cdot 10^{-19} C$

5.. Strong-Force $S_F = \left| \frac{g}{r^2} \right| \bar{E} = \left| \frac{g}{r^2} \right| \frac{\pi}{g r^2} [g^2 r + 2 \cdot L^2 \cdot f^2] = \frac{\pi}{r^4} [g^2 r + 2 \cdot L^2 \cdot f^2]$ depend on \bar{E} ,

found in our Sun, for Proton-Bonding as frequency $f^5 = \frac{g}{(2\pi a)^3}$

6.. From Orbit-equation $g [f^2 \pi^3] = 1$, Electron-charge $\bar{q}_E = g [k_E / c\sqrt{2}]$, Nutation

Energy $E = g \left[\frac{M \cdot m^2}{2 S^2} \right] \cdot [2k + Mm] \equiv g \frac{k_o}{2 S^2}$, Nut-Frequency $f_N = f_R = g \left[\frac{s \cdot m_e \cdot}{2\pi \cdot J_3 w} \right]$ is Seen

7.. The Strong-close-Energy $E = \left\{ \frac{k}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2m r^2} \right\} = \frac{\pi}{g r^2} [g^2 r + 2L f^2]$ is for Force $S_F = \left| \frac{g}{r^2} \right| \bar{E}$ i.e.

The effect of Gravity, g , is on All Energy-structures and it is the Resonance frequency f_R of, ELECTRON Charge, \vec{e} , and of Spin \vec{S} . The Produced Work as frequency f_R is Conserved in the Caves. The difference between Potential-Energy of the Orbit and that of the Electron-Nutation in Electron-Precession-motion is the lowest Potential-Energy, Resonance-Energy as Resonance-Frequency f_R . [82]. $R-F \rightarrow f_R$, IS the Energy in [Bracket-Orbit-Hook] which Joints the Atoms.

8.. In [82] is presented the Circular Planetary-motion where the constant velocity from

Orbit-Geometry is equal to $v = v_p = wr$ and the Centripetal-acceleration $a_p = \frac{v^2}{r}$.

The Elliptical motion after collision, where the acceleration is increased, the velocity is equal

to $v^2_p = 4 \pi^2 a^3 \cdot f_p^2 \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right]$ and the Centripetal acceleration $a_p = - \frac{32 \cdot C^2 a^2}{r^5} = - \frac{32 \cdot \pi \cdot a^4 [1]}{T^2 r^4 [r^5]}$,

where for $r = a \rightarrow a_p = - \frac{32 \pi}{T^2 r^5}$, and $C = \frac{dS}{dt} = r^2 \cdot d\phi / 2 = \text{constant} = \text{The Area swept in equal}$

times of radius Orbit-Nucleus. For Circular, Elliptical, Parabola, Hyperbola motion after collision, where then acceleration is increased and the velocity is equal to $p = \text{parameter}$,

$v^2_p = 4\pi^2 \frac{a^3}{T^2} \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = 4\pi^2 a^3 f_p^2 \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] = k \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1}{a} \right]$ and Centripetal-acceleration

$a_p = \frac{d^2 r}{dt^2} - \frac{4c^2}{z^3}$, where $k = \frac{4C^2}{p} = \text{constant}$, $\frac{d^2 r}{dt^2} = \text{The Natural acceleration}$

Velocity equation in a Central-motion is $v^2 = 4C^2 \cdot \left[\frac{e^2 \sin^2 \varphi}{p} + \frac{1}{r^2} \right]$..(f-4) where constant

$C = \frac{\pi ab}{T} = \pi ab f_p = \frac{dS}{dt} = r^2 d\phi / 2 \equiv \text{The covered orbiting area per time second}$, and

derivative $\frac{d(1/r)}{d\varphi} = - \frac{e \sin \varphi}{p}$. From Planet-Nucleus ... (a-1), $r = \frac{p}{1+e \cos \varphi}$ and velocity is,

$v^2 = 4C^2 \cdot \left[\frac{e^2 \sin^2 \varphi}{p^2} + \frac{1+e^2 \cos^2 \varphi + 2e \cos \varphi}{p^2} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p^2} [e^2 + 1 + 2e \cos \varphi] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{e^2 + 1}{p} + \frac{2}{r} - \frac{2}{p} \right] =$

$$v^2 = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] \dots (f5), \text{ and for ellipse issuing } 2a = r_{\varphi=0} + r_{\varphi=a} = \frac{p}{1+e} + \frac{p}{1-e} = \frac{2p}{1-e^2}$$

therefore, Velocity from Geometry $\rightarrow v^2 = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1}{a} \right] \dots (f-6)$

From (f-6), when Planet is at Perihelion near the Focus then $\frac{1}{r} = \frac{1+e}{p}$, and velocity is

$$v^2 = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e}{r} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right], \text{ where } k = \frac{4C^2}{p} = \frac{4(\pi ab/T)^2}{b^2/a} = 4\pi^2 \frac{a^3}{T^2} \dots (f-7)$$

then Kepler constant, K, is as below and for $e = \sqrt{1 + 2EL^2/G^2M^2m^3}$, velocity

$$v^2 = 4\pi^2 \frac{a^3}{T^2} \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = [4\pi^2 \cdot a^3 f_p^2] \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = [4\pi^2 \cdot C] \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = K \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] \dots (f-7a)$$

From Mechanics Velocity $v = \dot{r} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} \left[E - V(r) - \frac{L^2}{2mr^2} \right]} \equiv \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} \left[E - \left\{ \frac{k}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2mr^2} \right\} \right]}$ and

$$v^2 = \frac{2}{m} \left[E - \left\{ \frac{k}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2mr^2} \right\} \right] = [4\pi^2 \cdot k] \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] \leftrightarrow E = \left\{ \frac{L^2}{2mr^2} + \frac{k}{r} [1+2\pi^2 mk(1+e)] \right\} \dots (f-8)$$

Remark-1 \rightarrow Hydrogen Atom with One Nucleus of Spin $\{+\frac{1}{2}\}$ and one Electron in Energy-Orbit of Spin $\{-\frac{1}{2}\}$, Is a Nucleus-Orbit-Magnet $\equiv \oplus$ Proton \leftrightarrow \ominus Electron which **ORIGINATES The-Constant-Resonance-frequency** f_R between them, becoming from the Eternal-changeable-motion of the Electron around the Nucleus and from the **Produced Variable – Magnetic - Orbital-Fields**.

Since the Total-Spin in Hydrogen is measured and at the Nucleus-Position then, Protons Absorb Energy from The-Electron-Spin which is moving in its different directions, and Store it as a Resonance-frequency f_R , IN ORBIT - RIM N-O.

This Orbit-Rim which is [The, m_N, m_e , Current-loop], continually increase its Energy and so produces a Signal in the Hydrogen-Atom, i.e.

Gravity g, acting On The Varying-Velocity \dot{x} of the Orbiting-Electron Creates Work which is Conserved as Electron-Magnetic-Field, magnetic moment, $\bar{\mu}$, in a time T, and as a Resonance-frequency f_R .

When velocity $\dot{x} = 0$ then $E = U(x)$, i.e. the Signal is the Increasing-Potential Energy in loop. The [m_N, m_e , Current-loop] consists the **Energy-Bond** between Atoms and is the **Communication-tool, The Resonance Signal**, in all Universe.

In case of **An-External-Magnetic - Field, Electron-Spin is swigging around the Magnetic-Vector** and this Motion, *the Nutation*, is transferred to the Nucleus.

The Produced-Work as Frequency $f_N = \frac{sQ}{2\pi J_3 w} \equiv f_R = 2,8398447 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

IN MRI, this is the Transverse-Precession, where B-Vector creates an RF - Signal from the Precessing Protons, and **Conserved Energy is the frequency $f_N = f_R$.**

Because of the Magnetic-field created On-Orbit and Applied at-Nucleus with

the same Effect then, exists LARMOR Equation as, $w_0 = \gamma \cdot \beta_0 / 2\pi$, and

for Hydrogen at 1,5 T Magnet, $\gamma = 2,675 \cdot 10^8 / \text{sT}$, $\beta_0 = 1,5 \text{ T}$, then an-frequency $w = 63,864 \text{ MHz} = 63,864 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Hz}$, the frequency $f_N = 2\pi \cdot w = 4,012575 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Remark - 2 \rightarrow On Figure -13 : [87]

BONDING, $f_N = \frac{sQ}{2\pi J_3 w}$, Happens in the Maximum-Potential cave

$E = -U(x)$, which is needed for any **Two Atoms to Joint** and create **molecules**. **Resonance Phenomena** in any Media (Mechanical , Electrical , Acoustic , Magnetic) is that , for Response is the maximum at a Specific-frequency f_R and **requires more Energy Input** including that frequency . Nucleus with Spin $S \neq 0$ can absorb and emit Electromagnetic Radiation and undergo , **Resonance**, when placed in a magnetic field. **This Uniform-Magnetic-field of Nucleus-Orbit [$p \leftrightarrow e$] already exists in Protons** which Eternally becomes from the Swinging of the **Electron-Angular-velocity-Cone** , with **Spin-Vector \bar{S}** in the axis of cone as **Angular-Momentum-Vector , the Polhode** , at a fixed Point of the **Central-Cone-circle** . Because of Gravity g , **SPIN ψ** is under **NUTATION $\hat{\theta}$** , and the **Response** is the **PRECESSION $\hat{\phi}$** , or **THE \rightarrow ELECTRON-NUTATION \leftarrow** due to Gravity is applied for a short time in the **Plane Perpendicular , \perp , to the variated Moment-Vector , $|\bar{R}| \equiv |\bar{M}_T| = |\bar{M}_N| + |\bar{M}_O|$** and the Work produced is **Conserved** in \rightarrow Nucleus - Orbit [$p \leftrightarrow e$] \equiv the Energy-Box. **The angular velocity-cone \bar{w} , is Rolling with Spin-Vector \bar{B} in the central cone.** The difference between the Potential-energy of the Orbit and that of the Electron-Nutation Precession with the lowest Potential energy , is the Resonance -Frequency \equiv The Energy . In figure 11, is shown the **Magnetic-Dipole-moment** of nucleus which is associated with the Orbital angular momentum , **$\bar{B} = \text{the Spin}$** . When an external **Static-Magnetic-field** is present then Spectral-lines Split into multiple closely-spaced-lines. As was calculated the **Strength of a Magnetic-field** of 1 Tesla is $\text{Static-M} = 1,174462 \cdot 10^{-4} = 11,74462 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ eV}$. In the Absence of Electron $|\bar{M}_T| \equiv |\bar{M}_N|$ the Spin , and exists The Nucleus-Magnetic-field \bar{B}_L .

6b3.. The Origination of Hydrogen cave H :

From Kepler third law Energy-Closed-Space equation and Newton`s Laws of motion

$$\text{Constant } k = v^2. r = (w r)^2. r = \left[\frac{2\pi}{T} r \right]^2. r = \frac{4\pi^2 r^2}{T^2}. r = \frac{4\pi^2 r^3}{T^2} = 4\pi^2 \frac{r^3}{T^2} = 4\pi^2. r^3. f^2_p \dots (k)$$

Because (k) is constant , $r^3. f^2_p$, is also a Constant multiplication of cave r , and the frequency f , and the , Work \equiv motion is conserved in cave ,r, as the , n , frequencies

$$f_N = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} = \frac{nB}{\pi^2 r^4} , \text{ and for a Damping-cave } \rightarrow r(t) = r(t+w) \leftarrow \text{ as Planck`s scale is}$$

with **min-Damping = 1** and **Unit-Energy-Quantity W_u** , (the critical-energy-unit in min , r) is this Unit-Stress-Gravity g , as $k = E = \frac{T^2}{a^3} = g = \frac{1}{f^2. a^3}$, i.e. \rightarrow

Stress g , when is entering into the minimum cave a , of a minimum Surface , then from the Period of Rotation T on the Perimeter, is created in Surface the minimum Quantity of Energy-cave and is the Hydrogen-Atom , where $gf^2 \equiv$ the **Energy-Part** embodied with stress g , and cave a^3 is the **Space-Part** , in 3-DOF Space as \rightarrow

$$T^2 = g a^3 = 9,808238. [2,1145016 \cdot 10^{-11}]^3 = 9,2728158 \cdot 10^{-32} \text{ s} , \text{ and Period}$$

$$T = 3,04513 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ s} , \text{ or frequency } f = 3,2839982 \cdot 10^{15} / \text{s} . \text{ From equation } E = h f =$$

$$6.62607 \cdot 10^{-34} \cdot 3,2839982 \cdot 10^{15} = 2,175999 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ J} / (1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19}) = 13,59999 \text{ eV}$$

Above Quantized Energy of 13,6 eV corresponds to Hydrogen-Atom-cave .

It was shown that *in Conservative Systems* of a Central-Force , the Total energy E

$$\text{is conserved and at Periapsis , energy } E = \frac{G.Mm}{2a} \text{ and } e = \sqrt{1 + 2EL^2/G^2M^2m^3}$$

and for $e = 0$ then $\rightarrow E = - \frac{G^2M^2m^3}{2L^2}$, i.e. energy is always Negative .

From Hydrogen cave issues $k = E = \frac{T^2}{a^3} = g = \left[\frac{4\pi^2}{GM} \right]$ therefore $GM = \frac{4\pi^2 a}{g}$ and

from Total-energy $E = -\frac{GMm}{2a}$, Rotational-Momentum $L = \sqrt{(1-e^2).GMm^2.a}$
 eccentricity $e = 0$, $G Mm = -2a.E$, and then $\rightarrow L^2 = GMm^2.a = -2aE[a] = -2a^2E$.

i.e. Equation $L^2 = -2a^2.E$, denotes that Angular -Momentum L ,

in Orbit - Rims is always Negative and equal to , $L = - a \sqrt{2. aE}$.

So, Hydrogen-Atom, is the **minimum-Energy-cave** In Planck's - Length, occupying the minimum **Negative-Energy** in Rims \equiv Caves, the Space, where Quantum-Energy-Rims are the Plane Traces-Conductors in where can roll the \ominus charged Electrons.

In Hydrogen-cave, the Resonance Frequency of an **Electron \ominus** , and a **Proton \oplus** , happens from the Stationary Unit-Cave of a System of Kepler second Planetary-law as equation, $4 \pi^2 m f_o^2 = k$, and from constant law of Areas $l = k . f_o^2 . a^3$. Their common Constant-Energy k , is $\rightarrow k = 4 \pi^2 m f_p^2 =$

$= \frac{1}{f_p^2 a^3}$ or, $f_p^4 = \frac{1}{4\pi^2 m a^3}$ and $f_p = \sqrt[4]{\frac{1}{4\pi^2 m a^3}}$. A loop in Planck's length $2a = L_p = \pi.1,616199.10^{-35} m$

and frequency $f = \frac{c}{\lambda}$, where then $f_p^4 = \frac{1}{4\pi^2 m a^3} = \left[\frac{c}{\lambda} \right]^4 = \left[\frac{1}{\lambda} \right]^4 . \{c^4 = \frac{1}{[4\pi a^3] m \pi a}\}$, or for Unit Intensity

$I = \frac{\text{Energy}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{E = hf}{A = 4\pi a^3} = \frac{1KW}{A} = \frac{1}{[4\pi a^3]} = \frac{1}{\lambda^4} \{mc^4 . \pi . a\} = \frac{1}{\lambda^4} \{1\} . 80,760865.10^{32} . (3,14) . 0,8080995.10^{-35}$
 $= 0,5865 . \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda^4} \right\}$, or Energy-Intension $\rightarrow I = 0,5865 . \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda^4} \right\}$ ← which is the Rayleigh Scattering, i.e.

The Quanta of Energy, Passing through a Unit-Surface or Volume, which becomes from the Kepler's Second and third law Mechanism, is **Inversely Proportional** to the **fourth Power** of the wavelength λ .

In Outer Electromagnetic fields, frequency, w , is that of inner motion $\rightarrow w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = 2\pi . f_N \equiv \left[\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right] \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma . \Phi}{r}$, which continuous to follow the **Growth-Golden-Ratio-Pattern**. Photon occupies such the Property of Material Point as the Growth-Pattern. With this way Photon's frequency $\rightarrow f_p = 1 / T_p$, Kicks-Start

everything found on its-way. From Resonance constant $k = \frac{1}{f_n^2 . a^3} \rightarrow$ or $l = k . f_n^2 . a^3$ ← and from

\rightarrow **Kepler's laws and Newton's Lagrange laws** ← for Orbits, then the cave-Semi-major-axis is

$$a = \sqrt[3]{T^2 / k} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{g . f^2}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{4 . \pi^2 . r^2}{g . \sigma^2 . \Phi^2}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{[4\pi^2] . x . r^2}{[g . \Phi^2] . x . \sigma^2}}, \text{ and } f_R = \frac{w_R}{2\pi} = \sqrt{\frac{k-1}{g . a^3}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{g . \Phi^2 . a^3}} \equiv \sqrt{\frac{k}{m d}} \text{ eV ... (a)}$$

i.e. It is the Resonance-frequency f_R , in **Photons loop**, and which is the Energy-Space Quanta, following the **Growth - Golden Ratio-Pattern**, when travels in all Cosmos.

1)... **It was shown** that when **two Photons** strike each other, $\vec{c} = \vec{c}$, or reflect on a wall, then $c = 0$ and then their fundamental frequency $f_1 = n . \left[\frac{v}{2r} \right] \times \left[\frac{1}{4} \right] = n . \left[\frac{v}{8.r} \right]$ which for $n = \left[\frac{8 . \pi r c}{v . \lambda} \right]$ increases to $\frac{\lambda}{c}$,

Therefore for $n = N . \left[\frac{8 . \pi r c}{v . \lambda} \right] = N . \left[\frac{c}{\lambda} \right]$, and for $N \rightarrow \infty$ then $f_1 = E / h = \infty \dots \dots (b)$

In Dual Photon $\bar{v} \left[\frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \bar{v} . \left[\left[\bar{f}_n \right] + f_n \right]$, **Colours** are **Still-Sub-Units** of Storage $\left[\bar{v} . \left[\bar{f}_n \right] \right]$, and exist as **Frequencies**, Violet, Blue, Green, which Stabilize with their Complementary colors Yellow, Orange, Red, of wavelength $d = \lambda \rightarrow \lambda_{\min} \approx \lambda_{\max} = 3.10^{-7} m \approx 3 . \sqrt{3} . 10^{-7} m$

2). **The Quanta of Energy**, Passing through a Unit-Surface or Volume is **Inversely Proportional** to the **fourth Power** of the wavelength λ as $I = 0,5865 . \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda^4} \right\}$. When $f_{BE} = E / h = \infty$ then the

Energy-Intension Increases and the **wavelength λ Decreases** and for $f_{BE} = \infty$ then $\lambda = 0$.

This is what happens in **Black-Holes** where $d = \lambda = 0$, and in where $E = f_{BE} = \infty$.

Hydrogen-Energy $E = h . f_p = [6,6262.10^{-34} J.s] . [3,28393.10^{15} / s] = 2,176.10^{-18} J$,
 and in eV $\rightarrow [2,176.10^{-18}] / [1,6.10^{-19}] = 13,6 \text{ eV}$,

Above quantity of energy consist the Hydrogen minimum Energy-Rim , becoming from equation $a = \sqrt[3]{T^2/g} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{[3,04513 \cdot 10^{-16}]^2}{9,80769411}} = 2,1145016 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}$, for unit energy quantity.

6b4.. : The Origination of Spin \bar{B} :

It is an Application to Material-Points $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$, by considering the Positive-constituent with angular velocity $\bar{w} = \bar{v} / r = \frac{\sigma}{2r} [1 + \sqrt{5}] \dots\dots\dots(1)$ [70] and for an angle 45° from , x , axis , where then the Ellipsoid of Angular-velocity is Perpendicular to the Plane of motion .

Moment of Inertia to , z , axis is that of sphere equal to $J_3 = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$ which is the same in all

Principal axes , and exists , $J = J_1 = J_2 = J_3 = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$, therefore Angular-kinetic-energy \equiv

Angular-velocity-Ellipsoid and then becomes , $J_1 w_1^2 + J_2 w_2^2 + J_3 w_3^2 = 2E \dots\dots\dots(2)$

The Energy-Ellipsoid as $\bar{B} \equiv \text{Spin}$ are , $w_1^2 + w_2^2 + w_3^2 = \frac{2E}{J^2} = \frac{32 E}{(\pi r^4)^2} = \frac{B^2}{J^2}$.

Angular-momentum \equiv Spin $\equiv \bar{B} \equiv [r \sigma (1+\sqrt{5})]$ (3) In Figure -14- and

for the center , K , of \oplus sphere , issues $\bar{v}_K = [\bar{w} \cdot \bar{r}_K] = [\frac{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})}{2r} 2r] = \sigma [1+\sqrt{5}]$ and $\bar{B} = \bar{S} = [\bar{r} \cdot m\bar{v}] = [r \cdot m \sigma (1+\sqrt{5})] / 2$ and for $m=1$ then $\bar{B} = [r \sigma (1+\sqrt{5}) / 2]$.The Interchangeable Ellipsoids of Angular velocity [70-P49] , and Momentum for the same Moment of Inertia is $J_1 = J_2 = J_3 = J$, and Angular Velocity $w_1 = w_2 = w_3 = w$, and Momentum $B_1 = B_2 = B_3 = B$

becomes $3J w^2 = C$ and $3B^2/J = C$ and since for circle $J = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$ then $\frac{3\pi r^4}{4} w^2 = C = (\frac{3\pi r^4}{4}) w^2 = (\frac{3\pi r^2}{4})(rw)^2 = (\frac{3\pi r^2}{4}) [\frac{\sigma}{2} (1 + \sqrt{5})]^2 = \frac{3\pi r^2 \cdot \sigma^2}{8} [3+\sqrt{5}] \rightarrow$ *The Ellipsoid of Angular-velocity, \bar{w} ,*

and $3B^2/J = \frac{3(rmv)^2}{J} = \frac{3(rv)^2}{J} = \frac{3r^2 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{2} [\frac{4}{\pi r^4}] = \frac{6 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{\pi r^2} \rightarrow$ *The Momentum-Ellipsoid , \bar{B} .*

From equation $3B^2/J = \frac{6 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{\pi r^2}$ and $J = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$ then $B^2 = \frac{\pi r^4}{3.2} \frac{6 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{\pi r^2} = 4 \cdot r^2 \sigma^2 \Phi^2$ and

The Angular-momentum In Planck`s-Length \equiv Spin $\equiv |\bar{B}| \equiv 2 \cdot r \sigma \Phi = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot r^2 \cdot f \dots$ (s)

The value of $|B| = [2 \cdot 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35} \cdot 1,16180339] = 2,845976 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ {Kg/m/s}}$.

For Planck-Length $r_p = 1,61623 \cdot 10^{-35} \sqrt{3}\pi = 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m}$, velocity $|\bar{v}| = \frac{\sigma}{r} [1 + \sqrt{5}]$

and from (s) then \rightarrow **Planck-cave-Stress $\sigma = \frac{\bar{B}}{4r \cdot \Phi} = 1$, Total-Energy $2E = |J w|^2$,**

From $|\bar{v}| = \frac{\sigma}{r} [1 + \sqrt{5}] = c = 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$ then , $\sigma = \frac{3 \cdot 10^8}{3,679551 \cdot 10^{34}} = 8,1477332 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ Kg/m}^2$

$|w| = \frac{\sigma}{2r} [1 + \sqrt{5}] = (\frac{8,1477332 \cdot 10^{-27}}{2 \cdot 8,794551 \cdot 10^{-35}}) \cdot 3,2360675 = 1,499 \cdot 10^8$, or $|w| = 1,5 \cdot 10^8 \text{ rad / sec}$,

For $\sigma = 8,147733 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ Kg/m}^2$ and $\bar{B} = 5,691952 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J}$ then , Period $T = \frac{2\pi}{w} = \frac{2\pi r}{v} =$

$\frac{4\pi r}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})} = \frac{4\pi \cdot 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35}}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})} = \frac{3,4151}{\sigma} 10^{-34} \text{ s}$, or **Period $T = [\frac{4,191584}{10^9}] \text{ s}$** , and frequency $f = \frac{1}{T}$

i.e. **Planck-frequency $f_1 = 2,38573294 \cdot 10^{34} \text{ Hz}$.** From above issues ,

a).. The Spin of cave , r , is Equal to the Angular-momentum-Vector \rightarrow **Spin $\equiv |\bar{B}| \equiv 2r \sigma \Phi$** which contains and is the Golden-Radio-frequency Φ as Pressure , $\pm \sigma$, in cave r .

b).. In Planck`s-length [for light velocity $c = 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$] , **velocity** is $|\bar{c}| = \frac{\sigma}{2} [1 + \sqrt{5}] \text{ m/s}$ and in cave $r_p = 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m}$, the **Pressure $\sigma = \frac{r \cdot c}{[1 + \sqrt{5}]} = 8,147733 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ Kg/m}^2$** .

c).. In Planck`s-length the Period of Oscillation is $T = \frac{4\pi r}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})} = 4,192 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ s}$, and

Frequency $f_p = \frac{1}{T} \equiv \frac{\sigma \cdot (1+\sqrt{5})}{4\pi r} = 2,3857265 \cdot 10^7 \text{ Hz}$, which is the minimum in Planck-cave .

The extreme for stresses is $\sigma_{1,2} = \sigma_1 / 2 \pm (\frac{1}{2}) \cdot \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + 4 \cdot \sigma_1^2} = \sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \sigma \Phi$,
 velocity $v = w \cdot r = \frac{2\pi}{T} = 2\pi r \cdot f = [\frac{\sigma}{2}] \cdot (1+\sqrt{5})$, frequency $f = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5}) \cdot \sigma}{4\pi r}$, Period $T = \frac{4\pi r}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})}$

d).. From Orbit vibration $f_n = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \Phi$, $f_n^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{4\pi^2 r^2} \Phi^2 = \frac{1}{g \cdot a^3}$ and $g a^3 \Phi^2 = \frac{4\pi^2 a^2}{\sigma^2}$, or

$a = \frac{1}{g} [\frac{2\pi}{\sigma \Phi}]^2$ and from Work $W = 2E = B w = J \cdot w^2$, or $2E = 2\pi f$ and $\bar{B} f = \frac{E}{\pi}$ and Energy

in Planck-scale-cave $2E = \bar{B} f_n = [\frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} = [\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} \Phi$, or $E = [\Phi \frac{\sigma}{4\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B}$ i.e.

Energy in Planck-cave-Particles is dependent on their Spin only, and for Electron $r = a_e$

$$E = [\Phi \frac{\sigma}{4\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} = 1,6180339 [(\frac{1}{4\pi \cdot 1,6840307 \cdot 10^{-17}}) \cdot 2,845976 \cdot 10^{-17} = \frac{21,76 \cdot 10^{-19}}{1,6 \cdot 10^{19}}] = 13,6 \text{ eV}$$

All above equations define \rightarrow **The Ubiquity of Golden-Ratio- Φ** \leftarrow in all motions

\rightarrow **The Angular-Momentum, Stresses, Frequency or Velocity** in nature . [64-A-B-C]

e).. Generally all Systems Possessing **mass**, *Reaction to any motion or changes*, and **Elasticity**, $dl > 0$, are capable of Free-Vibration or **Vibration** that take place in the absence of external excitation . On this Property is based the Programming of the Atoms and their Compounds as is [106]-Dokimes .

Remark – 3 For the Nucleus-Electron SPIN .

1).. The Spin of cave, r , is Equal to the Angular-momentum-Vector \rightarrow **Spin** $\equiv |\bar{B}| \equiv 2r \sigma \Phi$ which contains and is the Golden-Ratio-frequency Φ as Pressure, $\pm \sigma$, in cave r .

2).. From Orbit vibration $f_n = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \Phi$, $f_n^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{4\pi^2 r^2} \Phi^2 = \frac{1}{g \cdot a^3}$, from relation $g \cdot a^3 \cdot f_n^2 = 1$

and $g \cdot a^3 \cdot \Phi^2 = \frac{4\pi^2 a^2}{\sigma^2}$, or $a = \frac{1}{g} [\frac{2\pi}{\sigma \Phi}]^2$. Also from Work $W = 2E = B w = J \cdot w^2 = B \cdot 2\pi f$ then

$\bar{B} = \frac{E}{\pi \cdot f} = \pi \cdot r^2 \cdot \sigma \cdot \Phi / 2$, and Energy in Planck-scale-cave is $2E = \bar{B} f_n = [\frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} = [\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} \Phi$,

or $E = [\Phi \frac{\sigma}{2r}] \cdot \bar{B}$ i.e. Energy in Planck-cave-Particles is dependent on their Spin only, and for

Electron $r = a_e$, then $E = [\Phi \frac{\sigma}{4\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} = 1,6180339 [(\frac{1}{4\pi \cdot 1,6840307 \cdot 10^{-17}}) \cdot 2,845976 \cdot 10^{-17} = \frac{21,76 \cdot 10^{-19}}{1,6 \cdot 10^{19}}] = 13,6 \text{ eV}$, agreeing with Bohr's Atoms theory .

6b5.. The Origination of Electron - charge \bar{e} :

From relation $G \equiv g \cdot k_E \equiv g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv [\frac{T^2_P}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = g k$, is seen that Gravitational-Force G , is **The Spring-like central-force** from a fix point, *the Source*, on an attached, *probe*, mass as

$$\rightarrow F = -k r = -k r \cdot \bar{r}, \text{ as 1-DOF equation, } \ddot{r} + w^2 r = 0,$$

where $k =$ The Unit-Spring-Force \equiv [*meter* of area] [*meter* of force \equiv *stress*] $\equiv \pi g \equiv$

with a general solution $r = A \sin w_n t + B \cos w_n t$, where A, B are constants and evaluated from the initial velocity-conditions which become $r = [\dot{x}(0) / w_n] \cdot \sin w_n t + x(0) \cdot \cos w_n t$.

Above equation represents the **Natural-frequency of the Celestial-Structures**, and

for Planck's length the only one **Primary-Particle** occupying the less **frequency**

and **Negative-charge**, which is the **electron** equation and with the solution as ,

$$\frac{w_n}{2\pi} = f_e = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}, \text{ or } 4 \pi^2 f_e^2 \cdot m_e = k = \pi g \text{ and or } \rightarrow m_e = \frac{g}{4 \pi f_e^2}$$

From Planck's min-equation $f_e = E/h = [-13,6 \times 1,6 \cdot 10^{-19} = 2,176 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ Joule}] / [6,6262 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J.s}] = 3,283998 \cdot 10^{16} / \text{s}$, where in Hydrogen atom energy $E = hf = -13,6 \text{ eV}$
 Substituting all the *minimum-meters of Planck's scale* then, *Electron mass is*,

$$m_e = \frac{g}{4\pi f_e^2} = \frac{9,808238}{4\pi [3,283998 \cdot 10^{16}]^2} = -7,2373149 \cdot 10^{-30} \text{ kg} \dots\dots\dots (4b)$$

$$f_e = 3,283998 \cdot 10^{16} / \text{s}, \text{ and } L_e = 2,3762992 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ m} \dots\dots\dots (4c)$$

Relation $4\pi^2 f_e^2 \cdot m_e = k = \pi g$, denotes that Electric-field generated by an electron has both, a component oscillating at the Electron's - Compton - frequency f_e , **which is The Energy-Part**, and the Non-oscillating component, the Electric-field-lines as the Energy-Conductor, **The Space-Part**, which is **connecting Gravity with Electric-field**. **So, Electron**, is the minimum-Energy massive Particle in Hydrogen-cave $\{-13,6 \text{ eV}\}$, becoming from Material-Point In Planck's-length, *minimum-cave*, occupying the less Unit frequency in Planck's - Length, with Negative-charge $\{f_e = 3,283998 \cdot 10^{16} / \text{s}\}$. Because of the **Negative-Energy** in Hydrogen-cave, and the less-Negative Energy of Rims which consist the Plane-traces-Conductors or the Paths in-where electrons roll so Energy Rims consist the Energy-minimum-Paths in Hydrogen-cave-Potentials, as $E_n - E_{n-1} = [m_e \cdot v^2] \cdot [2n-1]$, where the electrons, **the Electric-Charges**, roll.

Electron Charge \bar{q} Becomes from Magnetic Field **M** which creates the Electric-Field **E**, which is acting on Charge **q**, and the acting Force per second creates Work which is conserved and coincide with the Planck's constant **h**. This is because $h \rightarrow J \text{ s} = N \text{ m s} = \text{Power}$, where from, *Energy = Power x Time*, issues the Beyond Planck's length **L_p**, & Voltage **V** as $\rightarrow \bar{q} \equiv \frac{K_E}{V_p=1} = \frac{m_e \cdot c^2}{2} = \frac{g \cdot c^2}{8\pi f_e^2 \cdot 1}$ and $\bar{V} \equiv V_p \equiv \frac{c \cdot \text{Charge}}{\text{Total-Energy} = h} = \frac{c \cdot \bar{q}}{h} \dots(1)$

Using the two Energy-equations for *Linear-motion* $\rightarrow f_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$ and *Orbital-motion*

$$a = \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{k \cdot f^2}}, \text{ for Unit-Energy-Space-frequency } k = g, a = \pi, \text{ then } \rightarrow g \cdot f^2 \cdot \pi^3 = 1 \dots(2)$$

$$\text{Frequency } f_n = \sqrt[2]{\frac{1}{g \cdot \pi^3}} = \sqrt[2]{\frac{1}{9,808238 \cdot \pi^3}} = 1,8133418 \cdot 10^{-3}, \text{ i.e. The Unit-Charge-Cave, } \bar{q}$$

into Hydrogen cave $[a = 1,82043047 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}] \cdot [1,813342 \cdot 10^{-3} / \text{s}] = 3,3010625 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ C}$
From equations Charge and Voltage is the *Self-Growing* Property of frequency f_n in Material-Point, therefore and for Hydrogen-cave is equal to $\rightarrow \bar{q} \cdot \Phi$,

Because Gravitational Force is equal to \rightarrow the Geometric-Resultant of light-velocity **c**, acting on **Electron-Unit-Charge \bar{q}** \leftarrow or, $G = c \sqrt{2} \bar{q}$, then Electron-Charge is,

$$\bar{q} = \frac{G}{c \sqrt{2}} = \frac{6,680561 \cdot 10^{-11}}{1,41429 [2,9979346 \cdot 10^8]} = 1,585 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C}, \text{ the known Coulomb's charge quantity,}$$

From g_L, k_L Universal constants then the Newton's Gravitational constant Force is, $G \equiv g \cdot k_E \equiv g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv [\frac{T^2 P}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv 9,808238 * 6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} \equiv 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{Ns}^2}$

The in depth Position of electrons allows to the Work Produced in Prior Phase-Areas as **Golden Ratio Pattern**, to be Stored in the Next. Energy = motion / T $\equiv (\frac{v}{2\pi r}) \cdot [\sigma + \sigma \Phi] = \bar{v} \cdot [\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r}] \equiv \bar{v} \cdot [\frac{\bar{f}_n}{2\pi r} + f_n] \equiv \text{Moving - Storage} \rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot \frac{\bar{f}_n}{2\pi r}] \leftarrow + \text{Moving-Frequency} \rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \leftarrow \equiv \text{Material-Point}$

i.e. The Energy produced in Photon-Cave is consisted of **Two-moving-Storages**, that travel as

Wave $[\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot \frac{\bar{f}_n}{2\pi r}] \rightarrow [\bar{v} = \bar{c} = \lambda \cdot \frac{f}{\Phi}] \rightarrow [S \equiv \text{EM-R} \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2]$ and, **as**

Particle $\rightarrow [f_1 = (E^2 + H^2) = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} = \frac{n\bar{B}}{\pi^2 r^4}] \rightarrow \{W \equiv \text{EM-R} \equiv [\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2] = 2 \cdot \lambda \cdot c \cdot \sin(2\phi)\}$ and,

The Duality of an Energy-Storage $S = \{ [\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus] + \text{Motion } M \} . [87-89]$

THE ORIGINATION OF ANTI - GRAVITY - STRESS - g :

Figure - 11- : The Stability of , \pm SPIN , as an Electromagnetic Wave with Two frequencies $0, c$.

a).. The light velocity c is constant . Since c is constant then is analyzed to , (c_x, c_y) in any two directions x, y where $x \perp y$ and y to be the gravity direction on where gravity is acting . In figure (8) are seen the 4-Point Positions , at where Velocity Phase changes and the Work done in each Phase of Photon's inner motion . The 4-Phases correspond to the Wavelength λ , as $\lambda / 4$, in distance with $90^\circ = \frac{\pi}{2}$ to be the change of Phase . This means that the Produced Work in the Prior Phase-Area is as the Golden - Ratio Pattern which is Stored in the Next and Perpendicular Phase-Area . Light velocity , c , changes Phase every 90° and the **created Work** $W = c_y \times$ [Semicircle 1-2-4] and is Symmetrically **Stored** from $0^\circ \rightarrow 90^\circ$ alternately $+, -, +, -$, in [Semicircle 1-2-4] , and in the [Semicircle 1-2-3] . Spin follows equation $\bar{B} = r m v = [\frac{\pi.r^2}{2}] . \bar{c} \times \bar{r}^3$ where $\pm [\frac{\pi.r^2}{2}]$ =The Semicircles

b).. The Dual Property of The **Simultaneously existing** Spin as Electric and as Magnetic Field in wavelengths , λ_x, λ_y , as **Effective Range** , is **thrusted** through the Light velocity c , and finally is from the Newton's Gravitational Force \bar{G} . In Planck's length $r_p = 1,616255 . 10^{-35}m$ the created Work of \bar{c} , from 1-3 Position is stored in the [1-3] Semi circle surface and at Phase-3 where $c = 0$ is then stored in the [2-4] Semi circle surface , At Phase-4 , where $\bar{c} = 0$ the motion is stored in the [1-3] Semi circle surface , i.e. is alternately repeated the $+\left[\frac{\pi.r^2}{2}\right] =$ The + Semicircle [1-3] , and the $-\left[\frac{\pi.r^2}{2}\right] =$ The - Semicircle [2-4] both in the same Plane-surface [1-3] , [2-4] of motion . Surface [1 - 3 - 2 - 4] is \perp on the SPIN Axis $\rightarrow U - D$. From

$f_n = \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \Phi$ and $\bar{c} = \bar{\omega}.r = 2\pi f_n . r = 2\pi r . f_n = \sigma \Phi$, is frequencies $0, c$, relation .
 At $c = 0$ exist **minima or maxima** , where change the two Energy-Semicircles .

c).. The origination of Spin and cave H

From Orbit vibration $f_n = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r}$ and from relation $g.a^3.f_n^2 = 1$, $f_n^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{4\pi^2 r^2}$, $\Phi^2 = \frac{1}{g.a^3}$
 then $g.a^3.\Phi^2 = \frac{4\pi^2 a^2}{\sigma^2}$, or 1). $a = \frac{1}{g} \left[\frac{2\pi}{\sigma\Phi} \right]^2$, and from Work $W = 2E = B w = J.w^2$, or $2E = 2\pi.f$
 and $\bar{B}f = \frac{E}{\pi}$ then 2). The Energy in Planck-scale-cave $2E = \bar{B}f_n = \left[\frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} \right].\bar{B} = \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \right].\bar{B}\Phi$, or
 $E = \left[\Phi \frac{\sigma}{4\pi r} \right].\bar{B}$ i.e. The Energy in Planck-cave-Particles is Dependent on their Spin only, and for
 Electron $r = a_e \rightarrow E = \left[\Phi \frac{\sigma}{4\pi r} \right].\bar{B} = 1,6180339 \left[\left(\frac{1}{4\pi \cdot 1,6840307 \cdot 10^{-17}} \right) \cdot 2,845976 \cdot 10^{-17} \right]$
 $= \frac{21,76 \cdot 10^{-19}}{1,6 \cdot 10^{19}} = 13,6 \text{ eV}$, which is the min-Voltage in Hydrogen cave .

d).. The Angular Momentum in cave $\bar{c} - r$,

In cave , r , The Energy-Vector \bar{r} is Positive for $\bar{O}4, \bar{O}1, \bar{O}3$, Directions while ,
 The Energy-Vector \bar{r} is Negative for $\bar{O}4, \bar{O}2, \bar{O}3$, Directions .

Since Total-Energy $L = B w = \frac{J.w}{2} w = \frac{J.w^2}{2}$ then $2L = J.w^2$, then Angular Momentum relation

$$\bar{B} = r.mv = r \left[\frac{\pi.r^4}{2} \right]. 2\pi f r = \pi^2.r^6.f. \text{ i.e.}$$

$$\text{Angular Momentum } \bar{B} = r m v = r \frac{\pi.r^4}{2} c = \left[\frac{\pi.r^5}{2} \right] c \left[\frac{\pi.r^2}{2} \right]. \bar{c} \times \bar{r}. \bar{r}. \bar{r} = \left[\frac{\pi.r^2}{2} \right]. \bar{c} \times \bar{r}^3 \dots\dots(a)$$

For $\bar{r} = \pm \bar{r}$, then $+\bar{B} = + \text{Gravity} - \text{Spin} = + \left[\frac{\pi.r^2}{2} \right]. \bar{c} \times \bar{r}^3$, The Gravity Force

$$-\bar{B} = - \text{Gravity} - \text{Spin} = - \left[\frac{\pi.r^2}{2} \right]. \bar{c} \times \bar{r}^3, \text{ The Antigravity Force}$$

From Momentum relation $\bar{B} = m r v = m r^2 w = m r^2 (2\pi f) = \frac{J.w}{2} = \left[\frac{\pi r^4}{2} \right]. [2\pi f]$ then Spin $S \equiv$

$$\underline{\text{Angular-Momentum}} \bar{B} \equiv \bar{S} = \frac{J.w}{2} = \frac{\pi r^4}{2} [2\pi f] = \pi^2.r^4.[f] = \frac{\pi.r^3.\Phi.\sigma}{2} \equiv \frac{[1+\sqrt{5}].\sigma.\pi.r^3}{4} = \frac{\pi r^3.\sigma.\Phi}{2} \dots(b)$$

For $\bar{r} = \pm \bar{r}$, then $+\bar{S} = + \text{Gravity} - \text{Spin} = + \frac{\pi.r^3.\sigma.\Phi}{2}$, The Gravity Spin

$$-\bar{S} = - \text{Gravity} - \text{Spin} = - \frac{\pi.r^3.\sigma.\Phi}{2}, \text{ The Antigravity Spin}$$

From Spin-Momentum relation $S = \bar{B} = \frac{E}{w} = \frac{E}{2\pi f} = \frac{Er}{\sigma\Phi} = \frac{rG}{\sigma\Phi}$, and $\bar{B}^2 = \frac{J^2\sigma^2}{r^2}\Phi^2$, so $\rightarrow [\bar{B}]^2 = \left[\frac{\Phi J\sigma}{r} \right]^2 \leftarrow$

while from Gravity-force $F_G \equiv m_G g = g.\nabla[\sigma c] . r = m_G \frac{c^2}{r} = Jw^2.g_G = \frac{v^2}{r} . \left[\frac{\pi r^4}{2} \right] \frac{v^2}{r^2} = \frac{\pi r v^4}{2}$, and

$$\text{Gravity-Acceleration is } \pm g_G = s.\left[\frac{\pi r v^4}{2} \right] = \left[\frac{3,1415926([\sqrt{5}+1].^4.\sqrt{2}.10^{-35}).(2,99793458.10^8)^4}{2} \right].e^3 =$$

$$= 6,044981.10^{-35}.80,773378.10^{32}.20,085536 = g_G = \pm 9,8076925 .$$

i.e. Gravity + $g_G = + 9,8076925 = \frac{\partial r\bar{c}}{\partial t} = + \bar{S}$, and Antigravity = - $g_G = - 9,8076925 = \frac{\partial r\bar{c}}{\partial t} = - \bar{S}$,

are the Two Opposite Forces as Spin , for the Stability of the Spin - \bar{S} , Equilibrium .

For $c = 0$ exist minima or maxima and thus SPIN is equal to the Negative Gradient of the Potential Energy in the two Interchange Energy Semicircles .

The Stability of Equilibrium :

In the Conservative System , of cave $\bar{c} - r$, the Total Energy E_T remains constant and Total-Energy

$$E_T = E_K + E_U = \frac{1}{2} [\dot{x}]^2 + U(x) = \text{constant} \dots(1) \text{ where , } E_K = \text{Kinetic Energy , } E_U = \text{Potential Energy}$$

By solving for $y = \dot{x}$ then , $y = \dot{x} = \pm \sqrt{2.[E - U(x)]} \dots(2)$

The differential equation of motion in cave $\bar{c} - r$, for Conservative Systems is $\ddot{x} = f(x)$ and because

$$\ddot{x} = \dot{x} \left(\frac{d\dot{x}}{dx} \right) \text{ then } \dot{x}.d\dot{x} = f(x)dx = 0 \dots (3) \text{ By Integrating then } \frac{\dot{x}^2}{2} - \int_0^x f(x)dx = E, \text{ and by}$$

comparison to Priors then $U(x) = - \int_0^x f(x)dx$ or $f(x) = - \frac{dU}{dx} = \ddot{x}$ (4)

i.e. For the Conservative System , of cave $\bar{c} - r$, the force $= \bar{B} = r m \bar{c} = \frac{I.w^2}{2} = [\frac{\pi.r^2}{2}] . \bar{c}^2$,

is Equal to the **Negative Gradient** of the **Potential Energy**.

For $y = \dot{x}$ then (3) becomes $\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{f(x)}{y} = \Phi(x, y)$, and the Singular Points correspond to $f(x) = 0$,

and $y = \dot{x} = 0$ and hence are the Equilibrium Points . For every Point x, y in the Phase-Plane for which $\Phi(x, y)$ is not indeterminate exists a unique slope of the trajectory .

When the velocity vector is at Points 1,2 then $y = 0$ and $f(x, y) = C \neq 0$ then the Slope of the trajectory is infinite and angle $\phi = 90^\circ$. Since **motion** in cave $\bar{c} - r$, is a single-DOF oscillator then equation is

$\ddot{x} + w^2 x = 0$. Equation indicates that at the Equilibrium Singular Points 3, 4, the Slope of the Potential Energy curve $U(x)$ must be zero , meaning **minima or maxima** which is the Interchange of the two

Energy-Semicircles . (c_x, c_y) , $\bar{c}_y = \bar{c}$,

Conclusions :

1... From equation $\bar{B} = r m \bar{c} = \frac{I.w^2}{2} = \frac{1}{2} [\dot{x}]^2 + U(x) = \frac{1}{2} [y]^2 + \frac{1}{2} k x^2 = \text{constant}$, then

Spin S $\equiv \bar{B} = \frac{1}{2} [y]^2 + \frac{1}{2} k x^2 = [y]^2 + w^2 x^2 = C = \text{Constant}$, or $\rightarrow y^2 + w^2 x^2 = C \leftarrow \dots(a)$

Equation (a) is a series of Ellipses determined by C , and in the case of $y/w = y$ then reduce to circles in , $\bar{c} - r$ Plane and Perpendicular to S as , $[\bar{c} - r] \perp \bar{S}$.

2... In the Conservative System of cave $\bar{c} - r$, where $\bar{c} = \text{Light-Velocity} = 2.9985163 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$.

$r = \text{Planck's Length} = \sqrt[4]{2} \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m}$, motion in cave is an single-DOF oscillator of equation

$\ddot{x} + w^2 x = 0$. Equation of motion is a circle on where exist 2-Singular Points 3, 4, meaning

minima or maxima , where issues $\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{f(x)}{y} = \Phi(x, y)$, and are in Mode-Shapes the **Points**

of Equilibrium . At Singular Points 3, 4, Velocity $\bar{c}_y = \bar{c} = 0$ and Spin $\bar{S} = \text{Gravity} = 0$,

and since $\frac{dy}{dx} < 0$, then Spin \bar{S} changes Direction becoming $-\bar{S} = \text{Antigravity} = 0$.

3...At Point 1 , Velocity $\bar{c}_y = + \bar{c}$ because of \bar{c}_y , + **direction** , and corresponds the Spin

$\bar{S} = \text{Gravity} = \bar{B} = r m \bar{c}$ which is Constant and equal to Work $= \bar{c}_y \times [\text{Semicircle 1-2-3}]$

At Point 2 , Velocity $\bar{c}_y = - \bar{c}$ because of \bar{c}_y , - **direction** , and corresponds the Spin

$\bar{S} = \text{Gravity} = \bar{B} = r m \bar{c}$ which is Constant and equal to Work $= \bar{c}_y \times [\text{Semicircle 1-2-4}]$, where

$[\text{Semicircle 1-2-3}] = + \bar{B} = \text{The Gravity}$, and $[\text{Semicircle 1-2-4}] = - \bar{B} = \text{The Antigravity}$.

6b6.. The Gravitational Redshift and Time Dilation : [42]

Gravitational redshift is the Phenomenon where low frequencies of light [long $T=620-750 \text{ nm}$] shifted to **red** (redshift $\rightarrow f = 400 - 484 \text{ THz}$) and higher frequencies of light [short $T=450-495 \text{ nm}$] are shifted to **blue** (blue-shifted $\rightarrow f = 606 - 668 \text{ THz}$) and Time Dilation the opposite Phenomenon for time .

Removal of λ creates , $+ \sigma 1$, and since velocity , c , is constant , long and short Period T , or low and high , f , varies and a vector with Low energy $E = h.f$ at Red , (**Redshift**) \rightarrow low $f = 400-484 \text{ THz}$,

long $\lambda = 620-750 \text{ nm}$ (**Blueshift**) \rightarrow high $f = 606-668 \text{ THz}$, short $\lambda = 450-495 \text{ nm}$ and High energy since $E = h.f$ at Blue . In this way Light is **s = Particle as Photon** , $s = \lambda = 380-780 \text{ nm} = (3,8-7,8) \cdot 10^7 \text{ m}$

and as **Wave** , the Stationary Electromagnetic fields $\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{P} = \nabla \mathbf{i} \times \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{i} = \text{is of an Wave nature force}$

where $\nabla \mathbf{i} = \bar{v} = \lambda f = \lambda / T$, since Light also = quaternion $\rightarrow [q = s + \nabla \mathbf{i}]$ and $1 \text{ nm} = 10^{-9} \text{ m}$.

The Energy \equiv motion of 1-eV is $1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ J}$, while for mass $= eV / c^2 = 1,782602 \cdot 10^{-37} \text{ Kg}$,

and for $f_n = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} = \sqrt{\frac{k = \pi 1 eV = \pi 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ J}}{m = 1,782602 \cdot 10^{-37} \text{ Kg}}} = \sqrt{\frac{2,8236586 \times 10^{18}}{1}} = 1,6803745 \cdot 10^9 \text{ H}$.

6b7.. The Hydrogen Bracket-Hook :

Figure-12.. The \pm Energy in Hydrogen and Atoms , with $H + H = H_1^1 + H_1^1 = H_1^{1-1} H_1^{1-1} = H_1^0 + H_0^1 = H_2$ and with Water $H_2O = O_1 H_2 = O_2^2 H_2^2 = T_4^4 = O_2^{2-2} H_2^{2-2} = O_2^0 H_0^2 = ES \frac{2=T/2}{2=T/2}$, which Still .

6b8.. The Precession and Nutation of Electron :

Gravitational constant , G , is The Pulling and the Cohesive Force on all the Quantized Energy Structures which communicates with everything due to the *Periodic excitation* on all Spaces. [84] The Newton's laws issues for the masses and also the same to Electrons in caves as below ,

$$G \equiv g \cdot k_E \equiv g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv \left[\frac{T^2 P}{a^3} \right] \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv 9,8078925 * 6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} \equiv 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$$

The Electron being in Hydrogen-cave **Precesses because of the different axis of Rotation and Nutation's** , from the continuous and immense-communication to the gravity , g .

Electron-Spin is the Angular-momentum-vector \vec{B} and rotates according to equation $\frac{dB}{dt} = [\vec{u}\vec{B}] = u \cdot B \cdot [\vec{k}\vec{k}']$ in Gravitational Potential $U_g = [mg] \cdot s \cdot \cos \theta = -s \cdot Q \cdot [\vec{k}\vec{k}']$, so the change of angular momentum \vec{B} is $\rightarrow \frac{dB}{dt} = u = \frac{s \cdot Q}{B} = \frac{s \cdot Q}{J_3 \cdot \omega_3}$ and from the 1-degree equation of motion u , becomes

$$\ddot{u} + \omega^2 u = 0$$

with solution the **Period of Nutation** $T = \frac{2\pi}{u} = \frac{2\pi \cdot J_3 \omega}{sQ}$, and its natural **Frequency** $f_N = \frac{sQ}{2\pi \cdot J_3 \omega}$ (1) with Total Energy of Nutation $E_N = \frac{1}{2} [w_1^2 + w_2^2] + \frac{1}{2} w_3^2$ (2) [70].

For Material-Points , the chains of Spins due to Periodic excitation $[\leftrightarrow]$ is created in **Orbit a Magnetic field** due to LRC-circuit and which is tuning to the critical Quantum critical-State g_G .

The Light velocity vector $\vec{v} = \vec{c}$, by Acting on cave , $r = L_P$, finds the **Impedance** m_g , and becomes the **Centrifugal-Force** F_g of Cave equal to **Gravity** g . The chains of Spins for the , ONE-WAY Pointy vibrating , is the Resonance - Frequency $f_R = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5}) \cdot \sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma \cdot \Phi}{2\pi r}$ of vectors \vec{v} and \vec{B} , of the-Stationary-Photon-cave , where $\vec{B} \equiv \vec{S} \equiv$ Spin , i.e. f_R is common to both .

The Moving Electron in Orbit of charge $\vec{q} \equiv \ominus$, energy E with the **Orbit-Velocity - Vector**

$\bar{v} = \sqrt{\frac{Z}{m} [E - (\frac{k}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2mr^2})]}$ which creates IN Orbit , r , the Varying and Perpendicular Magnetic-Field \bar{B} , which in time-turn Creates an Electric-field $\bar{E} \perp \bar{B}$, with the Resultant force **F** acting on Electron Velocity \bar{v} and which is composed of the V_p , Perpendicular to the Magnetic-circles $O \perp B$, and V_v , Parallel to the Magnetic-field-Vector $|\bar{B}|$, is tending in such way that $L \equiv S \equiv \text{Spin}$. The resulting motion of Electron in trajectory is the *Helical motion* and the **Work Produced** during this motion .

Conservation of Energy exist in Orbit , between Protons and Electrons [p↔ e] therefore , Energy as frequency occupies the *Orbit only* , and *differing that of those of Energy - levels* .

Since frequency $f_N = f_R = 2, 8398447.10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and exists in all Atoms , *due to the Hydrogen first cave* , then this f_N is the **Resonance - frequency** f_R between all **Atoms and Molecules** .

It is later proved that → Since $f_R = \frac{\sigma \phi}{2\pi r}$ and related to Hydrogen cave r and **Stress** σ only ←

it is the unique Common and Neutral-Monad , in all Chemistry structures and Composites .

Energy from equation $E = h.f_N = 6,62607.10^{-34} . 2,8398447.10^{10} = 18,817009.10^{-24} \text{ J} / (1,6. 10^{-19})$

$= 1,174463 . 10^{-4} \text{ eV}$, and conserved as **Thermal-Energy** E_T in kilo Cal and is continually

increasing as , $E_T = 18,817009. 10^{-24} \text{ J} / [(4,19. 10^3) = \text{kcal}] = 4,49093. 10^{-27} \text{ kcal}$. Since

$1\text{eV} = 96,363636 \text{ kJ/mol}$ then thermal energy $E_T = 4,49093. 10^{-27} \text{ kcal} / [96,363636.\text{kcal/mol} = 1\text{eV}]$

$E_T = 4,660399.10^{-29} \text{ eV}$. This happens because of the closed Energy - Orbit-Rims r , the constant

light velocity c , and from **Spin** equation $S = r m c$.

Taking into consideration the Thermal - Energy of a Photon when it is pressing the surface of

1 m^2 for 60s then , $E_p = 20 \text{ kcal} = 20. (4,19. 10^3) = 8,3777.10^4 \text{ J}$, and the ratio , $[E_T / E_p] =$

$4,49093 . 10^{-27} / 20 = 2,24546 . 10^{-28}$, which is a Quantity **Not - detected** . The Hydrogen caves

created in the Sun **1 Million years-ago** $= 10^6.365.24.3600 = 3,1536.10^{13} \text{ sec}$, is accumulated a

Thermal-Energy of a magnitude $E_{\text{Therm}} = 3,1536.10^{13}.4,49093.10^{-27} = 1,41626.10^{-13} \text{ kcal}$, i.e.

The Stationary Hydrogen-wave-cave needs 1-Quadrillion years to conserve 1-kcal Thermal-Energy .

For Half-frequency $f_R / 2 = 1,4199223.10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the Kinetic Energy is Zero and the Potential-Energy

is $U = E = h f = 6,62606957.10^{-34} . 1,4199223.10^{10} = 9,4085039.10^{-24} \text{ J} / (1,6022.10^{-19} \text{ eV}) =$

$5,8722405.10^{-6} \text{ eV}$, which agree with the Bohr-Magneton .

Fig. – 13 – .. The Effect of Gravity , g , on Electron-mass Originates Electron -Nutation

θ , in **Electron - Precession** , ϕ , and changes **Electron – Spin - Direction** , ψ .

The **Produced - Energy** is stored in Nucleus Magnetic-field $\bar{B}_p = 2\pi.m_p.f_r / \bar{q}_p$

The Atoms Precession , frequencies and Colors relation :

After some operations results the equation of motion under above restrictions as , [90] .

$$J_1 \cdot \mathbf{u}^2 \cdot \cos \theta - J_3 \cdot \omega_3 \cdot \mathbf{u} + s Q = 0 \dots (1) \text{ where } \mathbf{u} = \frac{d\phi}{dt} = \frac{d\mathbf{B}}{dt}, \text{ with solution}$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{J_3 \cdot \omega_3}{2J_1 \cdot \cos \theta} \pm \sqrt{\left[\frac{J_3 \cdot \omega_3}{2J_1 \cdot \cos \theta} \right]^2 - \frac{sQ}{J_1 \cdot \cos \theta}} \dots (2) \text{ Displacement , } \mathbf{u}, \text{ and is called}$$

→ **The Regular Precession of The Rigid - Body** ←

The under root terms are > 0 when $\frac{sQ}{J_1 \cdot \cos \theta}$ is very small or when Angular velocity $\omega \cong \omega_3$ where then , angular velocity axis is very closed to the Principal Ellipsoid axis . The change of Angular -momentum is $d\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{M} \cdot dt = [\bar{s}_0 \cdot Q] dt = s Q \cdot [\bar{k} \bar{k}'] dt \dots (3)$ where Kinetic energy during a displacement $2s$, is not changing , while Angular-velocity vector $\bar{\omega}$, is placed around \bar{B} , for which Moment of Inertia Ellipsoid executes a circular Polhode . The moving Inertia is rolling on the Steady Cone , driving in Precession the Electron-Spin-axis . Since vectors , \bar{B} , $\bar{\omega}$, are very closed each other and both to symmetric axis \bar{k} , **then the Polhode** are the narrow closed loop-curves on Poisson-Plane around \bar{B} vector. The Angular-momentum-vector \bar{B} rotates according to equation $\frac{d\mathbf{B}}{dt} = [\bar{u} \bar{B}] = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B} \cdot [\bar{k} \bar{k}']$

in Gravitational Potential $U_g = [mg] \cdot s \cdot \cos \theta = - s Q \cdot [\bar{k} \bar{k}']$, so the change of \bar{B} is $\rightarrow \frac{d\mathbf{B}}{dt} = \mathbf{u} = \frac{sQ}{\mathbf{B}} = \frac{sQ}{\frac{2\pi}{u}} = \frac{sQ}{2\pi \cdot J_3 \cdot w}$ and from the 1- degree equation of motion , $\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \omega^2 \mathbf{u} = 0$, then **Period of Nutation** $T = \frac{2\pi}{u} = \frac{2\pi \cdot J_3 \cdot w}{sQ}$, and **Frequency** $f_N = \frac{s \cdot Q}{2\pi \cdot J_3 \cdot w} \dots (4)$ with **Nutation-Total Energy** $E_N = \frac{1}{2} [w_1^2 + w_2^2] + \frac{1}{2} w_3^2$, or in Euler angles $E_N = \frac{1}{2} [\dot{\theta}^2 + \dot{\phi}^2 \sin^2 \theta] + \frac{1}{2} [\dot{\psi} + \dot{\phi} \cos \theta]^2 \dots (5)$

An Example : For Electron radius $s = r_e = 5,82 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ m}$,
 Weight of Electron $Q = m_e g = 9,11 \cdot 10^{-31} \cdot 9,808 = 8,93 \cdot 10^{-30} \text{ Kg}$,
 Moment of Inertia-Disk $J_e = J_3 = [\pi a^4/2] = \pi/2 [5,8 \cdot 10^{-16}]^4 = 1,777591 \cdot 10^{-61} \text{ m}^4$,
 Angular velocity $w_e = \frac{v}{r_N} = \frac{c}{1836} = \frac{3 \cdot 10^8}{1836} = 1,633 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m/s}$ because of masses analogy

The-Electron-Nutation-frequency $f_N = \frac{sQ}{2\pi \cdot J_3 \cdot w} = \frac{5,82 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot 8,93 \cdot 10^{-30}}{2\pi \cdot 1,777591 \cdot 10^{-61} \cdot 1,633 \cdot 10^5} =$
 $f_N = f_R = 2,8398447 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1} \dots (6)$

From equation (5) is seen , The **moving Electron** [\ominus charge] creates a Magnetic-field which **Changes** from Total-Kinetic-energy $E = T_K + L$, where $L = S = \text{Spin}$.

Remarks :

- 1.. Since the frequency created from Electron-Nutation is on the Basic , *the fundamental frequency* , **first Energy Level** with the minimum energy in Orbit of Atoms , therefore allows the **Resonance frequency** between all the **Atoms and Molecules** , for their Bonding or and other Operations .
- 2.. Since Electron is continually-oscillating with the Nutation-frequency f_N , so Produces continuous oscillating Magnetic-field -M- which in turn is the source of an oscillating Electric-field -E- which implies the **Regeneration of each other** , i.e. it is a **Propagating Electromagnetic-Wave** where $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{c}$. In an constant Lag of Time then , This is a **Way of Information** as stress , σ , and as a **Storage in Nature** , and this may be used in medicine and elsewhere . P_1
- 3.. Since Resonance-frequency is IN the first Orbit of Atoms , therefore allows Electromagnetic-Wave **to get out the Atoms-cave** with a quantum-Energy $E = h f_N$ or $E = 2\mu \cdot B$, which may be controlled
- 4.. Since Electron is rotating in Orbits so Electromagnetic Wave is also rotating , therefore is needed a **Proper-Stationary-Magnet** on which Rotation becomes Oscillation in order to succeed a clear 3-dimensioned Φ^3 , Magnetic-Resonance-Imaging [The MRI] and the other Systems using this Property of Bottom-Information . This Property of Spin in all depths of Energy - caves allows the Granularity of Energy in Energy- loops , and after to be Bonded . This Property of Electron may be used for **Cancer Chromosomes** .
- 5.. The Photoelasticity Fringe - Pattern is as **Strain-Fringe , Deflection and Stress -Fringe** .

This Electromagnetic-Wave $[\bar{c} \cdot \bar{f}_n] + \bar{c} \cdot \bar{f}_n$ in the Principal-Stresses $\{ \bar{c} \cdot \bar{f}_n \} = \text{Strain-Fringe}$
 $\bar{c} \cdot \bar{f}_n = \text{Stress-Fringe}$ \rightarrow is Scanning the Normal-Image-Fringe-Tracks and the Damaged or
 Diseased- Image- Fringe-Tracks , both through the , **Strain-Stress-Fringe - Pattern** .
 The Normal and Diseased Image-Fringe Stresses and Strains are Complementary-Spectral colors ,
i.e. The Yellow color is Opposite to Violet , Blue color Opposite to Red and Green to Orange .
 Motion Stabilizes by Change, **from** $\text{TX}_{36\bar{M}}^{36\bar{E}} \rightarrow$ **Halve** $\text{U}_{18\bar{M}}^{18\bar{E}} \rightarrow$ and Equilibrium . Uracil consisted of
 four Atoms H , C ,N ,O , Vibrating in a multi-DOF System , and because of Inertia Stabilize to 4-
 Eigenvalues defining the Positions and converges to the Eigenvectors corresponding to the largest
 eigenvalue and which is the smallest natural frequency w_1 .

6... In Hydrogen-Atom's case , *The transferred-Energy in Current-loop* N-O , is that of the Electron
 motion with light velocity in the circular-Magnetic-field-lines which are Perpendicular to the Orbit .
 This Magnetic-field is related to , m , q , f , units .The Direction x-x , of the two Couples of Oscillation
 is that of the two masses as are , $m_N, m_O \equiv e$ of *Current-loop* , which is continually altered because
 of the Polhode curve .Since the Total Angular Momentum $M_T = M_N + M_O$ where $M_T = L = S = I \times w$
 and is Swinging on the Precession-circle and w -Nib on Polhode curve , therefore the Resultant M_T ,
Resonates with the Quantum frequency f_R of the cave to form with $\pm q$ Charges the Magnetic Field
 \bar{B}_R . At Nutation - Period , M_O is Swinging and angle ϑ , Decreases or Increases , so the Diagonal
 Resultant M_T Increases or Decreases and Energy is transferred in $[m_N, m_O \text{ Current-Potential-loop}$
 $U(x)] \equiv \text{The-Proton-Vector-Bracket}$] since $K_E = 0$.The Bound-States of the Hydrogen have Negative
 Energies because Proton and Electron can never become infinitely-distance . Kinetic-Energy K_E , is
 supplied in the form of a Rotating-Nucleus-Magnetic field IN ORBIT-RIM N-O , which is applied
 for a short time in Plane \perp to the variated \bar{R} vector and which is rotating very near to the Resonance
 Precession frequency of the Nucleus Protons . $[m_N, m_O \equiv e \text{ Current-loop Increases its } P_E \equiv U(x)]$.
 This ORBIT-RIM is \rightarrow **The Nucleus -Orbit Vector - Bracket** \leftarrow Oriented in Spin axis . The Energy
 Nucleus-Orbit-Vector-Bracket , of The-One-Proton-Atom issues and for the multi Proton and the
 Electrons in Orbits and the variated vector \bar{R} as in Fig-27 .

7... The Hydrogen Atom with One Nucleus of Spin $\{+\frac{1}{2}\}$ and one Electron in Energy-Orbit of Spin
 $\{-\frac{1}{2}\}$, is a **Nucleus-Orbit-Magnet** $\equiv \oplus \text{Proton} \leftrightarrow \ominus \text{Electron}$ which **ORIGINATES The Constant**
Resonance-frequency f_R between them , becoming from the **Eternal-changeable-motion** of the
 Electron around the Nucleus and from the **Produced Variable Magnetic** Orbital-Fields .
 Since the Total-Spin in Hydrogen is measured and at the Nucleus-Position then **Protons Absorb**
Energy from **The-Electron-Spin** which is moving in its different directions , and **Store it** as an
Resonance-frequency f_R , **IN ORBIT-RIM N-O** . This Orbit-Rim which is the , m_N, m_e Current
 loop , continually increases its Energy and so Produces a Signal , f_R , in The Hydrogen-Atom , **i.e.**
 Gravity g , acting On The Varying - Velocity - \dot{x} - of the Orbiting-Electron , e^- , Originates ,
the Nutation of Electron , \sim , which Work is Conserved as the Electron-Magnetic- Field \bar{B}
 and magnetic moment , $\bar{\mu}$, in a time T , and as a Resonance-frequency f_R .

When velocity $\dot{x} = 0$ then $E = U(x)$, i.e. the Signal is the Increasing-Potential Energy in N-e loop .
 The $[m_N, m_e, \text{Current-loop}]$ consists the Energy-Bond between Atoms and is the Communication
 tool , **The Resonance Signal** , in all Universe . Energy equation is $\rightarrow E_{\text{loop}} = E_{\text{dipole}} + \bar{\mu} \cdot [\nabla \times \bar{P}] \equiv$
 $E_{\text{dipole}} + \bar{B} \cdot [\nabla \times \bar{P}] \dots (e)$. In this case , An- External-Magnetic-Field P , makes the Electron-Spin to
 swing around the Magnetic-Vector and this Motion , **Is the Nutation** , and transferred to the Nucleus.
The Produced - Work is The-Frequency as , $f_N = \frac{sQ}{2\pi \cdot J_3 w} \equiv f_R = 2,8398447 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$,

IN MRI , this is the Transverse-Precession , where B-Vector creates an RF Signal from the Precessing
 Protons , and Conserved Energy is the frequency $f_N = f_R$. Because the Magnetic-field is created on
 Orbit and Applied at-Nucleus with the same Effect **then** exists LARMOR Equation as , $w_0 = \gamma \cdot \beta_0 /$
 2π , and for Hydrogen at 1,5 T Magnet , $\gamma = 2,675 \cdot 10^8 / \text{sT}$, $\beta_0 = 1,5 \text{ T}$, then an w -frequency is as
 $w = 63,864 \text{ MHz} = 63,864 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Hz}$, and frequency $f_N = 2\pi \cdot w = 4,012575 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

8... The Accumulation of Energy as (e) creates the [The-Proton-Electron-Vector-Bracket] which is

the BONDING - FREQUENCY, $f_N = \left[\frac{s Q}{2\pi J_3 w} \right]$, and Happens in the Maximum Potential cave $E = -U(x)$, and which is needed for any Two Atoms to Joint and create the molecules. The Resonance Phenomena in any Media (Mechanical, Electrical, Acoustic Magnetic) is that, for Response to be the maximum at a Specific-frequency f_R and requires more Energy Input including that of frequency. Nucleus with Spin $S \neq 0$ which can absorb and emit Electromagnetic Radiation and undergo, **Resonance**, when placed in an magnetic field. This Uniform-Magnetic-field of Nucleus-Orbit [p ↔ e] already exists in Protons which Eternally becomes from the Swinging of the Electron-Angular-velocity Cone, with Spin-Vector \vec{S} in the axis of cone as Angular-Momentum -Vector, **The Polhode**, at a fixed Point of the Central- Cone -circle. Because of Gravity, g , SPIN $\vec{\psi}$, is under NUTATION $\vec{\theta}$, and the Response is the PRECESSION $\vec{\phi}$, or is THE → ELECTRON-NUTATION ← due to Gravity and applied for a short time in the Plane Perpendicular, \perp , to the variated Moment-Vector, $|\vec{R}| \equiv |M_T| = |M_N| + |M_O|$ and the Work produced is Conserved in → Nucleus-Orbit [p ↔ e] ≡ The [Energy-Box]. The Angular-velocity-cone, \vec{w} , is Rolling with Spin-Vector \vec{B} , in the central cone. The Difference between the Potential-energy of the Orbit and that of the Electron-Nutation Precession with the lowest Potential energy, is the **Resonance -Frequency** ≡ **The Energy**. In figure 36, is shown the Magnetic Dipole-moment of nucleus which is associated with the Orbital Angular Momentum $|\vec{B}|$, **The Spin**, resulting to the $|\vec{R}| \equiv |M_T| = |M_N| + |M_O|$. When an **External Static-Magnetic-field is Present** then, → **The Spectral-lines Split into** Multiple-closely-Spaced-lines, because of the **Released-Energy** in the Magnetic-Field, due to the Dual-Photon as, $\bar{\nu} \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \bar{\nu} \cdot \left[\left[\bar{f}_n \right] + f_n \right]$ ← and applied in Photosynthesis-Process to Convert light Energy-vector to Chemical Energy, through Stress σ , → The Above **Zeeman-effect In Astrophysics** is the Trapping of Magnetic field, $\bar{B}_C \equiv \left[\frac{2\pi \cdot m \cdot r}{q_T} \right] \cdot f$, where frequencies are variated from The Suns Under the Polarized Electromagnetic Outer - Radiation, → **In Lasers** is the **cooled-velocity-trapping** which is related to the Frequencies **In Electric-Dipole Spin**, and thus is the controlling of the Magnetic moment $\vec{\mu} = \vec{B}$, by flipping the orientation of the Magnetic - Moment. As has been calculated, for the Strength of an Magnetic-field of 1-Tesla, the Static-Moment = $1,174462 \cdot 10^{-4} = 11,74462 \cdot 10^{-5}$ eV. In the Absence of Electron, $|M_T| \equiv |M_N| \equiv$ The Spin exists only as Nucleus-Magnetic-Field \vec{B}_N . The Kinetic Rotational-Energy in a monad, is the Scalar Quantity, $L = E$, while the Vectors of, **Angular-Momentum** $\vec{B} \equiv \vec{S}$, and that of **Angular-Velocity** \vec{w} , which are related in monads as $\vec{B} \cdot \vec{w} = 2L = J \cdot w^2$. Analysis in [90].

6b9.. The Priors and Cosmology : [74-87]

a.. Article [87] is the completion of [72-80] and [80-86] of the Physical interpretation of the Two constants of nature, that of Newton's Gravitational constant G , and that of light velocity \bar{c} , with Derivatives the Photon - Charge \bar{q}_{photon} in Material Point cave r , Gravity Constant g , and the Planck constant L_p , with a Rigorous Geometrical and Mechanical logic. It was shown [33-39] that from < *The Balancing of Space, Anti-Space in a Rotating Sub-Space Common circle* >, Un-clashed Fragments through center, O , consist the Medium - Field Material Fragment → $[\pm s^2] = [\text{MFMF}] \equiv$ **The Chaos**, as base for all motions, and Gravity as force $[\nabla_i]$, while the clashed with the constant velocity, \bar{c} , consist the Dark matter $[\pm \bar{c} \cdot s^2]$ and the Dark Energy $[\bar{c} \cdot \nabla_i]$, **Declaring that** → Antimatter-Galaxies and Antimatter-Asteroids can exist only as Dark-matter or and Dark-Energy and **NOT** as Antimatter light, $(-c)$, alone, or from → velocity - Breakages, $[\pm s^2 = \pm (wr)^2]$ and $[\nabla_i = 2(wr)^2]$, where then become → the **Waves** { *On distance* $ds = |AA_E|$ **Wave is**, *The Work embedded in monads and it is what is vibrated*, in the **three either two either one dimensions, separately or together** } → and the **Material - Points**, the Photons the Elementary-Particles with their Vibrating equations of motion. **Vibration is the motion in Wavelength λ , either is Stationary or Transported, Propagated, as Electromagnetic - Radiation**. For Photon-Material-Point exists the **Duality of an Energy-Storage** as,

$$\text{Space} \equiv \left[\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus \right] \text{ and the Motion } M \equiv \left[\bar{\nu} - \text{Vector} \right] \text{ as in [87].}$$

From vibrations in Primary - Material-Points become, [55]

$$A \rightarrow \text{The Particles, with Inherent Vibration occupying distance } r = ds = |AA_E|,$$

- B → The Gravity-Field-Energy without Vibration , the only Stationary-Rotating Photon-Spinning-Material-Points .
 - C → The Dark-matter-Energy constituents as below ,
 - A.. [$\pm \bar{v}.s^2$] → The Fermions , *Quarks and Leptons* , and
→ [$\pm \bar{v}.\nabla i$] → Bosons ,
 - B.. [$\pm s^2$] → The [MFMF] *Neutral Field* ≡ *The Equilibrium Energy - Chaos* , with the *Negative-Energy* binder Field [∇i] .
→ The Gravity force G_f
 - C.. [$\pm \bar{c}.s^2$] → Dark-matter , and the binder Gravity-force [∇i] , [$\bar{c}.\nabla i$] → The Expanding Dark Energy , *Positive-Energy* , which both are moving with light velocity , c , causing the Universe to grow . *From above in , A , and , C , case → Energy as velocity* , \bar{v} , and , \bar{c} , exists in the , **Quantized** , *Discrete monads* , $\pm \bar{v}.s^2$ and $\pm \bar{c}.s^2$.
- B. case is the Transportation of Energy , from Chaos to the Stationary Material Points .**
Dark Energy $DE \equiv [\bar{c}.\nabla i]$ (©) → Acting , *is Positive - Energy* , on the Five Constituents as
→ { [∇i] , $(+s^2)$, $(-s^2)$, $(+cs^2)$, $(-cs^2)$ } and Produces ,
[$\pm s^2$] → MFMF Field [$\pm \bar{c}.s^2$] → DM-DE Field of , Dark matter and Anti-matter
[$\pm \bar{v}.s^2$] → Fermions [∇i] → $G_f \equiv$ Gravity - Force in DM-DE Stationary Field ,
[$\bar{v}.\nabla i$] → Bosons , Forces and [$\bar{c}.\nabla i$] ≡ DE → Dark Energy $c \times$ (©) [∇i]
→ Gravity Force $DE \equiv [\bar{c}.\nabla i] = \bar{c} [\nabla i] =$ The Travelling-Energy-cave , c ,
with the velocity-vector. , $n \bar{c}$,

In all above issue the Kepler's - laws , denoting that **Macrocosm and Microcosm Obey Newton's Laws of motion in all Scales** , as this was in Prior Proofed . [56]
All above laws exist in STPL line - Circuit and in the Arrangement-Mechanism of the three elements of nature in [STPL] - Physical Mechanism.

D.. : THE CONDUCTORS, VECTORS & PARTICLES .

Id... The Stability of Elementary Particles , Conductors and the Atoms -Nucleus :

Figure - 14- : The Stability of → { ⊕ - Space [A B C] } , { ⊖ - Anti-Space [K_A K_B K_C] } , and of Sub-Space { [⊕ ↔ ⊖] ≡ ds ≡ [⊕ ← ds → ⊖] - or -The Neutral-Space [A_E , B_E , C_E] :

a...The Space Anti-Space and , Neutral-Space Conductors : [60]

The Equations of motion become everywhere from any Opposite , Space ≡ ⊕ , and Anti-space ≡ ⊖ . During these motions as , ds , is done a Constant-Work , k , or and from their velocities \bar{v} . In Figure Conductor $D = d = AK_A$ where ⊕ constituent attacks ⊖ by a *Hook's law force as Stress* $\sigma = E u$, and an *Coulomb force* $F_{(+ \leftrightarrow -)} = \frac{[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]}{r^2} = \frac{[2 \sigma]}{r^2}$, creating Work ≡ motion as was shown

It was shown that , **The Stability of Forces** , is succeeded in *The Pascal's* - launched caves r while Leptons , from their *Anti - Leptons* existence in the same launched Pascal's-caves r . [58]

Equilibrium of the Three-Spaces is succeeded on the three Cyclic-Quadrilaterals $\rightarrow (AB_EA_EC_E), (BC_EB_EA_E), (CA_EC_EB_E)$ of 6 Conductors each $[a, b, c, d, p, q] \times [3-ABC] = 18$ Conductors .

Linearly is through *the Products* of the Diagonal - connectors *as* , $\rightarrow \rightarrow \rightarrow [AA_E].[B_EC_E] = [AC_E].[A_EB_E] + [AB_E].[A_EC_E]$, $[BB_E].[C_EA_E] = [BA_E].[B_EC_E] + [BC_E].[B_EA_E]$, $[CC_E].[A_EB_E] = [CA_E].[B_EC_E] + [CB_E].[C_EA_E]$ and , **Rotationally** through *the Ratio* of Diagonals \equiv The Conductors | $\frac{AK_B}{AK_C} \times \frac{BK_C}{BK_A} \times \frac{CK_A}{CK_B} = 1$ or \pm **Rotational-Equilibrium** $[AK_B].[CK_A].[BK_C] = [AK_C].[BK_A].[CK_B]$,of all

above Opposites \rightarrow **Tangential-Electromotive-Forces** \leftarrow From Mechanics ,*all Systems Possessing Elasticity \equiv motion and Reaction to motion* , called mass , *are capable of free vibration or vibration taking place in the Absence of External Excitation* . [7] From **Lorentz-Force** , $F = \bar{q} \bar{v} \times \bar{B}_F$, where , $\bar{q} \equiv$ Charge , $\bar{v} \equiv$ The velocity of Charge , $\bar{B}_F \equiv$ The Strength of Magnetic field then Centrifugal Force , $F_{CF} = m \cdot \omega^2 \cdot r$,and from Cave-Spin , $\bar{S} = r \ m \ v$ then mass $m = (\frac{S}{r \cdot v})$.Equating equations then , $F = F_{CF} \equiv \bar{q} \bar{v} \times \bar{B}_F$, and force $Q_{\pm} = m \cdot \omega^2 \cdot r = (\frac{S}{r \cdot v}) \cdot \omega^2 \cdot r = \frac{S \cdot \omega^2}{v} = \frac{S \cdot v^2}{r^2 \cdot v} \equiv |\frac{v \cdot S}{r^2}| \dots$ (EMF) where is $r_{min} = \sqrt[2]{\pi b^{-n}}$, [95] , [96BB] .

Electromotive-Forces , $F = \bar{q} \bar{v} \times \bar{B}_F = Q_{\pm} = \frac{v \cdot S}{r^2} \equiv |\frac{c \cdot S}{r^2}|$, **are The Elementary-Particles** {F, L, Q} .

From Electromotive-Force in min-cave $r = 1,7724538 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. exists Electron-Force-Charge \bar{q}_e as

$Q_{\pm} = |\frac{c \cdot S}{r^2}| = \frac{[2,998 \cdot 10^9] \cdot [1,0546 \cdot 10^{-34}]}{(1,7724538 \cdot 10^{-3})^2} = 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19}$ eV , which is the **Electron-Force-Charge** and

from the Gravitational-Stress-Charge $\bar{q}_{Electron} = \frac{G}{c \sqrt{2}} = \frac{6,6736923 \cdot 10^{-11}}{1,41429 \cdot 2,9979346 \cdot 10^8} = 1,575 \cdot 10^{-19}$ C .

Electromotive-Force in the min-cave $e^{-15,572707} = r = 1,7252787 \cdot 10^{-7}$ m , is the Gravitational-Force G

$Q_{\pm} = |\frac{c \cdot S}{r^2}| = \frac{[2,998 \cdot 10^9] \cdot [6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34}]}{(1,7252787 \cdot 10^{-7})^2} = 6,673692 \cdot 10^{-11}$, which is the G - Physical-Force-Charge.

Conclusions :

- 1.. **The Stability of Nucleus Forces** $\rightarrow \{ \oplus - \text{Space} [A B C] \} \leftarrow$ is succeeded by the $\rightarrow \{ \ominus - \text{Anti-Space} [K_A K_B K_C] \}$, of the Inner equilibrium **on the Three-Perspective triangles** & happening Through the Ceba's theorem **Inverse-Products** as. Fig-14-2 .
- 2...**The Stability of Nucleus Forces** for $\rightarrow \{ \oplus - \text{Space} [A B C] \} \& \{ \ominus - \text{Anti-Space} [K_A K_B K_C] \}$ is succeeded by *The Pascal's* -launched caves r , through the **STPL Circuit** of the **Ptolemy's and Ceba's Geometry theorem** for **Vector-Forces** . Fig-14-1.
- 3...In Fig-16. **Is shown The Stability of Electron Forces** , The Hydrogen , Carbon , Oxygen , Atoms- Conductors Sustains **In** the First 4-Dimentional Spinning

\rightarrow [The Inscribed-Tetrahedron-Sphere] , Tetrahedron-Cube, {Circumscribed-Cube Sphere} \leftarrow
 3-1... O-1-3-5-7 - \rightarrow The First Solid Tetrahedron Structure in Nature , *Holding Nucleus* ,
 3-2... O-1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8 \rightarrow The First Cube with max. Positions $e = 2 \cdot n^2 = 8$, *Electrons-Position*
 3-3... R - [O , A , B , C] \rightarrow NUCLEUS IS IN the First Inscribed Sphere of Tetrahedron.
 3-4... R-O-1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 \rightarrow ORBITS ARE IN Enveloped Cube-Sphere of Tetrahedron.

i.e. Deka hexahedron , Octahedron = Cubes , Tetrahedron \equiv 4-Points , Triangle \equiv 3-Points , Vector \equiv 2-Points \equiv The Closed-Conductor , 1-Point \equiv The Opened -Conductor \equiv It is The Bracket-Hook . The Hydrogen **Nucleus** is kept in the Inscribed to the **Tetrahedron-Cube-System** where exist the Protons and Neutrons , while The Electrons of Hydrogen **Orbits** are kept into the Circumscribed, to the **Tetrahedron-Cube-System** . Both Equilibrium by following the Menelaus-Ceba's Principles. A wide analysis in [99]

- 4... **The Communication of the System** [Inner-Sphere , Tetrahedron , Cube , Outer-Sphere] , is

succeeded by the , **Ptolemy's and Ceba's Vector-Forces** , in their **Closed-Conductors** , Above 4-Parts Vibrating System Drives each one another at a specific **maximum frequency** in the Opened Conductors known as the **Resonance Frequencies** . Small **Periodic Driving-Forces** Produce large Amplitude Oscillations due to their **Storage-Vibrating-Energy** . Due to the large damping resonance frequency it differs the **natural frequency** which is a frequency of the **Unforced - Vibrations** . With **this way the System is able to Store and Transfer Energy between KE and PE Storage-modes.**

b...An Example of Space , Anti-Space in Conductors-Forces .

- 1... $\oplus A \Rightarrow \ominus K_A \equiv \overline{AK_A} \equiv q^+ = - \gg P_A$, creating $[P_{+A1}] \rightarrow$ Strong-Chromodynamics-Force $Q^+ \leftarrow$
- 2... $\oplus B \Rightarrow \ominus K_B \equiv \overline{BK_B} \equiv q^{0-} = - \gg P_B$, creating $[P_{-B1}] \rightarrow$ Weak-Chromodynamics-Force $C^{0-} \leftarrow$
- 3... $\oplus C \Rightarrow \ominus K_C \equiv \overline{CK_C} \equiv q^- = - \gg P_C$, creating $[P_{-C1}] \rightarrow$ Strong-Chromodynamics-Force D^-
- 4... $\oplus A \Rightarrow \ominus A_E \equiv \overline{AA_E} \equiv q_+ = - \gg P_A$, creating $[P_{+AAE}] \rightarrow$ Weak-Lepton-Force $W^+ \leftarrow$
- 5... $\oplus A \Rightarrow \ominus K_C \equiv \overline{AK_C} \equiv q_+ = - \gg D_A$, creating $[D_{+AKC}] \rightarrow$ Strong - Up - Quark $u \leftarrow$

The Nuclear Fusion = [Mixture] :

On Nucleus Tetrahedron $\begin{pmatrix} q^+ & \dots & q^- \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ q^- & \dots & q^+ \end{pmatrix}$ when Three Hydrogen Mixture , $H_1^1 + H_1^1 + H_1^1 \equiv$

$$[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] + [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] + [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] = \begin{matrix} q^+ & q^- & q^+ \\ q^- & 3He & q^- \\ q^+ & q^- & q^+ \end{matrix} = H_1^1 + H_1^2 = H_2^3 + 6e = H_2^3 + \underline{25,6.MeV \gamma rays}$$

For the six elements issues $6.e = 6.[m_e, c^2] = 6.\{7,6.10^{-30}.(3.10^8m/s)^2 / [1,6022.10^{-19}eV]\}$
 $= 256,14779.10^5eV = 256,14779.10^5eV = 25,614779.10^6 eV = 25,614779.MeV = \gamma rays .$

Hydrogen-Stability is as $\rightarrow [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] \rightarrow [Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = D] \equiv \left\{ \uparrow Z + \left[\oplus \frac{::}{2} + \ominus \frac{::}{2} \right] D \right\}$

The Nuclear Fission = [Braking] :

When Uranium U_{235} is bombarded by Neutrons then forms unsteady U_{236} which breaks down , Splitting into two Particles by emitting 3-Neutrons \emptyset . Elements Uranium Krypton Barium are

92- Uranium ---- $U - 238,030 \rightarrow |3p| - |3s| = \overline{6}U_{-2M}^{+2E} = [238] \equiv m, k = \{ 2-2 \}$

36- Krypton ---- $Kr - 83,800 \rightarrow |3p| - |3s| = \overline{4}Kr_{-0M}^{+0E} = [84] \equiv m, k = \{ 00 \}$

56- Barium ---- $Ba - 137,327 \rightarrow |3p| - |3s| = \overline{6}Ba_{-6M}^{+2E} = [137] \equiv m, k = \{ 2-2 \}$

The Neutron action is , $\emptyset \rightarrow U_{235} , \rightleftharpoons U_{236} = Ba_{56}^{137} + Kr_{36}^{84} + 3.n_0^1$, and this

Because from the **Three elements** issuing

a.. from atomic-numbers $\rightarrow 92 = 36 + 56$

b.. from orbital-numbers $\rightarrow |3p| - |3s| = 3.\{ |3p| + |3s| \} = [|3p| + |3s|]$

c.. from bonding-numbers $\rightarrow [|3p| = 20. e^+ \rightleftharpoons 3s| = 20. e^-] = 3.n_0^1$

Or from relation ,

54 $Xe_{48}^6 \equiv Kr_{4x8}^4 + 18 \equiv$ **The Fifth-Stable-State where the 18 Electrons are Neutrons .**

55 $Cs_{49}^6 \equiv Xe_{48}^6 + 1.n_0^1$

56 $Ba_{50}^6 \equiv Xe_{48}^6 + 2.n_0^1 \rightarrow$ **i.e. the $3.n_0^1$**

1...For α Decay = $U_{92}^{238} \rightarrow He_{2}^4 + Th_{90}^{234}$ issues (a) $92 = 2 + 90$, (b) $238 = 4 + 234$, (c) $0 = -2 + 2 = 0$,

For α Decay = $U_{90}^{230} \rightarrow He_{2}^4 + Ra_{88}^{226}$ issues (a) $90 = 2 + 88$, (b) $230 = 4 + 226$,

(c) $+2 = +2 + 0 = +2$,

2...For β Decay = $Th_{90}^{234} \rightarrow e_{-1}^0 + Pa_{91}^{234}$ issues (a) $90 = -1 + 91$, (b) $234 = 0 + 234$,

(c) $4 = 1 + 3 = 0$,

For β Decay = $Pa_{91}^{234} \rightarrow e_{-1}^0 + U_{92}^{234}$ issues (a) $91 = -1 + 92$, (b) $234 = 0 + 234$,

(c) $3 = 1 + 2 = 3$,

3...For γ Decay = $U_{92}^{238} \rightarrow He_{2}^4 + Th_{90}^{234} + 2.\gamma_0^0$, issues (a) $92 = 2 + 90 + 0$,

- (b) $238 = 4 + 234 + 0$, (c) $0 = +2 - 2 + 0 = 0$,
For γ Decay = $U_{92}^{238} \rightarrow He_2^4 + Th_{90}^{234} + 2.\gamma_0^0$, issues (a) $92 = 2 + 90 + 0$,
 (b) $238 = 4 + 234 + 0$, (c) $2 = 0 + 4 - 2 = 2$,

Examples :

- 1.. In an Conductor $d = AK_A = 2r$, with \oplus obstacle at K_A Point occupies zero velocity and \oplus Charge is accelerated .The Initial light-velocity is accelerated as $v^2 = \bar{v}_0^2 + 2a.r$, or $a = \frac{-\bar{v}_0^2}{2.r} = \frac{[2,9979.10^8]^2}{2.r} = \frac{8,9874044.10^{16}}{2.r}$ m/s² . For Conductors , $r = 10^{-16}, 10^0, 10^{16}$ then , $a = \frac{-\bar{v}_0^2}{2.r} = \frac{8,9874.10^{16}}{2.10^{-16}} = 4,4937.10^{32} \frac{m}{s^2}$
 $a = \frac{-\bar{v}_0^2}{2.r} = \frac{8,9874044.10^{16}}{2.10^0} = 4,4937022.10^{16}$ m/s² , $a = \frac{-\bar{v}_0^2}{2.r} = \frac{8,9874044.10^{16}}{2.10^{16}} = 4,4937022.10^0$ m/s² .

The force on Charges becomes from the Electric field as $\bar{F}_K = m. \bar{a}_x = q. \bar{E}_F = +e. \bar{E}_F$ and $\bar{E}_F = \frac{m.a}{q = e}$,
 or

$$\bar{E}_F = \frac{F}{q} = \frac{m.a}{e} = \frac{m}{e} [a] = \frac{9.10^{-31}}{1,6022.10^{-19}} [4,4937022.10^{32}] = 25,242366. 10^{20} \frac{N}{C}$$

$$\bar{E}_F = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Charge}} = \frac{m.a}{e} = \frac{m}{e} [a] = \frac{9.10^{-31}}{1,6022.10^{-19}} [4,4937022.10^{16}] = 25,242366. 10^4 \frac{N}{C}$$

$$\bar{E}_F = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Charge}} = \frac{m.a}{e} = \frac{m}{e} [a] = \frac{9.10^{-31}}{1,6022.10^{-19}} [4,4937022.10^0] = 25,242366. 10^{-12} \frac{N}{C}$$

- i.e. The \oplus Charge is accelerated **Opposite to initial direction** of \ominus Charge in an Electric-field \bar{E}_F
 This Property of Acceleration , creates the Magnetic-Fields in Electric Conductors as Atoms are.
 It is shown later that this happens Since Nucleus is of \oplus Charge and Electrons of \ominus Charge ,

- 2.. The Uniform circular motion of electron in Caves constitutes a current $I = \frac{e}{T} = e.f$, and $T = \frac{2\pi r}{c}$,
 $I = \frac{e.c}{2\pi r} = \frac{1,6022.10^{-19}.2,997910^8}{2\pi.r} = 7,644811.10^{-12} . [\frac{1}{r}]$, and for $r = 10^{-16}, 10^0, 10^{16}$ m then ,

$$I = \frac{e.c}{2\pi r} = 7,644811.10^{-12} . [\frac{1}{r=10^{-16}}] = 7,644811.10^4 , 7,644811.10^{-12} , 7,644811.10^{-28}$$
 Ampere.

- 3.. The Electric-Potential $V = \frac{q}{r} = 8,99.10^9 \frac{Nm^2}{C^2} [\frac{1,6022.10^{-19}}{r=10^{-16}}] = 14,403778.10^6 = 1,4403778.10^7$ Volt
 $V = \frac{q}{r} = 8,99.10^9 \frac{Nm^2}{C^2} [\frac{1,6022.10^{-19}}{r=10^0, 10^{16}}] = 14,403778.10^{-10}$ V , $14,403778.10^{-26}$ V ,

- 4.. Electric-Field $\bar{E}_F = \frac{\Delta V}{d} = [\frac{14,403778.10^6}{r=10^{-16}, 10^0, 10^{16}}] = 14,403778.10^{22}$, $14,403778.10^6$, $14,403778.10^{-10}$ V

- 5.. Force on electron is $F = q. \bar{E}_F = 1,6022.10^{-19} . \{14,403778.10^{22}\} = 23,077733.10^3$ N . and
 $F = q. \bar{E}_F = 1,6022.10^{-19} . \{14,403778.10^{6-16}\} = 23,077733.10^{-13}$ N , $23,077733.10^{-35}$ N , and

- 6.. The Produced Work is $W = F.ds = F r = 23,077733.10^3 . \{10^{-16}\} = 23,077733.10^{-13}$ Joule
 $W = F.ds = F r = 23,077733.10^3 . \{10^0, 10^{16}\} = 23,077733.10^3$, $23,077733.10^{19}$ J . e_0

- 7.. The Intensity I_{E-r} is , $I_{E-r} = \frac{c.E^2}{2} = [\frac{2,9979.10^8.1,6022.10^{-19}(14,403778.10^{22})^2}{2}] = 498,26077.10^{33}$ W/m²
 $I_{E-2} = \frac{c.E^2}{2} = 498,26077.10^1$ W = $4,9826077.10^3$ W and $I_{E-3} = \frac{c.E^2}{2} = 4,9826077.10^{-29}$ W/m²

- 8.. The Power $P_{E-r} = \frac{E^2}{Z = \pi r^2} = \frac{(14,403778.10^{22})^2}{\pi.(10^{-16})^2} = 6,6039377.10^{77}$ W , $6,6039377.10^{57}$, $6,604.10^{13}$ W

- 9.. In an Conductor of Two-Capacitors of area A and Charge q then Charge density on Plates is
 $\sigma = \frac{q}{A}$, and the Electric field $E = \frac{\sigma}{e_0} = \frac{q}{A.e_0}$, and from Potential difference $V = E d$ then $E = \frac{V}{e_0}$,
 and $\frac{V}{d} = \frac{q}{A.e_0}$ or $V = q. [\frac{d}{A.e_0}] = \frac{q}{A} = E d$. From above area $\rightarrow A = \frac{q.d}{V} = [\frac{1,6022.10^{-19}(10^{-16})}{14,403778.(r=10^6)}] = m^2$
 $1,112347.10^{-42}$, $1,11235.10^{-26}$. $1,11235.10^{-10}$ m² , and Stress $\sigma = \frac{q}{A} = 1,44038.10^{23,7,-9} \frac{T}{m^2}$

- 10.. From $E_K + E_P = 2.E_u = \sigma . \Phi = \sigma \{ \frac{[1 \pm \sqrt{5}]}{2} \} = \sigma \{ 1,6180339 , -0,6180339 \} = \sigma \{ e^+ , e^- \}$, then
 $e^- = 1,6180339 / 2 = 0,8090169$, and $2.e^+ = -0,6180339 \rightleftharpoons eV$.

- 11.. **The Stability of Forces in a Nucleus** , is succeeded by *The Ceba`s - Cave - Forces* , which are in the **Inscribed Sphere** of the Tetrahedron , while **The Stability of Forces in Cube** , is also succeeded by *The Ceba`s - Cave - Forces* , which are in the **Circumscribed Sphere** of the Tetrahedron and on which exist the Atom`s - Orbitals .

- 12.. Exists $1\text{KPa} = 10^3 \text{Pa}$, $1\text{MPa} = 10^6 \text{Pa}$, $1\text{GPa} = 10^9 \text{Pa}$, $q = i t A s = C b$,

$1\text{eV} = [1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ Cb}]$, $1\text{V} = 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ Joule}$, $q_e = 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ Culomb}$,
The Density of Electric current becomes from the Electron- Orbit-motion as equation
 $J = \frac{i}{A} = \sigma_{n-\text{max}} = \frac{v_{n-\text{max}}}{\Phi} = \frac{\text{Amper}}{\text{m}^2} = \frac{w_H}{\Phi}$, **Energy** becomes from the maximum velocity
 and it is The Kinetic energy, **of the Bracket-Hook electrons of the n-element**,

$$E_{n-\text{max}} = \frac{m_e \cdot [v_{n-\text{max}}]^2}{2} = \frac{9,1 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ Kg} \cdot [v_{n-\text{max}} \text{ m/s}]^2}{2} = \text{Joule}$$

From **Hydrogen Bracket-Hook Ellipse**, $a = 0,6 \text{ \AA} = 5,29 \cdot 10^{-11} = 0,529 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}$. $b = R_H = 12 \cdot 10^{-9} = 120 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}$, and from equation $v = w R$ then are measured stresses and Energy.

2d. The Bracket-Hooks as Conductors Are The Physical-Hands of Atoms for Actions :

Figure - 15- : The Active-Conductors of Elements and The Space , Anti-Space formation .

Point , in E-geometry is considered nothing , without Position and direction while in , MG = **Material - Geometry** [1 Positive ⊕ and 1 Negative ⊖] . From Nothing (i.e. the Point Z) to Existence (i.e. to be another Spherical Point P) issues the **Zero Virtual work law** , where zero Work is the equilibrium of two Equal and Opposite forces on Points and is [⊕ - d - ⊖] . Thus Space [S] is **Z-Point ⊕** , **Anti-space P-Point ⊖** , and $d = ZP =$ The Conductor of Points . Since , **The Position and the Number of Points** , create the Spaces so the Only Three elements are $\rightarrow \{ \oplus , [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] , \ominus \} \equiv [+ , 0 , -] \leftarrow$ for Material Geometry exist linearly in moulds . The Space Anti-Space and , Neutral-Space Conductors are self-Sustaining .The Stability of $\{ \oplus - \text{Space} [A B C] \}$, $\{ \ominus - \text{Anti-Space} [K_A K_B K_C] \}$ and Neutral-Space or Sub-Space in a Plane $[A_E , B_E , C_E]$ is $\rightarrow \{ [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] \equiv ds \equiv [\oplus \leftarrow ds \rightarrow \ominus] .$

Stability :

The number of Moulds of **Stationary-States** are $as \rightarrow 2^{n-1-4 \text{ Points}} \equiv 2, 4, 8, 16 \equiv 4\text{-Types} \leftarrow$ i.e. Monads are formed from the first **4- Moulds** as \rightarrow The 1-Point which is everywhere, the 2- Points which form Vectors , the 3- Points which form the Planes , the 4- Points which form

the Volumes .For $n > 4$ as this is the Atoms Structure, follows the Sustainability of the Spaces and Anti-spaces. Since Space-Energy Structures follow the M-Geometry Stability these follow the Mould of Spaces $2^{n-3} = 8$ Elements which is **The-Cube** as shown before.

- 1.. In the constant , **Hydrogen Conservative-Cave-System** , which creates only closed Orbit shapes as Circles , Ellipses and Eight-shape , ∞ , are placed the above elements , $\pi g \equiv$ **Energy** \equiv [meter of area * meter of force] \equiv **Electrons on Orbits** , and also the **Unit-Space** \equiv **Massive-United-Unit-Space** $\equiv \rightarrow [+v.s^2] \leftarrow$ jointed through the Neutral Material-Points [(+) [\leftrightarrow] (-)] with the **Strong-force** $\rightarrow S_F = h . f_n \equiv h . \{ S \equiv B_p \equiv$ **EM-R** $\equiv f_{1=N} , f_2 , f_3 , f_D , f_n \} \equiv h.n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} \equiv h \frac{n.B}{4\pi^2 r^4} \dots(mg)$ Equations (m) , (mg) are the **Energy-Space-constituents** in Hydrogen-System .

2.. **The Protons and the Nucleus Structure :**

From above MP $\equiv [(+)[\leftrightarrow](-)] \equiv$ Neutral = **n** , then

- a.. For 1 Proton $[(+)[\leftrightarrow](-)] \leftrightarrow (+) \equiv$ Neutral $\rightarrow \begin{matrix} n = 1 & p = 1 \\ p & n \\ n & p \end{matrix}$
- b.. For 2 Proton $(+)\leftrightarrow[(-)\leftrightarrow(+)][(+)\leftrightarrow(-)]\leftrightarrow(+)$ \equiv Neutral $\rightarrow \begin{matrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{2} & 0 \\ 1e & 0 & 0 \end{matrix}$
- c.. For 3 Proton $(+)\leftrightarrow[(-)(+)](+)[(-)(+)](+)[(-)(+)] \equiv$ Neutral $\rightarrow \begin{matrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{2} & 0 \\ 1e & 0 & 0 \end{matrix}$
- d.. For 4 Proton $(+)\leftrightarrow[(-)(+)](+)[(-)(+)](+)[(-)(+)](+)[(-)(+)] \equiv$ Neutral $\rightarrow \begin{matrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{2} & 0 \\ 1e & 1e & 0 \end{matrix}$
- e.. For k Proton $(k1)\leftrightarrow[(-)(+)](k2)[(-)(+)](+)[(-)(+)](+)[(-)(+)] \equiv$ Neutral $\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} ke & ke & ke \\ ke & k : 8 - 18 & ke \\ ke & ke & ke \end{bmatrix}$

f.. The Inscribed to the Tetrahedron-Sphere consists the Nucleus \equiv The \oplus Space , and in the Circumscribed to the Tetrahedron-Cube Sphere consists the Orbitals \equiv The \ominus Space .

3.. **Electro-Mechanical** Equation , $q \bar{B}_L = 2\pi m f$, exploited in Hydrogen-Atom creates the **Uniform Magnetic-field** \bar{B}_L which IGNORES the velocities in cave **a** , and Capacitance in Energy-levels (1-2). The Heap of masses and Charges Follows Permutation Rules as the Neutral-quantities and Newton Planetary-Laws as well as the Vibrating-equation , $m \ddot{x} + w^2 x = 0$, which gives the frequencies .

a.. Hydrogen - Cave is a **Uniform-Magnetic-field** , Because \bar{B}_L , is **Independent** of the **Electron's - velocity** v_e and of the **Cave-radius** $r \equiv a$, therefore electron is not accelerated in the Magnetic-Field , but its Strength is **Dependent on Quantum-frequency** , **f** , only . This demand formulates the Hydrogen Energy-caves and the **Quantization** of Energy \equiv motion , beginning from the Nucleus and extended to Orbits-Planets with Resonance-Energy $E_R = \frac{1}{a} \left[\frac{4\pi^2}{c^2} + \frac{L^2}{2m} \right] = \frac{1}{a} \left[\frac{4\pi^2}{c^2} + \frac{S^2}{2m} \right] =$ a Signal ..(3)

The Atoms Electric and Magnetic vectors :

Carbon-Vectors $\rightarrow \overline{2C} \frac{+4\bar{E}}{-4\bar{M}} , V, O - A, B, C, D, \equiv \{ \overline{OA} , \overline{OB} , \overline{OC} , \overline{OD} \} , \{ \overline{AO} , \overline{BO} , \overline{CO} , \overline{DO} \} \leftarrow$ Where , $\bar{2}$, is the Stable-State for Carbon - Atom , in the **Tetrahedron -Volume** of the **Cube Inscribed** to the **Outer - Sphere** on which lie the Tetrahedron of 4-vertices .

4. \bar{E} = The Four-Electrical-Vectors from Conductor $\{ \overline{OA} , \overline{OB} , \overline{OC} , \overline{OD} \} ,$

4. \bar{M} = The Four-Magnetic-Vectors from Conductor $\{ \overline{AO} , \overline{BO} , \overline{CO} , \overline{DO} \} ,$ and in other Atoms ,

$$1\text{- Hydrogen -Vector} \rightarrow \vec{1H} \frac{+1\vec{E}}{-1\vec{M}}, L, O - B, \quad \equiv \{ \vec{OB} \}, \{ \vec{BO} \} \leftarrow$$

3d.. The Mechanical Explanation of Bonding . [80]

The Energy-Tetrahedron and , The 3- Conductors into The Energy- Cube and Spheres :

Figure - 16- : The Electric - Magnetic Field of 3-Conductors which lie on the DABC Tetrahedron , The Stability of the $\rightarrow \{ \oplus 4\text{-Space } [D A B C] \}$ Regular - *Tetrahedron* , occurs INTO the $\{ \ominus 8\text{-Anti-Space Cube } , [DA_1A D_1 , B B_1CC_1] \}$, and This Positive $\rightarrow \{ \oplus 8\text{-Space - Cube } , [DA_1A D_1 , B B_1CC_1] \}$, INTO The $\{ \ominus 16\text{-Anti-Space } [1 ,2 ,3 ,4 ,5 , 6 , 7 , 8 - 9 ,10 ,11 , 12 , 13 ,14 , 15 , 16] \}$ *Sphere Cube on Vertices* . = Point [The Point 16 $\equiv | \Rightarrow | Z]$ consists the **Navel-String Gate** into the **Triangle-Circle-System** $\{ Z-(\Delta D,ABC) , \Delta [T1T2 T3] \}$ of the Stationary Bases which Results on **2-Anti-Parallel-Strands** . These 2-Stands are **Pin & Socket** , of Atoms.

The Dual Photon $\vec{v} \left[\frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \vec{v} . [\vec{f}_n] + f_n]$, occupies Stresses = σ and velocities \vec{v} , in the Tiny-caves r . The Colours in light , are the **Still-Sub-Units** in Storage $\rightarrow [\vec{v} . \vec{f}_n] \leftarrow$ and exist as Frequencies of \rightarrow Violet , Blue , Green , with their Complementary Yellow , Orange , Red \leftarrow

Every 8-electrons are **vibrations** on **Atoms-Cube-Structure** $\{ A \text{ Tetrahedron in Cube in a Sphere } \}$ whether it be **Sound** or **Light** . Above Structure is followed by all Compounds .

Molecules are Systems consisted of \rightarrow The **PERIFERAL** \equiv *Skeleton* M_{16} and The **CENTRAL** \equiv *Fittings* M_8 , and the **ACCESSORIES** $\equiv M_4$ or M_2 , M_1 . This Property of Atoms and of the Compounds is **The Critical-Valve of Switching the motion** as this happens in the Electro-magnetic Solenoid Valves with High or low Pressure and flow rates directly or not .

DNA is a Nervous System consisted of , The Peripheral = *Skeleton* M_{16} , The Central = *Fittings* M_8 , and , The *Accessories* = M_4 or M_2 , M_1 . For the Outside Cells membrane is M_{16} and correspond to the Inside M_1 , M_2 , M_4 , M_8 *Accessories* . With this way is Possible the Damages to be repaired to all Parts concerning the Damages . The Healthy Parts consist the \rightarrow **Tetrahedron in Cube in an**

Sphere Mechanism ← where the \oplus Parts are in the Inscribed-circle of **Tetrahedron** , and the \ominus , Parts are in the Circumscribed-circle of **Tetrahedron** .

4d...The Absolute and Relative Wave - Motion of Systems ,

The Angular Momentum of any Material Point in STPL mechanism Applied

→ **In-Sphere , Tetrahedron - Cube , Out-Sphere Mechanism** ←

In - Fig.16 ABC is any Right-angled triangle at A , (The-Space) , $K_A K_B K_C$ triangle is the (Sub-Space) , $A_E B_E C_E$ triangle is the (Anti-space) respectively. The Instantaneous Pole P of rotation is off the Circle of diameter BC.

The Poles of rotation lie on

{ $D_A - P_A$ } Reference System. Reference System { $D_A - P_A$ } \equiv [R] (x', y', z', t') moves with velocity \bar{v} , Parallel to $x-x'$, axis

Figure - 17- : [64-A]

with respect to the fixed and Absolute System { $D_A - O$ } \equiv [S] (x, y, z, t).

The Geometrical expression of Lorentz factor γ , is as $\sec \phi = \gamma = OD_A : AD_A =$

$\pm 1 / \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} = c / \sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$, which is the Conchoidal of Nicomedes { $s = a + b \cdot \sec \phi$ }

and which acquires the material Angle $\phi = \frac{v}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}$, i.e.

The Euclidean Geometry is the Spring of the Geometrical Relative Velocities .

The STPL Line :

Points [A , B , C] , [A_E, B_E, C_E] , [K_A, K_B, K_C] when is applied on the three lines ($K_A K_B, K_B K_C, K_C K_A$) then the SIX Pairs of the corresponding lines , extended are concurrent at Points P_A, P_B, P_C for the Triple Pairs of lines (The Pascal's Perspectivity of Points in Euclidean Geometry) ,

[AA_E, BB_E, CC_E] , [BB_E, CA_E, AC_E] , [CC_E, AB_E, BA_E] and at Points D_A, D_B, D_C for the Triple Pairs of Lines [$K_B K_C, BC, B_E C_E$] , [$K_A K_C, AC, A_E C_E$] and [$K_A K_B, AB, A_E B_E$] , (Desargues's Perspectivity of Points in Euclidean Geometry) and all the 18 common Points lie on a straight line the → STPL Mechanism . This Mechanism Stabilizes the Nucleus Forces for → { \oplus - Space [A B C] } and { \ominus - Anti-Space [$K_A K_B K_C$] } and is succeeded by The Pascal's -launched caves r t Perspectivity through the STPL Circuit of the Ptolemy's and Ceba's Geometry theorem for Vector-Forces .

The 2-Anti-Parallel-Strands : Fig-18-

The 2-Stands are the **Electric - field and Magnetic Field** , of Atoms as in the LC - circuit . The Stationary Bases of Atoms result on the 2-Anti-Parallel-Strands . These 2-Strands are alternately the **Electromagnetic equilibrium** of Atoms . i.e. Atoms , **Electric - field - Strand [ZOM]** is the motion , and **Magnetic Field - Strand [OMZ]** is the Storage to this motion , which is thus the **Identity of Atoms -Actions** . For the LC-circuit , Energy in its Electric field E and the inductor L stores Energy in its Magnetic field B .

THE D, A B C - ENERGY- ELECTRIC-TETRAHEDRON ENTERS IN THE - CUBE'S -DIAGONALS , DA, DB, DC , DO , BEING COMMON TO , DT_T,1-2-3 , MAGNETIC -TETRAHEDRON -DIAGONALS

- (1) = The MOTION in ONE Conductor , DA , is an **Non-Guided missile**
- (2) = The MOTION in TWO Conductors , DA-DB , is an **Guided , DO , missile**
- (3) = The MOTION in TWO Equal-Conductors = **Electromagnetic , DO , Wave**
- (4) = The MOTION in THREE Conductors = That in **Regular , DABC , Tetrahedron**
- (5) = The MOTION in More than THREE Conductors is Equivalent to **TETRAHEDRON Diagonals = ELECTRIC - FIELDS , DM[⊥]ABC Base & Storage in CUBE'S Diagonals , OT₁ , OT₂ , OT₃ , = MAGNETIC - FIELDS .**
- (6) = **ELECTRIC-FIELD** in TETRAHEDRON Enters in CUBE'S STORAGES as **MAGNETIC - FIELDS** , and VICE -VERSA in AN ROTATING -PIVOT .

THE INSCRIBED - SPHERE INTO TETRAHEDRON , D , A , B , C , IN CUBE = Z 2 A 4 B 6 C 8
 $|\overline{OC}| = \lambda = \frac{c}{f} = \frac{2 c \cdot \pi r}{\sigma \cdot \Phi}$
 $\overline{OM} \downarrow = \overline{O} , \overline{A-B-C-D} = K E [x+y+z] = F_{x,y,z}$
 $\overline{TO} \uparrow = \overline{T} , T-1-2-3-T = \overline{U} E [x+y+z] = \overline{U}_{x,y,z}$

THE INERTIAL ELECTRIC FORCE { M - Z = - (M-Z) }

IN TETRAHEDRON Of- Edge-Length a , VECTOR $\overline{DO} \perp \{ABC\}$ PLANE MOTION EQUILIBRIUM IN THE TWO ANTIPARALLEL , $\uparrow \downarrow$, STRANDS , O_M , O_T .

$\overline{ZOM} = \overline{DA} + \overline{DB} + \overline{DC} =$ THE ELECTROMOTIVE -VECTOR $\downarrow \downarrow$
 $\overline{OMZ} = \overline{OMT_1} + \overline{OMT_2} + \overline{OMT_3} =$ THE MAGNETIC - VECTOR $\uparrow \uparrow$
 $\overline{OMZ} + \overline{OTZ} = \overline{O} =$ THE DOUBLE-HELIX -ELECTROMOTIVE-STRANDS $\uparrow \downarrow$

Figure - 18:- Motion \equiv Energy, Into Z , DABC Tetrahedron, Into Cube Z-8 of Outer Sphere {O,OZ}.

The Stability of the Space Anti-Space Circuit is formed by the three elements $\rightarrow \{ \oplus , [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] , \ominus \} \equiv \{ + , 0 , - \} \leftarrow$. The Bonding follows above logic with the same three Elements and compounds which are Atoms with Hydrogen as common Base . For all Atoms , the Hydrogen is the **Common Element** that exists in all Spaces , while the **Resonance frequency** is the \rightarrow **Neutral-Anti-Space-Element** \leftarrow **The First Solid** is that of \rightarrow **Regular Tetrahedron** In a Cube and , **Inscribed in Outer-Sphere** \leftarrow The why , its Properties as below. In Fig-16 , D -A , B , C , is the Tetrahedron in the Cube. (Fig-18)

- 1.. The Regular-Tetrahedron of edge-length , a , consisted of 4 Edges , 4 Vertices , and 4 Face Areas
- 2.. The Height $OM = h = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} a$, The Volume $V_{TET} = \frac{a^3}{6\sqrt{2}}$, The In-Sphere - Radius $R_{INS} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{24}}$,
The Mid-Sphere-Radius $R_{MIS} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{8}}$, The Ex-Sphere-Radius $R_{EXS} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{6}}$, Distance-Vertex $H_V = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} a$
- 3..The In-Sphere-Volume $V_{INS} = \frac{4\pi}{3}[R_{INS}]^3 = \frac{\pi}{18} \frac{a^3}{\sqrt{24}} = \frac{\pi}{36} \frac{a^3}{\sqrt{6}}$ Sphere in \overline{ZA} , \overline{ZB} , \overline{ZC} & ABC Base-Plane
- 4..The Mid-Sphere-Volume $V_{MIS} = \frac{4\pi}{3}[R_{MIS}]^3 = \frac{\pi}{6} \frac{a^3}{\sqrt{8}} = \frac{6\pi}{36} \frac{a^3}{\sqrt{8}}$ Sphere in Square $M_1M_2T_2T_1$
- 5..The Ex-Sphere-Volume $V_{EXS} = \frac{4\pi}{3}[R_{EXS}]^3 = \frac{2\pi}{9} \frac{a^3}{\sqrt{6}} = \frac{8\pi}{36} \frac{a^3}{\sqrt{6}} = 8.V_{INS}$, equal to the $2^3 = 8$ Electrons.
In this Ex-Sphere-Surface are also the 4-Pins \equiv Orbital-Bracket-Hooks \equiv Conductors
- 6.. For any 1- Face Area $[A , B , C]$, being in , $x - y$, Base-Plane the remaining -Three-Faces are in **D-Space** , so exist the 4-Types- Tetrahedron-Bases , $[A , B , C],[D , A , B],[D , B , C],[D , C , A]$.
- 7.. Regular-Cube is consisted of $4 \times 2 = 8$ Points , 4 Planes , of which Each Plane corresponds to the Nibs of Regular-Tetrahedron .This issues because of Stability needed in Spaces and Anti-Spaces .
- 8.. The Regular-Tetrahedron-in Cube is the **Active-Conductor** into the Regular-Cube \equiv Anti - Space.
- 9.. For The Regular-Anti-Cube which is consisted of $8 \times 2 = 16$ Points and Each Point corresponds to that of Regular-Cube . This because of Stability needed in Space-Cube and Anti-Space-Cube .

Let M_1 , M_2 , M_3 , be the middle-Points of Tetrahedron-Conductors , DA , DB , DC , of triangles $\Delta[M_1,M_2,M_3]$ which are similar to $\Delta[A,B,C]$ and of area $E_{ABC} = 2.E_{M_1,M_2,M_3}$ IN Level $H_V = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}a$
Points , M_2 , M_3 , of triangle $\Delta[DBC]$, lie in the Mid-Points of , DC , DB , $\therefore \rightarrow |M_2M_3| = \frac{CB}{2} = \frac{a}{2}$
Let T_1,T_2,T_3 , be the middle-Points of Plane- Base- Conductors , AB , BC , CA , IN Level $H_V = 0$.
Because Points T_2 , T_3 , of triangle $\Delta[ABC]$ lie on the mid-Points of , CB , CA , $\therefore \rightarrow |T_2T_3| = \frac{AB}{2} = \frac{a}{2}$
 $= |M_2M_3|$, and triangles $\Delta [M_1 , M_2 , M_3]$, $\Delta [T_1,T_2,T_3]$ are Symmetrically - equal , Parallels and Perpendicular. Because triangles sides, $M_1 - M_2 = M_2 - M_3 = M_3 - M_1 = |T_2T_3| = |T_3T_1| = |T_1T_2|$, the Shapes $[M_1 , M_2 , T_2 , T_3]$, $[M_2 , M_3 , T_3 , T_1]$, $[M_3 , M_1 , T_1 , T_2]$ are Squares on Levels $H_V = 0$, $\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} a$.

The Wave Analysis of monads - Systems :

For free vibration on monads $|AB| = \bar{q} = [s + \bar{v}\nabla i]$ oscillating under the action $[\oplus \rightarrow \ominus]$ (thrust) being inherent in itself , is subject to *damping* because Energy is dissipated by the *stiffness* , \mathbf{k} , of monad . The *constant of Proportionality* , \mathbf{c} , regarding motion of *mass* , \mathbf{m} , when is Placed into motion , oscillation will take place at the natural frequency , f_n , which also is a Property of monad.

Coulomb force $[\oplus \rightarrow \ominus] = F_{[+ \leftrightarrow -]} = \frac{[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]}{r^2} = \frac{[2\sigma]}{r^2} = F = \sigma .A = [\frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi}] .A = w r .[\frac{A}{\Phi}] = v .[\frac{A}{\Phi}] = \bar{v} \frac{a^2}{\Phi}$

Acts on a Surface , A , therefore motion is stored Into the Plane $|ZD|^2 = |\bar{v}|^2$, which is the Electromagnetic field , $\bar{E}\bar{M}_F$. Natural-Frequencies f_n , follow that Magnitude which is the Vibration to be measured differently there is not vibration and Not any Resonance with others .

a.. The Forced Vibration of an 2-DOF , the 2-Natural frequencies and their order of Magnitude

When a System is subjected to harmonic excitation , it is forced to vibrate at the same frequency as that of the excitation . Common sources of Harmonic excitation are unbalance in **Rotating Moulds** composed of , **Skeleton M_{16}** , **Fittings M_8** , and **Accessories M_4 or M_2** , as forces produced by reciprocating **Parts** and the motion of the **Skeleton** itself . These excitations may be undesirable for equipment , M_8 , M_4 , M_2 , whose operation may be disturbed or for the safety of the **Structure** if large vibration amplitudes develop . Resonance for large vibration is avoided by Dampers and or Absorbers from equipment M_8 , M_4 , M_2 , Properly modulated in vibrations Skeleton M_{16} .

Skeleton M_{16} is the 1st- Cube into the 2nd-Volume-Cube *Dekahexa - vertices* , **Skeleton M_8** contains the **Cube-Volume-Tetrahedron** , *Eight-vertices* , **Skeleton M_4** is the **Plane-Triangle** into *Volume-Tetrahedron* , and **Skeleton M_2** is the **Line -Vector** into *Plane-Triangle* , *where*

The Tetrahedron is **Solid** → M_4 , 1-3-5-7, → Needed for *Nucleus-Forces-Stability*.
 The Octahedron is **Solid** → M_8 , 1-(2)-3-(4)-5-(6)-7-(8), → Needed for *Electrons-Positions*.
 Deka -Exavertices-**Solid** → M_{16} , 1-(2)-3-(4)-5-(6)-7-(8)- [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16],
 The Triangles are **Planes** → M_2 , 1,3,4 - 1,5,6 - 1,7,2, → Needed for *Stresses-conservation*.
 The Line-Segments are **Vectors** → M_1 , 1,3 - 1,5 - 1,7, → Needed for *Forces-Actioning*.

→ i.e. $M_{16} \equiv$ Deka-hexa-vertices, $M_8 \equiv$ Cube, $M_4 \equiv$ Tetrahedron, $M_2 \equiv$ Triangle, $M_1 \equiv$ Vector

The **Joints** between Moulds are Line-Segments for $J_{M_8-16} = 1-16, 2-15, 3-14, 4-13, 5-12, 6-11, 7-10, 8-9$, for $J_{M_4-8} = (1-2, 1-4, 1-6), (3-2, 3-4, 3-8), (5-4, 5-6, 5-8), (7-2, 7-6, 7-8)$, for $J_{M_2-4} = (1-3-5), (1-5-7), (1-7-3)$, and for → J_{M_1-2} 1-3, 1-5, 1-7, **2nd-Volume-Cubes**
 Above Geometrical-Structures consist the Spaces and Anti-Spaces in which motion \equiv Energy is
 → **Conserved** \equiv **Survive, Developed, Reproduced, Stilled** \equiv **Split**, as in Figure, 19-24-26.

2., For a Forced 2-DOF Harmonic Vibration as is the case of *Skeleton* M_{16} , of the main mass

$m_{16} \equiv m_1$ and any *Fittings* M_8 , or and *Accessories* M_4 or M_2 , of mass $m_{8-4-2} \equiv m_2$

Response is of **2 - Natural frequencies**, w_1, w_2 . It was shown that the **Torsion** Magnitude is $TD_{OMT} = \sigma \cdot |ZD| \cdot |ZP| = \sigma \cdot r^2 = \sigma \cdot |ZD|^2 = w \cdot |ZA|^3 / \Phi$, and because the decline Dumping for

each n , Period c_{nf} is equal to $c_{nf} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(n)}}$, $n \cdot \sqrt{2} = \sqrt{2} \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \sqrt{2} \dots n$, times, then $c_{nf} = \frac{1}{n \cdot \sqrt{2}}$

and Torsion → $TZ_{OMT} = \sigma \cdot |ZA| \cdot |ZP| = \sigma \cdot r^2 = \sigma \cdot |ZA|^2 = w \cdot |ZA|^3 / \Phi = w \cdot v^3 \cdot \left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(n)}} \right| \dots (2-1)$

For Resultant-axis direction ↓, in Conductor's -Pivot-axis \rightleftharpoons is Propelled → $v_1 \cdot \pi \cdot [r]^2 = 2\pi^2 \cdot f \cdot r^3 =$

$\sigma \Phi [\pi r^2] = \frac{\pi \sigma \Phi}{4} [d]^2$, i.e. M-Vector $|\vec{M}| \perp |\vec{v}_A|$, \rightleftharpoons , and E-Vector, $\uparrow \downarrow |\vec{E}| \equiv |ZAD| \equiv \frac{\sigma \pi \Phi}{4} [\lambda]^2$.

Figure - 19 - The Electric - Magnetic Field of 3, Conductors Results on 2 -Anti-Parallel-Strands. The Stability of → { ⊕ 4-Space [D A B C]} Regular - Tetrahedron, IN { ⊖ 8-Anti-Space Cube, [DA₁B D₁, C C₁AB₁] }, and The → { ⊕ 8- Space [DA₁BD₁, CC₁AB₁] } Cube, INTO The { ⊖ 16-Anti-Space [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8-9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] } Sphere Cube Vertices. Point [16 \equiv |Z|] consists the Navel-String Gate in {Z-(ΔD,ABC), Δ[T1 T2 T3]} Stationary Bases, In Dual Photon $\vec{v} \left[\frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \vec{v} \cdot [\vec{f}_n + f_n]$, Colours are Still-Sub-Units in Storage → $[\vec{v} \cdot \vec{f}_n]$ ← and exist as Frequencies → Violet, Blue, Green, with their Complementary Yellow, Orange, Red ←

The **Stationary Bases of Atoms** result on the **2-Anti-Parallel-Strands** . These 2-Strands are the **Pins & Sockets** of Atoms , i.e. for Atoms , **Electric – field – Strand** is the motion and **Magnetic Field – Strand** is the Storage to this motion , which is thus the **Identity of Atoms –Actions** . With these two Elements is done , **The Programming of Atoms Bonding** .

The **Linear Relation** of the Three Dimensional **Master-Vector-Meters**

Figure -20- : The Three Master-Vector-Meters in **One Linear-Vector** , for E-geometry Quantization :

Master-meter is the **linear relation** of the Ratio , (*continuous analogy*) of **Geometrical magnitudes** , of all Spaces and Anti-spaces in **Any monad** . This is so because of the , Extrema - Ratio - Meters .

Saying **master-meters** , we mean That the Ratio of Two or Three Geometrical magnitudes , is such that they have a **linear relation** (*continuous analogy*) **in all Spaces** , in **One in Two in Three Dimensions** , as this happens to the Compatible Coordinate Systems as these are the Rectangular [x,y,z] , [i,j,k] , the Cylindrical and Spherical-Polar .

The Position and the **Distance of Points can be then calculated between The Points** , and thus to **Perform independent Operations** (Divergence , Gradient , Curl , Laplacian) on Points Only . This Property issues on material Points and monads . This is permitted because , Space is Quaternion and is composed of Stationary Quantities , The Position $\vec{r}(t)$ and The Kinematic Quantities as , the Velocity $\rightarrow \vec{v} = dr/dt$ and acceleration $\rightarrow \vec{a} = d\vec{v}/dt = d^2r / dt^2$. **Kinematic Quantities** are also The tiny Energy volume caves (*the cycloid length λ ,*) , **The Space of velocity \vec{v} , and acceleration \vec{a} , consist in gravity's field The infinite Energy Dipole Tanks in where Energy \equiv motion , is conserved) .**

In this way all Operations on Edge Points are Possible and applicable . The same to Tetrahedron-Cube.

Since Color \equiv Frequency \equiv motion , a disturbance = vibration that carries Energy and travels from One Point of Conductor to the other therefore the **3-Conductors - Case** , DA , DB , DC , with Base Triangle ABC and the **Sub-Units** , AT_1 , BT_2 , CT_3 - AT_3 , CT_2 , BT_1 , form **The Still Ratio = 1** of Diagonals as the Topological Tetrahedron on where , **Sub -Units -Vectors** in surfaces DAB , DBC , DCA , consist the Physical-colors as $AT_1 \equiv$ Violet , $BT_2 \equiv$ Blue , $CT_3 \equiv$ Green \leftrightarrow $AT_3 \equiv$ Yellow , $CT_2 \equiv$ Orange , $BT_1 \equiv$ Red , and where AT_1 , AT_3 - BT_2 , BT_1 - CT_3 , CT_2 , are the Complementary - Spectral colors , with White Resultant Vector $\vec{D}_{ZM} \uparrow \equiv \vec{D}_{MZ} \downarrow$ to be Anti-Parallel at apex Point D following the Cebas-Equilibrium - Ratio . This is a very important application on **Color-Vector-Monads** because the Electromagnetic-Spectrum is the result of Electric and Magnetic fields forces interactions . Fig-19

Color \equiv Frequency \equiv motion , a Pulse = a vibration . A dye Laser excited by Pulses from a flash-lamp Decolorizes an Pigmented lesion from the Complementary-Spectral colors , i.e. Yellow from Violet , Blue from Red and Green , from Orange . The Visual Pathways , the tracks , in human **Brain Cortex** originate from , **Cortex \equiv Object** , that specularly reflect light of different wavelengths with different efficiencies and , when **Cortex Scatter all wavelengths then appear White** and when impinging light is **Partly Absorbed then the rest look Black** . Above Procedure dependents for the Molecules .

Motion is transformed to Stress, $\sigma \equiv \frac{2\pi r}{f\Phi} \equiv [\oplus \rightarrow \ominus]$, and for Violet to Red Color is σ_V, σ_R .

2.. The System of Stresses and Velocities $\{(O_T, r_T) \text{ circle} + \Delta [T_1 T_2 T_3]\}$ Follows all above and The Winding of Nucleotide-Bases Produces an, -, Torque-Vector on Phosphate **Carbon-BH**, (e, f) applied on (O_T, r_T) circle and then Anti-Parallel and Complementary- EM-Vectors $+ f_f = [\frac{2.B}{\pi^2 r^4}]$

From $E_K + E_P = 2.E_n = \sigma \cdot \Phi = \sigma \cdot \left\{ \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right\} = \sigma \cdot \{ 1,6180339, -0,6180339 \} = \sigma \cdot \{ e^+, e^- \}$, and since $E_n = \sigma \cdot \Phi / 2$ then, $e^- = 1,6180339 / 2 = 0,8090169$, $e^+ = + 0,6180339 \rightleftharpoons eV$.

From [94], 3i-The Equilibrium of Orbital Bonding, The Stresses σ , occupy Minimum and Maximum because is related to an frequency and velocity as such is the frequency equation,

$$f_{ph} = \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \frac{\sigma + \sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma[1+\Phi]}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma[\Phi]^2}{2\pi r}, \text{ or } \sigma \equiv \frac{f_{ph} \cdot 2\pi \cdot r}{\Phi^2} \equiv \frac{w \cdot r}{\Phi^2} \equiv \frac{v}{\Phi^2} \equiv \bar{c} \cdot \frac{1}{\Phi^2}, \text{ and is}$$

The-Stress-Way of Photon-Storages $\bar{f}_N = \sigma / 2\pi r$, and **Photon-Information** $f_n = \sigma \Phi / 2\pi r$.

The Conservation of Energy IN Chemistry-Mechanism and Active Forces :

A.. Nature occupies The Glucose-Oxide Activity in, $H_2 O_2 \equiv O^4 H^2 = O^4 \times H^2 = O^3 H^0$
 $= S \frac{3}{3} \bar{E} \rightarrow ST_3^3 = 3+0$, X. Inn $\frac{3}{3} \bar{E} = 3+0 = 6/2$, X. Out $\frac{Halve\ 6=3\bar{E} \rightarrow 3+0 \rightarrow \text{Electric - Vectors}}{Halve\ 6=3\bar{M} \rightarrow 3+0 \rightarrow \text{Magnetic - Vectors}}$, which

Still - Halves Energies at $(+)$ Positions $O^3 H^0 = \times = \left[\oplus \frac{3}{2} + \ominus \frac{3}{2} \right]$, $O^1 H^0$ to $(-)$ Positions $\}$

Chemistry with the Infinite Reactions uses, The Conservation of Energy as Two-Still-Halves in Oxygen and Hydrogen are, $O^3 H^0 \rightarrow \pm \leftarrow H^1 O^2 = TS \frac{6}{6} = \frac{3+3}{3}$, Mould $M_{1,2,4,8}$.

To find the Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors of a multi-DOF System, Iteration method of motion is formulated by either the Flexibility Matrix, [a], or Stiffness Matrix, $[K^{-1}]$ and Dynamic Matrix \bar{A} needed for Symmetry. The equation of the Normal Mode Vibration is $\rightarrow \bar{A} X = \bar{\lambda} \cdot X \leftarrow (1)$ where
 $\rightarrow \bar{A} = [a] [m] = K^{-1} M$ and $\bar{\lambda} = \frac{1}{w^2} \leftarrow (2)$

Figure - 21- The Hydrogen – Oxygen Bonding Still at Halve \pm Energy Conservation :

Chemistry with the Infinite Reactions uses , The **Glucose-Oxide** of Oxygen and Hydrogen as the **Mechanism for Conservation of Energy** as $H_2 O_2 \equiv O_4^4 H_2^2 = O_4^4 \times H_2^2 = O_4^{-1-2} H_2^{2-2} = O_1^3 H_2^0 = ES \frac{3E}{3M} \rightarrow SN \frac{3e^+ E}{3e^- M} \rightarrow TS \frac{6-1-2=3}{6-1-2=3}$, $O_1^3 H_2^0 \rightarrow \pm \leftarrow H_0^2 O_0^2$ Mould $M_{1,2,4,8}$ Stiffness $k_O = 1e^+$, $k_H = 2e^+$, and $ES \frac{3}{3} = 3.[e^+ = 0,8090169] = 2,427 eV = 228 kJ/mol$.

From Iteration-Mechanics $8,56468 \begin{bmatrix} 0,8833 \\ 1,0000 \end{bmatrix} = \bar{\lambda} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} X1 \\ X2 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{k}{w^2 \cdot m} \begin{bmatrix} 0,8833 \\ 1,0000 \end{bmatrix}$ so $\lambda_1 = 8,56468$ is the Lowest

Mode-Frequency and $w_1 = \sqrt{\frac{k}{8,56468 \cdot m}} = \sqrt{\frac{2+2=4-1=3}{8,56468 \cdot 10^{-30}}} = \sqrt{\frac{0,3849407 \cdot 10^{30}}{1}} = 0,6204358 \cdot 10^{15} H$ with

mode $\begin{bmatrix} 0,8833 \\ 1,0000 \end{bmatrix}$, **Natural frequency** $f_1 = 0,6204358 \cdot 10^{15} H / 2\pi = 0,987483 \cdot 10^{14} Hz$, into Infra -

Red Color of Wavelength $\lambda = 2000-4000$ (nm), The **Resonance frequency** $f_R = 0,987483 \cdot 10^{14} H$ and Energy $E = 4,0838392 eV$, Related Stress on Atoms is $\sigma_{HOC} = \sigma_{INF} = 1,03201986 \cdot 10^{-7} Kg / [nm]^2$.

i.e. when the Frequency w_1 is calculated, then all other energy-elements are defined.

Energy of any State is $E = \frac{13,6}{n^2} eV$, where the first excited-State $n = 3$ is $E = 3,4 eV$. Moving from the 4th to the 2nd e-Level then $E = [13,6/4^2 - 13,6/2^2] = -0,85 + 3,40 = 2,55 eV$.

For Photon $E = 0 - (13,6/2^2) = 3,4 eV$. From Energy and wavelength relation $E = hf = \frac{h}{T} = \frac{h}{l/c} = \frac{hc}{l}$,

and $l = \frac{hc}{E} = \frac{6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34} \cdot 2,9979 \cdot 10^8 \cdot m/s}{3,4 eV} = \frac{6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34} \cdot 2,9979 \cdot 10^8 \cdot m/s}{4,08 \cdot 10^{-19} J} = 4,87 \cdot 10^{-7} m = 487 nm$.

The Linear Motion $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$ of Breakage $[\pm \bar{c} \cdot s^2_m]$ in cave $\{M\text{-Point} = d s_m = e^{i \cdot (\frac{N\pi}{2})} b = 10^{-N} = \pm \infty m\}$ as velocity, $v = w r = 2\pi r \cdot f = \sigma \Phi$, in the Great and Small circles of Glue-Bond rotation, creates the

Three-States of frequencies $f_{\pm 1/2} = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{8\pi r}$, $f_{\pm 1} = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r}$, $f_{\pm 1/2} = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{8\pi r} = \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r}$ and energy

$E = h f_m$, because the **Angular-Momentum** $\bar{B} = \frac{2L}{w} = \frac{2L}{2\pi f} = [\frac{2L}{2\pi}] \cdot [\frac{1}{f}] = \frac{\text{Constant}}{2\pi} [\frac{1}{f_m}] = \text{SPIN}$ [70]

The **Sphere - Cube - Tetrahedron Structure of Atoms** In Sphere Center -O - \equiv **The Core**, allows **The Stability** of the System, Per-Two electrons in Dipole Positions, $1 \leftrightarrow 6, 2 \leftrightarrow 5, 3 \leftrightarrow 8, 4 \leftrightarrow 7$, consisting The Positive Dipole- $[\overline{BH}]$, to be able to move \rightarrow Into-In- Outside it \leftarrow and thus allow the Atoms to Bond as this in Energy levels. *The Cube-Structure of Atoms and Orbits in the Out-Sphere* formulates + $[\overline{BH}]$ to those **Dipole Positions which lack of one electron** and so can **PLUG - In the LOOP** of the Others. Since $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] \equiv 0$ then the Atoms with Zero Stable State are as,

$\textcircled{0} \equiv H^+ \equiv \oplus \equiv \vec{1} = \text{Hydrogen Bracket-Hook } \overline{BH} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \equiv \text{The Zero Stable-State-Group.}$

Since **The Stationary Bases of Atoms** result on the **2-Anti-Parallel -Strands**. These 2-Strands are the **Pins & Sockets** of Atoms. i.e. for Atoms, **Electric - field - Strand** is the motion and **Magnetic Field - Strand** is the Storage to this motion, which is thus the **Identity and Actions of Atoms**. With these two Elements is done, **The Programming of Atoms Bonding**.

5d... The Actions in Atoms-Bonding and Applications in Chemistry & The Conservation of Energy in Caves and in Atoms Compounds.

Preliminaries - Summary : [106]

One of the most important concept in Geometry is, **distance**, which is the Quanta in geometry, while in Material-Geometry the Composition of Opposite, **the Material-Point**, $[\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$ which is the Quanta in **Chemistry and Physics**. *As in Algebra* Zero ,0, is the **Master-key** number for all Positive and Negative numbers and this because their sum and multiplication becomes zero, *and the same* on any coordinate-System where \pm axes pass from zero, The Rolling of Positive \oplus , constituent on the Negative \ominus , constituent, in PNS Space $\{ \text{Planck-Cave } L_P \equiv e^{i \cdot (-5\pi/2)} \cdot 10 = 10^{-34} m < \text{PNS-Space} <$

Gravity Space = 10^{-62} m } creates the Neutral Material Point , $\rightarrow [Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = D] \equiv$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{A -} \\ \uparrow Z + \left[\oplus \frac{\text{::} \cup}{2} + \ominus \frac{\text{::} \cup}{2} \right] D \end{array} \right\} \equiv \left\{ \pm [\otimes] \frac{-\oplus/2}{+\ominus/2} + \downarrow \leftrightarrow \uparrow \right\} \leftarrow \text{which } \textit{Equilibrium by Division} .$$

The Angular-Momentum is identical with *Spin* and consists the *First-Discrete-Energy-Monad* which occupies *Discrete Value and Direction*, in contradiction to the Point which is Nothing *Dimensionless and without any Direction* , i.e. **Material Point** , $[Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = D]$ is **Electromagnetic-Wave** [15]

Atoms are consisted of a **Hydrogens - Heap** , which vibrates and equilibrium , at the Dynamic Mode-Shapes following The Stationary **In Ex-Sphere \rightarrow Cube \rightarrow Tetrahedron \rightarrow In-Sphere** , Geometrical construction . Since vibration means the frequencies in each Atom or and its Compound therefore , thus they consist the *Electromagnetic Waves* . The Interactions of any two or more Energy Systems with known Status use the Markos “ **Electronic - Program** ” i.e. **{ The Carrier – Modulating –Modulated– Demodulation - Analyzer Waves Process }** for their Energy - Spectrum Waveform .

Electromagnetic Signals may be used to Transmit Information very quickly and over great distances . Informations are encoded on Atoms - Signals using , Amplitude and Frequency modulation , and reviewed in the Program . The Process of retrieving the information from encoded Signals is detected by the **Antidotes** .This simple Program-Process allows the User to detect any ACTION of the, *Initial Signal* , through the Modulating–Modulated – Demotulated Process , to the *Final and wish Repaired Signal* . The Spectrum Analyzer is detected in all Steps . An Application of the method is used on the CELLS which consist themselves a Complete–Energy-Monad .

From Article [111] - The Interactions :

- 1... The Resonance of 2 frequencies A , B occurs , when their Natural-frequencies coincide , i.e. it is valid $A = B$.
- 2... The two frequencies A , B , **are coupled** , when a Third frequency C is added so that A , B , are in Resonance , i.e. it is valid vibrations $A + C = B + C$.
- 3... **When** [A] is an carrier wave , [B] is the modulating wave , [M] = [A] + [B] is the modulated wave , [DM] is the demodulated wave , [AN] is the Antidote , [HOS] is the Healthy Organ –System , [COS] is the Cancerous Ogan–System , **Then** for the coupled frequencies it is valid $\rightarrow [M] + [AN] = [HOS]$ & also $[M] + [AN] = [COS]$ \leftarrow **That is** , the Antidotes , [AN] are those frequencies as the above [C] that are added **so that** [A] , [B] **are in Resonance with them** .
- 4...**The Uncoupled values are inside of the Coupled Natural frequencies by small** Amounts .The multitude of numbers of the uncoupled signaling Systems are placed to the **Sidebands** as this is the **Athwart Energy Vibration Spectrum**.
- 5...**The Electron`s Nutation** in Hydrogen cave Produces Energy due to g effect , as minimum frequency $f_n \equiv 2,8398447 \cdot 10^{10}$ H , and thus exists in all Atoms . This Energy of Hydrogen-Cave becomes an **Electrical -Magnetic Conductor** which is

The Pin and Plug of atoms . Pins entering Into the other Atom-Sockets consist the Orbit-

Bracket-Hooks , i.e. are the Hands of Atoms-Hooks . Placing their Pins into the other Atoms Drains = Holes = Plugs , is done that what we say Bonding.

Hydrogen-Cave In -Out Universe occupies mass m_H velocity \vec{c} and Power P_H .

6...Placing \Rightarrow $[M] = [A] + [B] \rightarrow$ The Modulated Wave .

$[AN] = [C] \rightarrow$ The Antidote ,

$[M] + [AN] = [ICS] \rightarrow$ **IS in Resonance to Initial Chemical - Synthesis**

$[M] + [AN] = [RCS] \rightarrow$ **IS in Resonance to Right Chemical - Synthesis**

APPLICATION OF PROGRAM TO NOVARTIS – DRUGS AND THE NEW-DETECTED FROM THE “ PROGRAM ”.

The detailed Electronic Program is in article [106]

While all the after , are the Applications of this .

The Breast Cancer :

[A] = THE INITIAL HEALTHY - BREAST CHEMICAL COMPOSITION .

Sodium $[Na] = 686 \text{ mg / kg}$

Sulfur $[S] = 385 \text{ mg / kg}$

Potassium $[K] = 194 \text{ mg / kg}$

Phosphorus $[P] = 201 \text{ mg / kg}$

Calcium $[Ca] = 77 \text{ mg / kg}$

Magnesium $[Mg] = 18 \text{ mg / kg}$

Iron $[Fe] = 13 \text{ mg / kg}$

Zink $[Zn] = 3 \text{ mg / kg}$

Copper $[Cu] = 1 \text{ mg / kg}$

[B] = THE MODULATED CANCEROUS - BREAST C - C .

Iron $[Fe] = 123 \text{ mg / kg}$

Zink $[Zn] = 35 \text{ mg / kg}$

Silicon $[Si] = 11 \text{ mg / kg}$

Copper $[Cu] = 4 \text{ mg / kg}$

Titanium $[Ti] = 6 \text{ mg / kg}$

Strontium $[Sr] = 1,4 \text{ mg / kg}$

Manganese $[Mn] = 0,5 \text{ mg / kg}$

Barium $[Ba] = 0,4 \text{ mg / kg}$

 $[M] = [A] + [B] \rightarrow$ **The Modulated Wave .**

$[AN] = [C] \rightarrow$ **The Antidotes ,**

$[M] + [AN] = [LNS] \rightarrow$ **IS in Resonance to Cancerous Chemical Composition ,**

THE FINAL Healthy BREAST Drugs & Antidotes .

The Needed Demodulated Efficiency $DE = 101,545.10^{15}Hz$

- 1., Novartis Drug – Piz ray = [C29 H26 Cl F N4 O4 S]x30,30 → $DE = 103,035.10^{15}Hz$
 - 2., Novartis Drug – Ry dapt = [C13 H23 Cl N4 O3 S]x44,25 → $DE = 108,134.10^{15}Hz$
 - 3., Novartis Drug – Ty kerb = [C29 H26 Cl F N4 O4 S]x21,60 → $DE = 101,728.10^{15}Hz$
 - 4., Novartis Drug – Afinitor = [C53 H83 N O14] x 12,00 → $DE = 101,971.10^{15}Hz$
 - 5., Novartis Drug –Lutathera = [C65 H87 Lu N14 O19 S2]x8,85→ $DE = 108,134.10^{15}Hz$
 - 6., Novartis Drug –Pluvicto = [C49 H68 Lu N9 O16] x 22,75 → $DE = 105,189.10^{15}Hz$
 - 7., Novartis Drug –Scemblix = [C20 H18 Cl F2 N5 O3] x29,10 → $DE = 101,644.10^{15}Hz$
 - 8., Novartis Drug –Tasigna = [C28 H22 F3 N7 O] x22,25 → $DE = 101,666.10^{15}Hz$
-
- 9.. 1-NEW – Compound = [C47 H51 N O14] x13,80 → $DE = 101,681.10^{15}Hz$
 - 10.. 2-NEW – Compound = [N2 Cl2 Pt H6] x 969 → $DE = 101,573.10^{15}Hz$
 - 11.. 3-NEW – Compound = [N3 C4 Pt H8] x 544 → $DE = 101,619.10^{15}Hz$
-

Modification of the inadequate Drug Azerra of Lymphacetic Leukemia , for Chemotherapy

- 12..Novartis–Arzerra = [C6480 H10022 N1742 O2020 S44] → $DE = 244,009.10^{15}Hz$
- 13..**Modified– Compound** = [C592 H992 N169 O186 S3] → $DE = 101,548.10^{15}Hz$

THE FINAL Healthy PROSTATE Drugs & Antidotes .

The Needed Demodulated Efficiency $DE = 95,758.10^{15}Hz$

- 1., Novartis Drug – Locametz = [C44 H59 Ga N6 O17] x 4,95 → $DE = 95,857.10^{15}Hz$
 - 2., Novartis Drug –Tetraxetan = [C30 H47 N7 O10 S] x 6,6 → $DE = 95,810.10^{15}Hz$
 - 3., Novartis Drug –Vipivotide = [C49 H71 Lu N9 O16] x 4,1 → $DE = 95,934.10^{15}Hz$
 - 4., Novartis Drug – Kisgall = [C23 H30 N8 O11 S] x 10,5 → $DE = 95,810.10^{15}Hz$
 - 5., Novartis Drug – Lutetium = [C49 H68 Lu177 N9 O16]x 3 → $DE = 96,075.10^{15}Hz$
 - 6., Novartis Drug – Pluvicto = [C49 H71 N9 O16] x 4 → $DE = 96,234.10^{15}Hz$
-
- 7.. 1-NEW – Compound = [Ca12 Zn7 Na23 Mg4] x 13,00 → $DE = 96,018.10^{15}Hz$
 - 8.. 2-NEW – Compound = [Si32 Zn8 Na25 S13] x 5,35 → $DE = 95,803.10^{15}Hz$
 - 9.. 3-NEW – Compound = [C148 H222 O40 S2] x 2,00 → $DE = 96,214.10^{15}Hz$

NOTES :

- a.. In the first Page are the **Antidotes` – Data** with their Chemical Composition.
- b.. In the second Page are the Results from the **Antidotes - Actions E-Spectrum**.
- c.. In the third Page are the Results from **LC -Antidotes – Chemical - Coupling** .

Healthy Breast Chemical Composition (Dry Mass Basis)

2. Elemental Construction (By Weight)

At a molecular level, healthy breast tissue consists of the same basic organic elements found in human soft tissue, but in specific proportions that change with the ratio of fat to glandular tissue:

- **Oxygen (O):** ~33% – 59% (Decreases as fat content increases)
- **Carbon (C):** ~27% – 53% (Increases significantly in fatty breasts)
- **Hydrogen (H):** ~10% – 11%
- **Nitrogen (N):** ~2% – 3%
- **Phosphorus (P):** ~0.2% – 0.4%

3. Trace Chemical Elements

Healthy breast tissue also contains essential minerals and trace elements. These concentrations are typically measured in **mg/kg (ppm) of dry tissue**:

- **Sodium (Na):** ~686 mg/kg
- **Sulfur (S):** ~385 mg/kg
- **Potassium (K):** ~194 mg/kg
- **Phosphorus (P):** ~201 mg/kg
- **Calcium (Ca):** ~77 mg/kg
- **Magnesium (Mg):** ~18 mg/kg
- **Iron (Fe):** ~13 mg/kg
- **Zinc (Zn):** ~3 mg/kg
- **Copper (Cu):** ~1 mg/kg

4. Key Metabolites and Markers

Advanced imaging like 2D COSY NMR identifies specific chemical species that maintain healthy tissue function:

- **Cholesterol:** Found in higher concentrations in denser healthy tissue.
- **Choline & Phosphocholine:** Indicators of healthy cell membrane turnover.
- **Taurine & Myo-inositol:** Small molecules involved in osmoregulation and cell signaling.

Cancerous Breast Chemical Composition (Dry Mass Basis)

Major Mineral Constituents

- Sodium (Na) : $6,262 \pm 2,771$ mg/kg
- Sulphur (S) : $4,599 \pm 1,797$ mg/kg
- Potassium (K) : $4,347 \pm 2,284$ mg/kg
- Phosphorus (P) : $3,867 \pm 2,230$ mg/kg
- Calcium (Ca) : 650 ± 856 mg/kg
- Magnesium (Mg) : 302 ± 148 mg/kg

Trace Elements and Heavy Metals

- Iron (Fe) : 123 ± 93 mg/kg
- Zinc (Zn) : 34.2 ± 18.3 mg/kg
- Silicon (Si) : 10.2 ± 31.1 mg/kg
- Aluminum (Al) : 8.88 ± 12.0 mg/kg
- Copper (Cu) : 3.90 ± 2.88 mg/kg
- Titanium (Ti) : 4.55 ± 7.18 mg/kg
- Strontium (Sr) : 1.37 ± 1.31 mg/kg
- Manganese (Mn) : 0.47 ± 0.27 mg/kg
- Barium (Ba) : 0.42 ± 0.94 mg/kg

Key Comparisons to Normal Tissue

Studies using **Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)** have noted that nearly all major trace elements (including Zn, Cu, Mn, Co, and Se) are **elevated** in malignant tissue, while others like Lead (Pb) and Antimony (Sb) may show lower levels relative to healthy glands. These shifts are often attributed to increased cellular metabolic activity and altered blood supply within the tumor microenvironment.

Would you like a similar breakdown of **macromolecules** like proteins and lipids, or do you need the data for **wet weight** instead of dry tissue?

Compound

Description CANCEROUS - BREAST = [123Fe 34Zn 10Si 9Al 4Cu 5Ti 1Sr 1Mn 1Ba] // +++ \\
 Novaltis -D- Piz ray = [C29 H26 Cl F N4 O4 S] Oncology x 30.3

Formula Fe₁₂₃Zn₃₄Si₁₀Al₉Cu₄Ti₅SrMnBaC₅₇₅H₆₆₆F₉₀N₁₅₁O₆₀S₃₀

Total Number of Elements 1760

Stiffness Factor 1463963864

Properties

#	Number	Symbol	Mass	Total Mass	Pins	Sockets	Bonded	Unbonded
1	575	C	12	6900	2300	2300		
2	123	Fe	56	6888	123	123		
3	34	Zn	65	2210	102	102		
4	151	N	14	2114	453	453		
5	90	F	19	1710	90	90		
6	60	O	16	960	120	120		
7	30	S	32	960	60	60		
8	666	H	1	666	666	666		
9	10	Si	28	280	40	40		
10	4	Cu	64	256	8	8		
11	9	Al	27	243	27	27		
12	5	Ti	48	240	20	20		
13	1	Ba	137	137	2	2		
14	1	Sr	88	88	2	2		
15	1	Mn	55	55	1	1		

Bond - Mode

230	123	102	453	90	120	60	666	40	8	27	20	2
C ⁰	Fe	Zn	N	F	O	S	H	Si	Cu	Al	Ti	Ba
230	123	102	453	90	120	60	666	40	8	27	20	2
0												

Matrices

Mass Matrix

m x	6900	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	6888	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	151	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	2210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	2114	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	666	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	1710	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	960	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Novaltis -D- Piz ray = [C29 H26 Cl F N4 O4 S] Oncology x 30.3

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	78.564716×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	8.2851×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	12.728×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.236003×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5181×10^{-20} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.620112×10^{-10} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$5113.923062 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	6.5091×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	423.69×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	168.9523 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$650.918549 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1999×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	121.313975 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-252.768343 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0067 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.464648×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	17.060562 \AA

Compound

Description CANCEROUS - BREAST = [123Fe 34Zn 10Si 9Al 4Cu 5Ti 1Sr 1Mn 1Ba] // +++ \
Novaltis -D- Ry dapt = [C13 H23 Cl N4 O3 S] Oncology x 44.25

Formula Fe₁₂₃Zn₃₄Si₁₀Al₉Cu₄Ti₅SrMnBaC₅₇₅H₁₀₁₇C₄₄N₁₇₇O₁₃₂S₄₄

Total Number of Elements 2177

Stiffness Factor 1941776280

Properties

#	Number	Symbol	Mass	Total Mass	Pins	Sockets	Bonded	Unbonded
1	575	C	12	6900	2300	2300		
2	123	Fe	56	6888	123	123		
3	177	N	14	2478	531	531		
4	34	Zn	65	2210	102	102		
5	132	O	16	2112	264	264		
6	44	Cl	35	1540	44	44		
7	44	S	32	1408	88	88		
8	1017	H	1	1017	1017	1017		
9	10	Si	28	280	40	40		
10	4	Cu	64	256	8	8		
11	9	Al	27	243	27	27		
12	5	Ti	48	240	20	20		
13	1	Ba	137	137	2	2		
14	1	Sr	88	88	2	2		
15	1	Mn	55	55	1	1		

Bond - Mode

230	123	531	102	264	44	88	101	40	8	27	20	2
C ⁰	Fe	N	Zn	O	Cl	S	H ⁷	Si	Cu	Al	Ti	Ba
230	123	531	102	264	44	88	101	40	8	27	20	2
0							7					

Matrices

Mass Matrix

m x	6900	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	6888	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	2478	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	2210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	2112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	1017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	2112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1540	0	0	0	0	0

Novaltis -D- Ry dapt = [C13 H23 Cl N4 O3 S] Oncology x 44.25

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	80.736009×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	8.5141×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	12.386×10^{-28} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.195173×10^{-15} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5111×10^{-29} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.534142×10^{-16} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$5549.749717 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	6.8739×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	472.5×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	169.0707 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$687.394605 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1945×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	124.66673 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-259.754103 \times 10^{19}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0048 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.845844×10^{-15} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	17.931791 \AA

Novaltis -D- Tykerb = [C29 H26 Cl F N4 O4 S] Oncology x 21.6

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	$106.132009 \times 10^{15}$ Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	11.192×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	9.4222×10^{-15} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.275726×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.4457×10^{-29} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	0.887784×10^{-19} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$12606.969972 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	11.878×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	1411.0×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	170.2585 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$1187.857471 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1480×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	163.881404 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-341.461327 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0084 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.302043×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	16.688926 Å

Novartis -D- Afinitor = [C53 H83 N O14] Oncology x 12

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	81.981492×10^{16} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	8.6454×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	12.197×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.288382×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5072×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.487882×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$5810.57377 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	7.0876×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	502.34×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	169.1372 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	708.76653×10^{-3} Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1916×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	126.589915 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-263.761228 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0095 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.106369×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	16.241709 \AA

Novartis -D- Lutathera = [C65 H87 Lu N14 O19 S2] Radiology x 8.85

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	84.351989×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	8.8954×10^{-16} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	11.855×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.231608×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5000×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.40543×10^{-16} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$6329.327204 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	7.5034×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	563.02×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	169.261 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$750.347119 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1862×10^{-18} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	130.250266 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$193.288293 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0063 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.595627×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	17.359917 Å

Novartis -D- Pluvicto = [C49 H68 Lu N9 O16] Radiology x 11.75

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	80.279308×10^{18} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	8.4659×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	12.456×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.182603×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5125×10^{-28} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.551646×10^{-13} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$5456.101302 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	6.7963×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	461.91×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	169.046 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$679.639802 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1956×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	123.961525 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-258.284746 \times 10^{18}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0049 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.609864×10^{-16} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	17.392455 \AA

Novartis -D- Scemblix = [C20 H18 Cl F2 N5 O3] Oncology x 29.1

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	$153.613771 \times 10^{15}$ Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	16.199×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	6.5098×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.164705×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.3705×10^{-28} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	0.423779×10^{-19} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$38226.277855 \times 10^{-8}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	24.884×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	6192.4×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	171.8643 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$2488.466866 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1022×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	237.19932 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-494.225657 \times 10^{18}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0041 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.801085×10^{-16} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	17.829492 Å

Novartis -D- Tassigna = [C28 H22 F3 N7 O] Oncology x 22.25

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	74.418051×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	7.8478×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	13.437×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.277678×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5323×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.805691×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$4346.167238 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	5.8402×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	341.08×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	168.7168 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	584.02057×10^{-3} Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.2110×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	114.910994 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-239.427168 \times 10^{19}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.009 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.158989×10^{-12} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	16.361974 \AA

1 - NEW Compound = [C47 H51 N O14] Chemotherapy x 13.8

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	78.048435×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	8.2306×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	12.812×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{zL}	=	0.29377×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5198×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.641616×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$5013.767175 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	6.4239×10^{-29} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	412.66×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	168.9236 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$642.391762 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.2012×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	120.516772 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	-251.1073×10^{10} Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0095 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.160615×10^{-16} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	16.365689 Å

2 - NEW Compound = [N2 Cl2 Pt H6] Chemotherapy x 989

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	97.519646×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	10.284×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	10.254×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.045846×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.4650×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.051516×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$9780.203943 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	10.028×10^{-25} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	1005.7×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	169.8909 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$1002.89576 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1610×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	150.582813 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-313.752542 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0001 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	$20.984848 \times 10^{-17}$ m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	47.961175 A°

Compound

Description CANCEROUS - BREAST = [123Fe 34Zn 10Si 9Al 4Cu 5Ti 1Sr 1Mn 1Ba] // +++ \ 3-
 \exists NEW Compound = [N3 C4 Pt H8] Chemotherapy x 544

Formula $Fe_{123}Zn_{34}Si_{10}Al_9Cu_4Ti_5SrMnBaN_{1632}C_{2176}Pt_{544}H_{4352}$

Total Number of Elements 8892

Stiffness Factor 48176640

Properties

#	Number	Symbol	Mass	Total Mass	Pins	Sockets	Bonded	Unbonded
1	544	Pt	195	106080	544	544		
2	2176	C	12	26112	8704	8704		
3	1632	N	14	22848	4896	4896		
4	123	Fe	56	6888	123	123		
5	4352	H	1	4352	4352	4352		
6	34	Zn	65	2210	102	102		
7	10	Si	28	280	40	40		
8	4	Cu	64	256	8	8		
9	9	Al	27	243	27	27		
10	5	Ti	48	240	20	20		
11	1	Ba	137	137	2	2		
12	1	Sr	88	88	2	2		
13	1	Mn	55	55	1	1		

Bond - Mode

544	870	489	123	435	102	40	8	27	20	2	2	1
Pt	C ⁴	N ⁶	Fe	H ²	Zn	Si	Cu	Al	Ti	Ba	Sr	Mn
544	870 4	489 6	123	435 2	102	40	8	27	20	2	2	1

Matrices

Mass Matrix

m ×													
106080	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	26112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	22848	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	6888	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	4352	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	2210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	280	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	256	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	243	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	240	0	0	0	0

3- NEW Compound = [N3 C4 Pt H8] Chemotherapy x 544

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	$104.239945 \times 10^{18}$ Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	10.992×10^{-16} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	9.5932×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.053075×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.4498×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	0.920305×10^{-18} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$11944.668086 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	11.458×10^{-29} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	1313.0×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	170.1803 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$1145.882038 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1506×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	160.959815 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-335.373939 \times 10^{17}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.000° Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	$17.078072 \times 10^{-18}$ m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	39.032182 \AA

MODIFIED Arzerra = [C592 H992 N169 O186 S3] - Lymphocytic Leukemia

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	82.563044×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	8.7067×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	12.111×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.369367×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.5054×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	1.466995×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$5935.10832 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	7.1885×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	516.75×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	169.1679 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$718.857742 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.1902×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	127.487905 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-265.632269 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0103 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	7.506291×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	17.155737 A°

Healthy Prostate Chemical Composition (Dry Mass Basis)

The prostate gland consists of roughly 83% water, with the remaining solids containing inorganic elements and organic molecules. The following are key elements found in healthy prostate tissue, typically measured on a dry mass basis:

- **Potassium (K):** ~11,200 mg/kg
- **Sodium (Na):** ~11,100 mg/kg
- **Calcium (Ca):** ~2,280 mg/kg (can range widely)
- **Magnesium (Mg):** ~1,118 mg/kg
- **Zinc (Zn):** ~1,000 mg/kg (significantly higher than other organs)
- **Bromine (Br):** ~32.9 mg/kg
- **Iron (Fe):** ~111 mg/kg
- **Rubidium (Rb):** ~12.7 mg/kg
- **Selenium (Se):** ~0.7 mg/kg
- **Chromium (Cr):** ~0.53 mg/kg

Note: These figures are medians derived from studies of healthy, non-hyperplastic adult male prostate tissues.

"Healthy Analogy" of Essential Elements

In a healthy state, the prostate maintains a precise balance of elements to prevent cell overgrowth (prostatitis/BPH). The "healthy analogy" of the prostate is a tightly regulated **Citrate-Zinc-Enzyme Engine**.

- **Zinc (The Governor):** In a healthy prostate, zinc concentration is high (10x higher than other tissues). Its role is to act as a governor on the "engine," inhibiting mitochondrial aconitase and preventing the oxidation of citrate, allowing it to accumulate.
- **Potassium/Sodium (The Osmotic Balancers):** High concentrations of K and Na maintain the cellular osmotic balance necessary for fluid production.
- **Magnesium (The Enzyme Regulator):** Magnesium supports the enzymatic functions necessary for cellular metabolism.
- **Calcium (The Structural Component):** While essential for structure, excessive buildup of Calcium relative to other minerals is often seen in unhealthy tissues.
- **Antioxidants (Selenium/Vitamins):** These protect the tissue from oxidation and inflammation.

Healthy Prostate Chemical Composition (Dry Mass Basis)

3. Elemental/Mineral Construction (Dry Mass Basis)

The prostate is unique for its extreme concentration of certain elements, which vary significantly by health status. For a healthy (nonhyperplastic) prostate, the approximate mass fractions (mg/kg on a dry mass basis) are:

Element	Approximate Concentration (mg/kg Dry Mass)	Key Function
Potassium (K)	~11,211 – 14,472	Intracellular fluid balance
Sodium (Na)	~11,100 – 11,612	Extracellular fluid balance
Sulfur (S)	~8,787	Component of amino acids/proteins
Phosphorus (P)	~7,907	Essential for DNA and ATP
Calcium (Ca)	~2,030 – 2,280	Signaling and secretion control
Zinc (Zn)	~1,000 – 1,235	Antibacterial and sperm stabilization
Magnesium (Mg)	~1,118 – 1,200	Enzymatic cofactor
Iron (Fe)	~111 – 130	Oxygen transport and cellular enzymes
Bromine (Br)	~30 – 33	Trace biological role
Selenium (Se)	~0.70 – 1.24	Antioxidant protection

4. Biochemical Secretions

The prostate "constructs" a slightly alkaline fluid (pH 7.2–7.8) that accounts for **25–33% of semen volume**. Key chemical ingredients include:

- **Citric Acid:** ~376 mg/dL (1000x higher than blood; inhibits sperm capacitation)
- **Prostate-Specific Antigen (PSA):** 0.5–5 mg/mL (enzyme for semen liquefaction)
- **Spermine:** 50–350 mg/dL (polyamine that aids sperm motility and gives semen its odor)
- **Cholesterol & Phospholipids:** ~186 mg/dL (stabilizes sperm membrane)

Would you like to compare these **healthy percentages** with the chemical shifts observed during **Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH)** or **prostate cancer**?

Elemental Construction of Cancerous Prostate Tissue (Dry Mass)

Major and Trace Element Construction

Malignant transformation disrupts normal mineral balance, notably depleting essential elements like **Zinc** and **Calcium** while accumulating others

Element Group	Chemical Element	Mass Fraction (mg/kg, dry mass)	Status vs. Healthy
Major	Potassium (K)	~8,992	Significantly Lower
Major	Sodium (Na)	~7,784	Significantly Lower
Major	Phosphorus (P)	~6,847	No significant change
Major	Sulfur (S)	~5,230	Significantly Lower
Minor	Calcium (Ca)	~676	Significantly Lower
Minor	Aluminum (Al)	~353	Significantly Higher
Minor	Magnesium (Mg)	~355	Significantly Lower
Minor	Silicon (Si)	~337	Significantly Higher
Trace	Iron (Fe)	~176	Significantly Higher
Trace	Zinc (Zn)	~127	Extremely Lower
Trace	Bromine (Br)	~95	Significantly Higher

Key Chemical Markers

- **The Zinc Drop:** Healthy prostate tissue contains the highest levels of Zinc in the human body. In cancer, these levels drop **10 to 20-fold**, as malignant cells lose the ability to accumulate Zinc to optimize their energy metabolism (oxidizing Citrate instead of secreting it).
- **Diagnostic Ratios:** Researchers use the **Ca·S·Zn test** as a highly accurate indicator; a simultaneous decrease in these three elements is a hallmark of malignancy.
- **Accumulated Elements:** Cancerous tissue often shows elevated levels of **Iron (Fe)**, **Copper (Cu)**, and **Manganese (Mn)**, which may play roles in the initiation or promotion of tumor growth.

Would you like to explore the **molecular construction** (such as specific protein fusions like **TMPRSS2-ERG**) or focus further on **trace element biomarkers** for diagnosis?

Novaltis-D- Locamez = [C44 H59 Ga N6 O17] Cancer x 4.95**LC - Chemical Coupling**

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	46.126833×10^{16} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	4.8643×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	21.679×10^{-16} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.458022×10^{-12} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.6761×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	4.699944×10^{-19} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$1034.981258 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	2.2437×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	50.345×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	166.6395 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$224.377262 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.3405×10^{-18} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	71.225734 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	89.571768×10^{10} Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0352 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	5.359383×10^{-19} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	12.248948 \AA

Novaltis-D- Tetraxetan = [C30 H47 N7 O10 S] Cancer x 6.6

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	47.247873×10^{19} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	4.9825×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	21.164×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.469018×10^{-17} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.6681×10^{-28} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	4.479561×10^{-19} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$1112.290834 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	2.3541×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	55.420×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	166.7438 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$235.416063 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.3324×10^{-18} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	72.956763 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-152.011836 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0391 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	5.219399×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	11.929011 Å

Novaltis-D- Vipivotide = [C49 H71 Lu N9 O16] Cancer x 4.1

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	46.78267×10^{18} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	4.9335×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	21.375×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.400921×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.6714×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	4.569093×10^{-18} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$1079.758341 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	2.3080×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	53.270×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	166.7009 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$230.803062 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.3357×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	72.238429 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-150.515124 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0308 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	5.362645×10^{-19} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	12.256403 Å

Novaltis-D= Kisqali = [C23 H30 N8 O1] x 10.5

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	42.515835×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	4.4835×10^{-16} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	23.520×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.477831×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.7043×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-18} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	5.532209×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$810.445275 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	1.9062×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	36.336×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	166.2855 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$190.621983 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.3694×10^{-10} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	65.64989 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-136.787323 \times 10^{14}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0399 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	5.216721×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	11.922891 \AA

Novaltis-D= Lutetium = [C49 H68 Lu177 N9 O16] x 3

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	32.060312×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	3.3809×10^{-18} J
LC -Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	31.191×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.518418×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.8110×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	9.728918×10^{-19} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	347.51598×10^{-6} Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	1.0839×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	11.749×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	165.0597 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$108.394449 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.4899×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	49.505224 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-103.148491 \times 10^{11}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.002 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	$14.424448 \times 10^{-19}$ m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	32.967286 \AA

Novaltis-D= Pluvicto = [C49 H71 N9 O16] x 4

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	45.756861×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	4.8253×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	21.854×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.37144×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.6789×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-18} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	4.776256×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$1010.276464 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	2.2079×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	48.749×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	166.6046 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$220.792345 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.3432×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	70.654449 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-147.214762 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0338 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	5.06742×10^{-10} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	11.581662 \AA

1 - NEW Compound = [12Ca 7Zn 23Na 4Mg] x 13

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	27.945007×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	2.9469×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	35.784×10^{-18} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.20429×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.8687×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	$12.805353 \times 10^{-19}$ Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	230.13582×10^{-6} Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	0.8235×10^{-29} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	6.7820×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	164.463 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	82.35311×10^{-3} Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.5621×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	43.150667 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-89.908212 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0038 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	8.589594×10^{-12} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	19.631643 \AA

2 - NEW Compound = [32Si 8Zn 25Na 13S] x 5.35

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	40.453357×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	4.2660×10^{-16} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	24.719×10^{-16} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{zL}	=	0.174968×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.7220×10^{-26} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	6.110699×10^{-16} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$698.128326 \times 10^{-6}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	1.7257×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	29.782×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	166.0695 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$172.576117 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.3882×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	62.46516 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	76.628735×10^{19} Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0052 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	$7.365^{\cdot}84 \times 10^{-19}$ m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	16.833234 A ⁹

Compound

Description: CANCERED-Prostatis = [K899 Na778 P685 S523 Ca68 Mg36 Zn13 Fe18 Al35 C296 H444 O80 S523 S4] // ++
 + \ \ 3 - NEW Compound = [C148 H222 O40 S2] Anti - Cancer x 2,
 Formula: $K_{899}Na_{778}P_{685}Ca_{68}Mg_{36}Zn_{13}Fe_{18}Al_{35}C_{296}H_{444}O_{80}S_{523}S_4$
 Total Number of Elements: 3879
 Stiffness Factor: 961616352

Properties

#	Number	Symbol	Mass	Total Mass	Pins	Sockets	Bonded	Unbonded
1	899	K	39	35061	899	899		
2	685	P	31	21235	2055	2055		
3	778	Na	23	17894	778	778		
4	523	S	32	16736	1046	1046		
5	296	C	12	3552	1184	1184		
6	68	Ca	40	2720	136	136		
7	80	O	16	1280	160	160		
8	18	Fe	56	1008	18	18		
9	35	Al	27	945	105	105		
10	36	Mg	24	864	72	72		
11	13	Zn	65	845	39	39		
12	444	H	1	444	444	444		
13	4	S	32	128	8	8		

Bond - Mode

899	205	778	104	118	136	160	18	105	72	39	444	8
K	P ⁵	Na	S ⁶	C ⁴	Ca	O	Fe	Al	Mg	Zn	H	S
899	205	778	104	118	136	160	18	105	72	39	444	8
	5		6	4								

Matrices

Mass Matrix

m x	35061	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	685	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	21235	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	523	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	17894	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	68	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	16736	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	3552	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	2720	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	1280	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1008	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	945	0	0	0	0

3 - NEW Compound = [C148 H222 O40 S2] Anti - Cancer x 2

LC - Chemical Coupling

Resonance - Frequency	=	W_0	=	54.184773×10^{15} Hz
Energy	=	Q_0	=	5.7141×10^{-18} J
LC - Circuit-Coupling	=	LC_{LC}	=	18.455×10^{-16} Farad/s
Wavelength - λ	=	λ_{2L}	=	0.433245×10^{-10} m
Wave Amplitude	=	A_{wave}	=	0.6238×10^{-25} m
Inductance	=	L	=	1×10^{-19} Hz
Capacity	=	C	=	3.406007×10^{-15} Farad
Resonance-Voltage	=	V_R	=	$1677.657594 \times 10^{-9}$ Volt
Voltage across Inductor	=	V_L	=	3.0961×10^{-20} eV
Power of LC-System	=	P_{CL}	=	95.863×10^{-22} Watt
Loudness of Resonance-Power	=	P_{RL}	=	167.3388 Decibel
Maximum Flowing Current	=	I_{max}	=	$309.617908 \times 10^{-3}$ Ampere
Capacity Discharged Period	=	T_s	=	0.2898×10^{-16} s
Radiation - Thermal	=	T_K	=	83.668223 Kelvin
Radiation - Frequency	=	f_{RAD}	=	$-174.330105 \times 10^{10}$ Hz
Conversion - Temperature	=	T_V	=	0.0304 Kelvin
Radius In Cleft	=	r_{LC}	=	5.527411×10^{-17} m
Diameter of Compound	=	d_{com}	=	12.632979 \AA

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